

M4L Technical Report

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Abstract

This report contains the full rules, a selection of which are shown in the main body of the M4L paper. Section 1 describes the syntax, Section 2 describes the typing rules for expressions (Figure 1), scoped statements (Figure 2), and statements (Figure 3). Section 3 describes the evaluation rules for expressions (Figure 4), scoped statements (Figure 5), and statements (Figure 6). Section 3.2 axiomatizes the types of the values being returned by the cryptographic protocols for ORAMs. Section 4 describes the trace semantics for expressions (Figure 7), scoped statements (Figure 8), and statements (Figure 9). Section 5 describes the reference semantics and Section 6 has rules for typing values. Using the auxilliary definitions of Section 7, Section 8 states the lemmas required to prove the correctness theorem. Finally, Section 9 proves these lemmas.

1 Intermediate language syntax

Party Set	$p ::=$ A set of integers
Label	$\ell ::= p \mid s$
Base Type	$\gamma ::= \text{uint} \mid \text{bool}$
Type	$\tau ::= \gamma_\ell \mid \gamma_\ell[n] \mid \text{oram}[n]$
Constant	$c ::= n \mid \text{true} \mid \text{false}$
Expression	$e ::= c \mid x \mid e_1 \oplus e_2 \mid e_1 > e_2 \mid [\overline{e_i}]_n \mid x[e] \mid e_1? e_2 : e_3 \mid \text{Oram}(e)$
Scoped Statement	$s ::= \tau x = e \mid x = e \mid \text{for } x \text{ in } [n_1, n_2] \text{ do } S \mid x[e_1] = e_2 \mid \text{if}(e, S_1, S_2) \mid$ $\mid \text{input}(x, \tau) \mid y = \text{OramRead}(x, e) \mid \text{OramWrite}(x, e_1, e_2) \mid s_1; s_2$
Statement	$S ::= \text{as}(p, s) \mid \gamma_p x_1 = \text{reveal}(x_2, p) \mid \gamma_s x_1 = \text{makesh}(x_2, p)$ $\mid \gamma_s x_1 = \text{reshare}(x_2, p) \mid \gamma_p x_1 = \text{broadcast}(x_2, p) \mid S_1; S_2$
Program	$\sigma ::= S$

2 Type system for intermediate language

2.1 Expression type checking

The typing environment Γ maps variables x to (τ, p) . $\Gamma \vdash_p e : \tau, p$, means that under the type environment Γ and party context p , the expression e has type τ, p . τ, p is a shorthand for $(t_1, \dots, t_n)$ where $t_i = \tau$ for all $i \in p$ and $\perp$ otherwise.

$\boxed{\Gamma \vdash e : \tau, p}$	$\frac{\text{T-UINT}}{\Gamma \vdash n : \text{uint}_{\mathbf{p}}, p}$	$\frac{\text{T-BOOL}}{e \in \{\text{true}, \text{false}\}}{\Gamma \vdash e : \text{bool}_{\mathbf{p}}, p}$
$\frac{\text{T-BINOP}}{\forall i \in \{1, 2\} \Gamma \vdash e_i : \text{uint}_{\ell_i}, p}{\mathcal{J}(\ell_1, \ell_2) = \ell}}{\Gamma \vdash e_1 \oplus e_2 : \text{uint}_{\ell}, p}$	$\frac{\text{T-GT}}{\forall i \in \{1, 2\} \Gamma \vdash e_i : \text{uint}_{\ell_i}, p}{\mathcal{J}(\ell_1, \ell_2) = \ell}}{\Gamma \vdash e_1 > e_2 : \text{bool}_{\ell}, p}$	$\frac{\text{T-MUX}}{\Gamma \vdash e : \text{bool}_{\ell}, p}{\forall i \in \{1, 2\}, \Gamma \vdash e_i : \gamma_{\ell_i}, p}{\mathcal{J}(\ell, \ell_1, \ell_2) = \ell}}{\Gamma \vdash e? e_1 : e_2 : \gamma_{\ell}, p}$
$\frac{\text{T-ARR}}{\forall i \in [n], \Gamma \vdash e_i : \gamma_{\ell}, p}{\Gamma \vdash [\bar{e}_i]_n : \gamma_{\ell}[n], p}$	$\frac{\text{T-ARR_READ}}{\Gamma \vdash x : \gamma_{\ell}[n], p}{\Gamma \vdash e : \text{uint}_{\mathbf{p}}, p}{\Gamma \models e < n}}{\Gamma \vdash x[e] : \gamma_{\ell}, p}$	$\frac{\text{T-ORAM}}{\Gamma \vdash e : \text{uint}_{\mathbf{s}}[n], p}{\Gamma \vdash \text{Oram}(e) : \text{oram}[n], p}$

Figure 1. Expression typing judgment

Join function

$$\boxed{\mathcal{J}(\ell_1, \ell_2) = \ell}$$

- $\mathcal{J}(\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{s}) = \mathbf{s}$
- $\mathcal{J}(\ell, \ell) = \ell$
- Symmetric: $\mathcal{J}(\ell_1, \ell_2) = \ell \implies \mathcal{J}(\ell_2, \ell_1) = \ell$
- $\mathcal{J}(\ell_1, \ell_2, \ell_3) \triangleq \mathcal{J}(\ell_1, \mathcal{J}(\ell_2, \ell_3))$

2.2 Scoped statement type checking

$\Gamma \vdash_p s \mid \Gamma'$ means that under type environment Γ and party context p , the statement type-checks and modifies the type environment to Γ' .

$$\boxed{\Gamma \vdash_p s \mid \Gamma'}$$

$\text{T-DEF} \frac{x \notin \Gamma \quad \Gamma \vdash e : \tau, p \quad \text{secret } \tau \implies \neg \text{singleton}(p)}{\Gamma \vdash_p \tau \ x = e \mid \Gamma, x : (\tau, p)}$	$\text{T-ARR_WRITE} \frac{\Gamma \vdash x : \gamma_\ell[n], p \quad \Gamma \vdash e_1 : \text{uint}_p, p \quad \Gamma \vdash e_2 : \gamma_\ell, p \quad \Gamma \models e_1 < n}{\Gamma \vdash_p x[e_1] = e_2 \mid \Gamma}$	$\text{T-ORAM_READ} \frac{\Gamma \vdash x : \text{oram}[n], p \quad \Gamma \vdash e : \text{uint}_\ell, p \quad y \notin \Gamma}{\Gamma \vdash_p y = \text{OramRead}(x, e) \mid \Gamma, y : (\text{uint}_s, p)}$
$\text{T-ORAM_WRITE} \frac{\Gamma \vdash x : \text{oram}[n], p \quad \Gamma \vdash e_1 : \text{uint}_{\ell_1}, p \quad \Gamma \vdash e_2 : \text{uint}_{\ell_2}, p}{\Gamma \vdash_p \text{OramWrite}(x, e_1, e_2) \mid \Gamma}$	$\text{T-IF} \frac{\Gamma \vdash e : \text{bool}_p, p \quad \forall i \in \{1, 2\}. \Gamma \vdash S_i \mid _ \quad \text{party}(\Gamma, S_1) \cup \text{party}(\Gamma, S_2) = p}{\Gamma \vdash_p \text{if}(e, S_1, S_2) \mid \Gamma}$	$\text{T-ASSIGN} \frac{\Gamma \vdash x : (\gamma_\ell, p) \quad \Gamma \vdash e : \gamma_\ell, p}{\Gamma \vdash_p x = e \mid \Gamma}$
$\text{T-FOR} \frac{x \notin \Gamma \quad \text{party}(\Gamma, S) = p \quad \Gamma, x : (\text{uint}_p, p) \vdash S \mid _}{\Gamma \vdash_p \text{for } x \text{ in } [n_1, n_2] \text{ do } S \mid \Gamma}$	$\text{T-INPUT} \frac{\text{singleton}(p) \quad x \notin \Gamma \quad \text{public } \tau}{\Gamma \vdash_p \text{input}(x, \tau) \mid \Gamma, x : (\tau, p)}$	$\text{T-SEQ} \frac{\Gamma \vdash_p s_1 \mid \Gamma' \quad \Gamma' \vdash_p s_2 \mid \Gamma''}{\Gamma \vdash_p s_1; s_2 \mid \Gamma''}$

Figure 2. Scoped statement typing judgment

2.3 Statement type checking

$\Gamma \vdash S \mid \Gamma'$ means that under type environment Γ , S type checks and modifies Γ to Γ' .

$$\boxed{\Gamma \vdash S \mid \Gamma'}$$

$\text{T-AS} \frac{\Gamma \vdash_p s \mid \Gamma'}{\Gamma \vdash \text{as}(p, s) \mid \Gamma'}$	$\text{T-ANNOT_SEQ} \frac{\Gamma \vdash S_1 \mid \Gamma' \quad \Gamma' \vdash S_2 \mid \Gamma''}{\Gamma \vdash S_1; S_2 \mid \Gamma''}$
$\text{T-REVEAL} \frac{\Gamma(x_2) = (\gamma_s, p') \quad x_1 \notin \Gamma}{\Gamma \vdash \gamma_p \ x_1 = \text{reveal}(x_2, p) \mid \Gamma, x_1 : (\gamma_p, p)}$	$\text{T-MAKESH} \frac{\Gamma(x_2) = (\gamma_p, p') \quad \neg \text{singleton}(p) \quad x_1 \notin \Gamma}{\Gamma \vdash \gamma_s \ x_1 = \text{makesh}(x_2, p) \mid \Gamma, x_1 : (\gamma_s, p)}$
$\text{T-RESHARE} \frac{\Gamma(x_2) = (\gamma_s, p') \quad \neg \text{singleton}(p) \quad x_1 \notin \Gamma}{\Gamma \vdash \gamma_s \ x_1 = \text{reshare}(x_2, p) \mid \Gamma, x_1 : (\gamma_s, p)}$	$\text{T-BROADCAST} \frac{\Gamma(x_2) = (\gamma_p, p') \quad x_1 \notin \Gamma}{\Gamma \vdash \gamma_p \ x_1 = \text{broadcast}(x_2, p) \mid \Gamma, x_1 : (\gamma_p, p)}$

Figure 3. Statement typing judgment

NOTES:

- The function $\text{party}(S)$ is defined as:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{party}(\text{as}(p, s)) &= p \\ \text{party}(\gamma_p \ x_1 = \text{reveal}(x_2, s, p)) &= p \cup p' \text{ where } \Gamma(x_2) = (\tau, p') \\ \text{party}(\gamma_s \ x_1 = \text{makesh}(x_2, p, s)) &= p \cup p' \text{ where } \Gamma(x_2) = (\tau, p') \\ \text{party}(\gamma_{s_1} \ x_1 = \text{reshare}(x_2, s_2, p, s_1)) &= p \cup p' \text{ where } \Gamma(x_2) = (\tau, p') \\ \text{party}(S_1; S_2) &= \text{party}(S_1) \cup \text{party}(S_2) \end{aligned}$$

- The predicate $\text{singleton}(p)$ is true if the party set p is a Singleton set.

3 Evaluation semantics

3.1 Runtime Value syntax

Base Value Component	$bv ::= c \mid \text{sh } c$
Value Component	$u ::= bv \mid [bv_i]_n \mid \text{oramst} \mid \perp$
Value	$v ::= (u_1, \dots, u_m)$

$\rho \vdash_p e \Downarrow v$

$\frac{v = \text{makeval}(c, p)}{\rho \vdash_p c \Downarrow v}$	$\frac{v = \rho(x) _p}{\rho \vdash_p x \Downarrow v}$	$\frac{\begin{array}{l} \text{E-BINOP} \\ \rho \vdash_p e_1 \Downarrow v_1 \\ \rho \vdash_p e_2 \Downarrow v_2 \\ v = \oplus_{\ell_1 \ell_2}(v_1, v_2) \end{array}}{\rho \vdash_p e_1 \oplus e_2 \Downarrow v}$	$\frac{\begin{array}{l} \text{E-GT} \\ \rho \vdash_p e_1 \Downarrow v_1 \\ \rho \vdash_p e_2 \Downarrow v_2 \\ v = >_{\ell_1 \ell_2}(v_1, v_2) \end{array}}{\rho \vdash_p e_1 > e_2 \Downarrow v}$
$\frac{\begin{array}{l} \text{E-TERNARY} \\ \rho \vdash_p e_1 \Downarrow v_1 \quad \rho \vdash_p e_2 \Downarrow v_2 \quad \rho \vdash_p e_3 \Downarrow v_3 \\ v = ?_{\ell_1 \ell_2 \ell_3}(v_1, v_2, v_3) \end{array}}{\rho \vdash_p e_1 ? e_2 : e_3 \Downarrow v}$	$\frac{\begin{array}{l} \text{E-ORAM} \\ \rho \vdash_p e \Downarrow v' \\ v = \text{convert}(v') \end{array}}{\rho \vdash_p \text{Oram}(e) \Downarrow v}$	$\frac{\begin{array}{l} \text{E-ARR} \\ \forall i \in [n], \rho \vdash_p e_i \Downarrow v_i \\ \forall j \in p, \pi_j(v) = [\pi_j(v_1), \dots, \pi_j(v_n)] \\ \forall j \notin p, \pi_j(v) = \perp \end{array}}{\rho \vdash_p [\bar{e}_i]_n \Downarrow v}$	
$\frac{\begin{array}{l} \text{E-ARR_READ} \\ \rho \vdash_p x \Downarrow v_1 \quad \rho \vdash_p e \Downarrow v_2 \\ v = \text{select}(v_1, v_2) \end{array}}{\rho \vdash_p x[e] \Downarrow v}$			

Figure 4. Expression Evaluation

$\rho \vdash_p s \Downarrow \rho'$

$\frac{\begin{array}{l} \text{E-ORAM_READ} \\ \rho \vdash_p x \Downarrow v \quad \rho \vdash_p e \Downarrow v_1 \quad v', v_2 = \mathcal{OR}(v, v_1) \end{array}}{\rho \vdash_p y = \text{OramRead}(x, e) \Downarrow \rho[y \mapsto v_2][x \mapsto v']}$		
$\frac{\rho \vdash_p e \Downarrow v}{\rho \vdash_p \tau x = e \Downarrow \rho[x \mapsto v]}$	$\frac{\rho \vdash_p e \Downarrow v}{\rho \vdash_p x = e \Downarrow \rho[x \mapsto v]}$	
$\frac{\begin{array}{l} \text{E-ARR_WRITE} \\ \rho \vdash_p x \Downarrow v \quad \rho \vdash_p e_1 \Downarrow v_1 \quad \rho \vdash_p e_2 \Downarrow v_2 \\ v' = \text{update}(v, v_1, v_2) \end{array}}{\rho \vdash_p x[e_1] = e_2 \Downarrow \rho[x \mapsto v']}$	$\frac{\begin{array}{l} \text{E-ORAM_WRITE} \\ \rho \vdash_p x \Downarrow v \quad \rho \vdash_p e_1 \Downarrow v_1 \quad \rho \vdash_p e_2 \Downarrow v_2 \\ v' = \mathcal{OW}(v, v_1, v_2) \end{array}}{\rho \vdash_p \text{OramWrite}(x, e_1, e_2) \Downarrow \rho[x \mapsto v]},$	
$\frac{n_1 > n_2}{\rho \vdash_p \text{for } x \text{ in } [n_1, n_2] \text{ do } S \Downarrow \rho}$	$\frac{\begin{array}{l} \text{E-FORI} \\ n_1 \leq n_2 \quad \rho[x \mapsto \text{makeval}(n_1, p)] \vdash S \Downarrow \rho' \\ n'_1 = n_1 + 1 \quad \rho' \vdash_p \text{for } x \text{ in } [n'_1, n_2] \text{ do } S \Downarrow \rho'' \end{array}}{\rho \vdash_p \text{for } x \text{ in } [n_1, n_2] \text{ do } S \Downarrow \rho''}$	
$\frac{\begin{array}{l} \text{E-IF} \\ \rho \vdash_p e \Downarrow v \\ \text{istrue}(v, p) \implies S = S_1 \\ \text{isfalse}(v, p) \implies S = S_2 \\ \rho \vdash_p S \Downarrow \rho' \end{array}}{\rho \vdash_p \text{if}(e, S_1, S_2) \Downarrow \rho'}$	$\frac{\begin{array}{l} \text{E-INPUT} \\ v = \text{userin}(\tau, p) \end{array}}{\rho \vdash_p \text{input}(x, \tau) \Downarrow \rho[x \mapsto v]}$	$\frac{\begin{array}{l} \text{E-SEQ} \\ \rho \vdash_p s_1 \Downarrow \rho' \\ \rho' \vdash_p s_2 \Downarrow \rho'' \end{array}}{\rho \vdash_p s_1; s_2 \Downarrow \rho''}$

Figure 5. Scoped statement evaluation

$$\boxed{\rho \vdash S \Downarrow \rho'}$$

$$\begin{array}{c}
\text{E-AS} \\
\frac{\rho \vdash_p s \Downarrow \rho'}{\rho \vdash \text{as}(p, s) \Downarrow \rho'} \\
\\
\text{E-REVEAL} \\
\frac{v = \mathcal{D}(\rho(x_2), p) \quad \rho' = \rho[x_1 \mapsto v]}{\rho \vdash \gamma_p x_1 = \text{reveal}(x_2, p) \Downarrow \rho'} \\
\\
\text{E-MAKESH} \\
\frac{v = \mathcal{E}(\rho(x_2), p) \quad \rho' = \rho[x_1 \mapsto v]}{\rho \vdash \gamma_s x_1 = \text{makesh}(x_2, p, s) \Downarrow \rho'} \\
\\
\text{E-RESHARE} \\
\frac{v = \mathcal{R}(\rho(x_2), p) \quad \rho' = \rho[x_1 \mapsto v]}{\rho \vdash \gamma_s x_1 = \text{reshare}(x_2, p) \Downarrow \rho'} \\
\\
\text{E-ANNOT_SEQ} \\
\frac{\rho \vdash S_1 \Downarrow \rho' \quad \rho' \vdash S_2 \Downarrow \rho''}{\rho \vdash S_1; S_2 \Downarrow \rho''} \\
\\
\text{E-BROADCAST} \\
\frac{v = \mathcal{P}(\rho(x_2), p) \quad \rho' = \rho[x_1 \mapsto v]}{\rho \vdash \gamma_p x_1 = \text{broadcast}(x_2, p) \Downarrow \rho'}
\end{array}$$

Figure 6. Statement evaluation

NOTES:

- $\pi_i(a)$ means the i -th element of the tuple a .
- $\text{makeval}(c, p) = v$ s.t. $\pi_i(v) = c$ if $i \in p$ and $\perp$ otherwise.
- $v|_p = v'$ s.t. $\pi_i(v') = \pi_i(v)$ if $i \in p$ and $\perp$ otherwise.
- $\text{istrue}(v)$ is true if the non-bot elements of v are true otherwise false.
- $\text{select}(v_1, \text{sh}_p p i) = v$ where $\pi_j(v) = \perp$ if $j \notin p$ otherwise $\pi_j(v) = \pi_j(v_1)[i]$
- $\text{update}(v, \text{sh}_p p c, v_2) = v'$ where
 1. $\forall i \notin p, \pi_i(v') = \perp$
 2. $\forall i \in p, \pi_i(v')[c] = \pi_i(v_2)$
 3. $\forall i \in p, \forall j \neq c, \pi_i(v')[j] = \pi_i(v)[j]$
- $\text{convert}(v) = v'$ where
 1. $\forall j \in [m], \pi_j(v) = [bv_i]_n \implies \pi_j(v') = \langle bv_i \rangle_n$
 2. $\forall j \in [m], \pi_j(v) = \perp \implies \pi_j(v') = \perp$

3.2 Auxiliary axioms

Axiom 1. $\vdash \text{userin}(\tau, p) : \tau, p$

Axiom 2. *If*

- $\vdash v_1 : \text{oram}_\gamma[n], p$
- $\vdash v_2 : \text{uint}_\ell, p$
- $v'_1, v_3 = \mathcal{OR}(v_1, v_2)$

then,

- $\vdash v'_1 : \text{oram}[n], p$
- $\vdash v_3 : \text{uint}_s, p$

Axiom 3. *If*

- $\vdash v_1 : \text{oram}[n], p$
- $\vdash v_2 : \text{uint}_{\ell_1}, p$

– $\vdash v_3 : \text{uint}_{\ell_2}, p$

then, $\vdash \mathcal{OW}(v_1, v_2, v_3) : \text{oram}[n], p$

Axiom 4. *If*

– $\vdash v_1 : \text{oram}[n], p$

– $\vdash v_2 : \text{uint}_{\ell}, p$

– $v'_1, v_3 = \mathcal{OR}(v_1, v_2)$

– $v_1 \sim \hat{v}_1$

– $v_2 \sim \hat{v}_2$

– $\hat{v}' = ((0 \leq \hat{v}_2 < n) ? \hat{v}_1[\hat{v}_2] : 0)$

then,

– $v'_1 \sim \hat{v}_1$

– $v_3 \sim \hat{v}'$

Axiom 5. *If*

– $\vdash v_1 : \text{oram}[n], p$

– $\vdash v_2 : \text{uint}_{\ell_1}, p$

– $\vdash v_3 : \text{uint}_{\ell_2}, p$

– $v_1 \sim [\bar{c}_i]_n, p$

– $v_2 \sim c_1, p$

– $v_3 \sim c_2, p$

– u' is such that

* $\forall i \in [n] \text{ s.t. } i \neq c_1, u'[i] = \bar{c}_i$

* $u'[c_1] = c_2 \text{ if } 0 \leq c_1 < n$

then, $\mathcal{OW}(v_1, v_2, v_3) \sim u', p$

4 Trace semantics

Trace	$\mathcal{T} ::= \emptyset \mid \langle P_i, P_j, \text{msg} \rangle :: \mathcal{T}'$
Observation	$\mathcal{O} ::= \emptyset \mid (c, p) :: \mathcal{O}'$
Side-effects	$\mathcal{G} ::= \emptyset \mid (d, p) :: \mathcal{G}'$

$$\boxed{\rho \vdash_p e \Downarrow v, \mathcal{T}}$$

$\frac{\text{A-CONSTANT}}{\rho \vdash_p c \Downarrow v, \emptyset}$	$\frac{\text{A-VAR}}{\rho \vdash_p x \Downarrow v, \emptyset}$	$\frac{\text{A-BINOP}}{\rho \vdash_p e_1 \oplus e_2 \Downarrow v, \mathcal{T}_1 \mathcal{T}_2 \mathcal{T}_3}$	$\frac{\text{A-GT}}{\rho \vdash_p e_1 > e_2 \Downarrow v, \mathcal{T}_1 \mathcal{T}_2 \mathcal{T}_3}$
$\frac{\text{A-MUX}}{\rho \vdash_p e_1 ? e_2 : e_3 \Downarrow v, \mathcal{T}_1 \mathcal{T}_2 \mathcal{T}_3 \mathcal{T}_4}$	$\frac{\text{A-ORAM}}{\rho \vdash_p \text{Oram}(e) \Downarrow v, \mathcal{T}}$	$\frac{\text{A-ARR}}{\rho \vdash_p [\bar{e}_i]_n \Downarrow v, \mathcal{T}_1 \cdots \mathcal{T}_n}$	
$\frac{\text{A-ARR_READ}}{\rho \vdash_p x[e] \Downarrow v, \mathcal{T}_1 \mathcal{T}_2}$			

Figure 7. Augmented expression evaluation

$$\boxed{\rho \vdash_p s \Downarrow \rho', \mathcal{T}, \mathcal{O}, \mathcal{G}}$$

$\frac{\text{A-ORAM_READ}}{\rho \vdash_p y = \text{OramRead}(x, e) \Downarrow \rho[y \mapsto v_2][x \mapsto v'], \mathcal{T} \mathcal{T}_1 \mathcal{T}', \emptyset, \emptyset}$		
$\frac{\text{A-DEF}}{\rho \vdash_p \tau x = e \Downarrow \rho[x \mapsto v], \mathcal{T}, \emptyset, \emptyset}$	$\frac{\text{A-ASSIGN}}{\rho \vdash_p x = e \Downarrow \rho[x \mapsto v], \mathcal{T}, \emptyset, \emptyset}$	
$\frac{\text{A-ARR_WRITE}}{\rho \vdash_p x[e_1] = e_2 \Downarrow \rho[x \mapsto v'], \mathcal{T} \mathcal{T}_1 \mathcal{T}_2, \emptyset, \emptyset}$	$\frac{\text{A-ORAM_WRITE}}{\rho \vdash_p \text{OramWrite}(x, e_1, e_2) \Downarrow \rho[x \mapsto v'], \mathcal{T} \mathcal{T}_1 \mathcal{T}_2 \mathcal{T}', \emptyset, \emptyset}$	
$\frac{\text{A-FOR_EXIT}}{\rho \vdash_p \text{for } x \text{ in } [n_1, n_2] \text{ do } S \Downarrow \rho, \emptyset, \emptyset, \emptyset}$	$\frac{\text{A-FORI}}{\rho \vdash_p \text{for } x \text{ in } [n_1, n_2] \text{ do } S \Downarrow \rho'', \mathcal{T}' \mathcal{T}'', \mathcal{O}' \mathcal{O}'', \mathcal{G}' \mathcal{G}''}$	
$\frac{\text{A-IF}}{\rho \vdash_p \text{if}(e, S_1, S_2) \Downarrow \rho', \mathcal{T} \mathcal{T}', \mathcal{O}, \mathcal{G}}$	$\frac{\text{A-INPUT}}{\rho \vdash_p \text{input}(x, \tau) \Downarrow \rho[x \mapsto v], \emptyset, \emptyset, (d, p)}$	$\frac{\text{A-SEQ}}{\rho \vdash_p s_1 ; s_2 \Downarrow \rho'', \mathcal{T}' \mathcal{T}'', \mathcal{O}' \mathcal{O}'', \mathcal{G}' \mathcal{G}''}$

Figure 8. Augmented scoped statement evaluation

$$\boxed{\rho \vdash S \Downarrow \rho', \mathcal{T}, \mathcal{O}, \mathcal{G}}$$

$$\text{A-AS} \quad \frac{\rho \vdash_p s \Downarrow \rho', \mathcal{T}, \mathcal{O}, \mathcal{G}}{\rho \vdash \text{as}(p, s) \Downarrow \rho', \mathcal{T}, \mathcal{O}, \mathcal{G}}$$

$$\text{A-REVEAL} \quad \frac{v, \mathcal{T} = \mathcal{D}(\rho(x_2), p) \quad v = \text{sh}_p p c \quad \rho' = \rho[x_1 \mapsto v]}{\rho \vdash \gamma_p x_1 = \text{reveal}(x_2, p) \Downarrow \rho', \mathcal{T}, (c, p), \emptyset}$$

$$\text{A-MAKESH} \quad \frac{\rho(x_2) = \text{sh}_p p' c \quad v, \mathcal{T} = \mathcal{E}(\rho(x_2), p) \quad \rho' = \rho[x_1 \mapsto v]}{\rho \vdash \gamma_s x_1 = \text{makesh}(x_2, p, s) \Downarrow \rho', \mathcal{T}, \emptyset, (c, p)}$$

$$\text{A-RESHARE} \quad \frac{\rho(x_2) = \text{sh}_s p' c \quad v, \mathcal{T} = \mathcal{R}(\rho(x_2), p) \quad \rho' = \rho[x_1 \mapsto v]}{\rho \vdash \gamma_s x_1 = \text{reshare}(x_2, p) \Downarrow \rho', \mathcal{T}, \emptyset, (c, p)}$$

$$\text{A-BROADCAST} \quad \frac{v, \mathcal{T} = \mathcal{P}(\rho(x_2), p) \quad v = \text{sh}_p p c \quad \rho' = \rho[x_1 \mapsto v]}{\rho \vdash \gamma_p x_1 = \text{broadcast}(x_2, p) \Downarrow \rho', \mathcal{T}, (c, p), \emptyset}$$

$$\text{A-ANNOT_SEQ} \quad \frac{\begin{array}{l} \rho \vdash S_1 \Downarrow \rho', \mathcal{T}', \mathcal{O}', \mathcal{G}' \\ \rho' \vdash S_2 \Downarrow \rho'', \mathcal{T}'', \mathcal{O}'', \mathcal{G}'' \end{array}}{\rho \vdash S_1; S_2 \Downarrow \rho'', \mathcal{T}'\mathcal{T}'', \mathcal{O}'\mathcal{O}'', \mathcal{G}'\mathcal{G}''}$$

Figure 9. Augmented statement evaluation

5 Reference semantics

Value $\hat{v} ::= c, p \mid [c_i]_n, p$

The store μ maps each variable to a value $\hat{v}$.

$\mu \vdash_p e \downarrow \hat{v}$	$\mu \vdash_p s \downarrow \mu', \hat{O}, \hat{\mathcal{F}}$	$\mu \vdash S \downarrow \mu', \hat{O}, \hat{\mathcal{F}}$	
$\frac{\text{R-CONSTANT} \quad \hat{v} = c, p}{\mu \vdash_p c \downarrow \hat{v}}$		$\frac{\text{R-VAR}}{\mu \vdash_p x \downarrow \mu(x) _p}$	
$\frac{\text{R-GT} \quad \mu \vdash_p e_1 \downarrow c_1, p \quad \mu \vdash_p e_2 \downarrow c_2, p}{\mu \vdash_p e_1 > e_2 \downarrow (c_1 > c_2), p}$		$\frac{\text{R-BINOP} \quad \mu \vdash_p e_1 \downarrow c_1, p \quad \mu \vdash_p e_2 \downarrow c_2, p}{\mu \vdash_p e_1 \oplus e_2 \downarrow (c_1 \oplus c_2), p}$	
$\frac{\text{R-MUX} \quad \mu \vdash_p e_1 \downarrow c_1, p \quad \mu \vdash_p e_2 \downarrow c_2, p \quad \mu \vdash_p e_3 \downarrow c_3, p}{\mu \vdash_p e_1 ? e_2 : e_3 \downarrow ?(c_1, c_2, c_3), p}$		$\frac{\text{R-ARR} \quad \forall i \in [n], \mu \vdash_p e_i \downarrow c_i, p \quad \hat{v} = [c_1, \dots, c_n], p}{\mu \vdash_p [\hat{e}_i]_n \downarrow \hat{v}}$	
$\frac{\text{R-ARR_READ} \quad \mu \vdash_p x \downarrow [\hat{c}_i]_n, p \quad \mu \vdash_p e \downarrow c, p \quad u = [\hat{c}_i]_n \quad \hat{v} = u[c], p}{\mu \vdash_p x[e] \downarrow \hat{v}}$		$\frac{\text{R-ORAM} \quad \mu \vdash_p e \downarrow \hat{v}}{\mu \vdash_p \text{Oram}(e) \downarrow \hat{v}}$	
$\frac{\text{R-ASSIGN} \quad \mu \vdash_p e \downarrow \hat{v}}{\mu \vdash_p x = e \downarrow \mu[x \mapsto \hat{v}], \emptyset, \emptyset}$		$\frac{\text{R-DEF} \quad \mu \vdash_p e \downarrow \hat{v}}{\mu \vdash_p \tau x = e \downarrow \mu[x \mapsto \hat{v}], \emptyset, \emptyset}$	
$\frac{\text{R-ORAM_READ} \quad \mu \vdash_p x \downarrow [\hat{c}_i]_n, p \quad \mu \vdash_p e \downarrow c, p \quad u = [\hat{c}_i]_n \quad \hat{v} = ((0 \leq c < n) ? u[c] : 0), p}{\mu \vdash_p y = \text{OramRead}(x, e) \downarrow \mu[y \mapsto \hat{v}], \emptyset, \emptyset}$			
$\frac{\text{R-ARR_WRITE} \quad \mu \vdash_p x \downarrow [\hat{c}_i]_n, p \quad \mu \vdash_p e_1 \downarrow c_1, p \quad \mu \vdash_p e_2 \downarrow c_2, p \quad u = [\hat{c}_i]_n \quad \forall i \in [n] \text{ s.t. } i \neq c_1, u'[i] = u[i] \quad u'[c_1] = c_2 \quad \hat{v}' = u', p}{\mu \vdash_p x[e_1] = e_2 \downarrow \mu[x \mapsto \hat{v}'], \emptyset, \emptyset}$		$\frac{\text{R-ORAM_WRITE} \quad \mu \vdash_p x \downarrow [\hat{c}_i]_n, p \quad \mu \vdash_p e_1 \downarrow c_1, p \quad \mu \vdash_p e_2 \downarrow c_2, p \quad u = [\hat{c}_i]_n \quad \forall i \in [n] \text{ s.t. } i \neq c_1, u'[i] = u[i] \quad 0 \leq c_1 < n \Rightarrow u'[c_1] = c_2 \quad \hat{v}' = u', p}{\mu \vdash_p \text{OramWrite}(x, e_1, e_2) \downarrow \mu[x \mapsto \hat{v}'], \emptyset, \emptyset}$	
$\frac{\text{R-FOR_EXIT} \quad n_1 > n_2}{\mu \vdash_p \text{for } x \text{ in } [n_1, n_2] \text{ do } S \downarrow \mu, \emptyset, \emptyset}$		$\frac{\text{R-FORI} \quad n_1 \leq n_2 \quad \mu[x \mapsto (n_1, p)] \vdash S \downarrow \mu', \hat{O}', \hat{\mathcal{F}}' \quad n'_1 = n_1 + 1 \quad \mu' \vdash_p \text{for } x \text{ in } [n'_1, n_2] \text{ do } S \downarrow \mu'', \hat{O}'', \hat{\mathcal{F}}''}{\mu \vdash_p \text{for } x \text{ in } [n_1, n_2] \text{ do } S \downarrow \mu'', \hat{O}'\hat{O}'', \hat{\mathcal{F}}'\hat{\mathcal{F}}''}$	
$\frac{\text{R-IF} \quad \mu \vdash_p e \downarrow \hat{v} \quad \text{istrue}(\hat{v}) \implies S = S_1 \quad \neg \text{istrue}(\hat{v}) \implies S = S_2 \quad \mu \vdash S \downarrow \mu', \hat{O}, \hat{\mathcal{F}}}{\mu \vdash_p \text{if}(e, S_1, S_2) \downarrow \mu', \hat{O}, \hat{\mathcal{F}}}$		$\frac{\text{R-INPUT} \quad \hat{v} = \text{userin}(\tau, p)}{\mu \vdash_p \text{input}(x, \tau) \downarrow \mu[x \mapsto \hat{v}], \emptyset, \hat{v}}$	
$\frac{\text{R-SEQ} \quad \mu \vdash_p s_1 \downarrow \mu', \hat{O}', \hat{\mathcal{F}}' \quad \mu' \vdash_p s_2 \downarrow \mu'', \hat{O}'', \hat{\mathcal{F}}''}{\mu \vdash_p s_1; s_2 \downarrow \mu'', \hat{O}'\hat{O}'', \hat{\mathcal{F}}'\hat{\mathcal{F}}''}$			
$\frac{\text{R-AS} \quad \mu \vdash_p s \downarrow \mu', \hat{O}, \hat{\mathcal{F}}}{\mu \vdash \text{as}(p, s) \downarrow \mu', \hat{O}, \hat{\mathcal{F}}}$		$\frac{\text{R-REVEAL} \quad \mu(x_2) = c, _ \quad \hat{v} = (c, p)}{\mu \vdash \gamma x_1 = \text{reveal}(x_2, p) \downarrow \mu[x_1 \mapsto \hat{v}], \hat{v}, \emptyset}$	
$\frac{\text{R-MAKESH} \quad \mu(x_2) = c, _ \quad \hat{v} = (c, p)}{\mu \vdash \gamma x_1 = \text{makesh}(x_2, p) \downarrow \mu[x_1 \mapsto \hat{v}], \emptyset, \hat{v}}$			
$\frac{\text{R-RESHARE} \quad \mu(x_2) = c, _ \quad \hat{v} = (c, p)}{\mu \vdash \gamma x_1 = \text{reshare}(x_2, p) \downarrow \mu[x_1 \mapsto \hat{v}], \emptyset, \hat{v}}$		$\frac{\text{R-BROADCAST} \quad \mu(x_2) = c, _ \quad \hat{v} = (c, p)}{\mu \vdash \gamma_P x_1 = \text{broadcast}(x_2, p) \downarrow \rho[x_1 \mapsto \hat{v}], \emptyset, \emptyset}$	
		$\frac{\text{R-ANNOT_SEQ} \quad \mu \vdash S_1 \downarrow \mu', \hat{O}', \hat{\mathcal{F}}' \quad \mu' \vdash S_2 \downarrow \mu'', \hat{O}'', \hat{\mathcal{F}}''}{\mu \vdash S_1; S_2 \downarrow \mu'', \hat{O}'\hat{O}'', \hat{\mathcal{F}}'\hat{\mathcal{F}}''}$	

Figure 10. Reference evaluation

NOTES:

- $\hat{v}|_p = c, p$ if $\hat{v} = c, _$ and $[c_1, \dots, c_n], p$ if $\hat{v} = [c_1, \dots, c_n], _$

6 Value typing

$\frac{\text{V-NAT}}{\vdash n : \text{uint}_p}$	$\frac{\text{V-TRUE}}{\vdash \text{true} : \text{bool}_p}$	$\frac{\text{V-FALSE}}{\vdash \text{false} : \text{bool}_p}$	$\frac{\text{V-SHARE}}{\vdash c : \gamma_p}$ $\vdash \text{sh}_s c : \gamma_s$
$\frac{\text{V-ARR}}{\forall i \in [n], \vdash bv_i : \gamma_\ell}$ $\vdash [bv_i]_n : \gamma_\ell[n]$	$\frac{\text{V-ORAM}}{\forall i \in [n], \vdash bv_i : \text{uint}_s}$ $\vdash \langle bv_i \rangle_n : \text{oram}[n]$	$\frac{\text{V-BOT}}{\vdash \perp : \perp}$	$\frac{\text{V-STORE}}{\forall i \in p, \vdash \nu_i : \tau}$ $\forall i \notin p, \vdash \nu_i : \perp$ $\vdash (\nu_1, \dots, \nu_m) : \tau, p$
	$\frac{\text{V-REF1}}{\vdash c : \gamma_p}$ $\vdash c, p : \gamma_p, p$	$\frac{\text{V-REF2}}{\vdash [\bar{c}_i]_n : \gamma_p[n]}$ $\vdash [\bar{c}_i]_n, p : \gamma_p[n], p$	

Figure 11. Value typing Judgment

7 Auxiliary definitions

$$\boxed{\Gamma \supseteq \Gamma'}$$

$$\frac{\text{EMP-EXT}}{\Gamma \supseteq \emptyset} \quad \frac{\text{NON-EMP-EXT}}{\Gamma \supseteq \Gamma'} \quad \frac{}{x : (\tau, p), \Gamma \supseteq x : (\tau, p), \Gamma'}$$

$$\boxed{\rho \models \Gamma}$$

$$\frac{\text{EMP}}{\rho \models \emptyset} \quad \frac{\text{NON-EMP}}{\rho \models \Gamma \quad \rho \models \Gamma' \quad \vdash \rho(x) : (\tau, p)}{\rho \models \Gamma, x : (\tau, p), \Gamma'}$$

$$\boxed{\mu \models \Gamma}$$

$$\frac{\text{REF-EMP}}{\mu \models \emptyset} \quad \frac{\text{NON-EMP-REF}}{\mu \models \Gamma \quad \mu \models \Gamma' \quad \mu(x) \models (\tau, p)}{\mu \models \Gamma, x : (\tau, p), \Gamma'}$$

$$\boxed{\hat{v} \models (\tau, p)}$$

$$\frac{\text{REF-NON-ARR}}{\tau = \gamma_\ell \quad \vdash \hat{v} : \gamma_p, p} \quad \frac{}{\hat{v} \models (\tau, p)}$$

$$\frac{\text{REF-ARR}}{\tau = \gamma_\ell[n]} \quad \frac{}{\vdash \hat{v} : \gamma_p[n], p} \quad \frac{}{\hat{v} \models (\tau, p)}$$

$$\frac{\text{REF-ORAM}}{\tau = \text{oram}[n]} \quad \frac{}{\vdash \hat{v} : \text{uint}_p[n], p} \quad \frac{}{\hat{v} \models (\tau, p)}$$

$$\boxed{v = \hat{v}}$$

$$\frac{\text{VAL_EQ}}{\forall i \in p, \nu_i = c \quad \forall i \notin p, \nu_i = \perp} \quad \frac{}{(\nu_1, \dots, \nu_m) = (c, p)}$$

$$\boxed{v \sim \hat{v}}$$

$$\frac{\text{SIM_NO_ARR}}{\vdash v : \gamma_\ell, p \quad \vdash \hat{v} : \gamma_p, p \quad \ell = \mathbf{p} \implies v = \hat{v} \quad \ell = \mathbf{s} \implies \hat{v} = \mathcal{D}(v, p, \mathbf{s})} \quad \frac{}{v \sim \hat{v}}$$

$$\frac{\text{SIM_ARR}}{\vdash v : \gamma_\ell[n], p \quad \vdash \hat{v} : \gamma_p[n], p \quad \hat{v} = [c_1, \dots, c_n], p \quad \forall i \in [n], \text{select}(v, \text{sh}_p p i) \sim (c_i, p)} \quad \frac{}{v \sim \hat{v}}$$

$$\frac{\text{SIM_ORAM}}{\vdash v : \text{oram}[n], p \quad \vdash \hat{v} : \text{uint}_p[n], p \quad \hat{v} = [c_1, \dots, c_n], p \quad \forall i \in [n], \text{select}(v, \text{sh}_p p i) \sim (c_i, p)} \quad \frac{}{v \sim \hat{v}}$$

$$\boxed{\rho \sim \mu}$$

$$\frac{\text{STORE_SIM}}{\text{dom}(\rho) = \text{dom}(\mu) \quad \forall x \in \text{dom}(\rho), \rho(x) \sim \mu(x)} \quad \frac{}{\rho \sim \mu}$$

$$\boxed{\mathcal{O} \sim \hat{\mathcal{O}}}$$

$$\frac{\text{EMP_OBS}}{\emptyset \sim \emptyset} \quad \frac{\text{NON_EMP_OBS}}{v \sim \hat{v} \quad \mathcal{O} \sim \hat{\mathcal{O}}} \quad \frac{}{v \mathcal{O} \sim \hat{v} \hat{\mathcal{O}}}$$

$$\boxed{\text{len}(\mathcal{O})}$$

$$\text{len}(\emptyset) = 0 \quad \text{len}(v \mathcal{O}_1) = 1 + \text{len}(\mathcal{O}_1)$$

$$\boxed{\text{len}(\hat{\mathcal{O}})}$$

$$\text{len}(\emptyset) = 0 \quad \text{len}(v \hat{\mathcal{O}}_1) = 1 + \text{len}(\hat{\mathcal{O}}_1)$$

$$\mathcal{G} = \hat{\mathcal{F}}$$

$$\frac{\text{EMP_EFF}}{\emptyset \sim \emptyset} \quad \frac{\text{NON_EMP_EFF}}{(d, p) = \hat{v} \quad \mathcal{G} = \hat{\mathcal{F}}} \quad \frac{\mathcal{G} = \hat{\mathcal{F}}}{(d, p) \mathcal{G} = \hat{v} \hat{\mathcal{F}}}$$

$$\text{len}(\mathcal{G})$$

$$\text{len}(\emptyset) = 0$$

$$\text{len}((d, p) \mathcal{G}_1) = 1 + \text{len}(\mathcal{G}_1)$$

$$\text{len}(\hat{\mathcal{F}})$$

$$\text{len}(\emptyset) = 0$$

$$\text{len}(\hat{v} \hat{\mathcal{F}}_1) = 1 + \text{len}(\hat{\mathcal{F}}_1)$$

8 Correctness theorem and associated lemmas

Theorem 1 (Correctness). *If $\vdash S : _$ then, $\vdash S \downarrow _, \hat{\mathcal{O}}, \hat{\mathcal{F}}$ and $\vdash S \downarrow _, _, \mathcal{O}, \mathcal{G}$ where $\hat{\mathcal{O}} \sim \mathcal{O}$ and $\hat{\mathcal{F}} = \mathcal{G}$*

Proof. Follows from Theorem 2, Theorem 3, and Lemma 15. □

Theorem 2 (Type Soundness of trace semantics). *If $\vdash S : _$ then $\vdash S \downarrow _, _, _, _$*

Proof. Follows from Lemma 9. □

Theorem 3 (Type Soundness of reference semantics). *If $\vdash S : _$ then $\vdash S \downarrow _, _, _$*

Proof. Follows from Lemma 11. □

Lemma 1. *If $\vdash c : \gamma_p$ then $\vdash \text{makeval}(c, p) : \gamma_p, p$*

Lemma 2. *If $\vdash v : \gamma_\ell, p$ then $\exists c$ s.t. $v = \text{sh}_\ell p c$ and $\vdash c : \gamma$*

Lemma 3. *If*

1. $\rho \models \Gamma'$

2. $\Gamma' \supseteq \Gamma$

then

- a) $\rho \models \Gamma$

Lemma 4. *If*

1. $\mu \models \Gamma'$

2. $\Gamma' \supseteq \Gamma$

then

- a) $\mu \models \Gamma$

Lemma 5. $\Gamma \vdash S : \Gamma'$ *then* $\Gamma' \supseteq \Gamma$

Lemma 6. *If*

1. $\rho \models \Gamma$

2. $x \notin \Gamma$

then

- a) $\rho[x \mapsto v] \models \Gamma$

Lemma 7. *If*

1. $\mu \models \Gamma$

2. $x \notin \Gamma$

then

- a) $\mu[x \mapsto \hat{v}] \models \Gamma$

Lemma 8. *If*

1. $\Gamma \vdash e : \tau, p$

2. $\rho \models \Gamma$

then,

$$a) \rho \vdash_p e \Downarrow v$$

$$b) \vdash v : (\tau, p)$$

Lemma 9. • *If*

$$1. \Gamma \vdash_p s \mid \Gamma'$$

$$2. \rho \models \Gamma$$

3. *s is not a loop statement.*

then

$$a) \rho \vdash_p s \Downarrow \rho', _$$

$$b) \rho' \models \Gamma'$$

• *If*

$$1. \Gamma \vdash S \mid \Gamma'$$

$$2. \rho \models \Gamma$$

then

$$a) \rho \vdash S \Downarrow \rho', _$$

$$b) \rho' \models \Gamma'$$

• *If*

$$1. \Gamma \vdash_p \text{for } x \text{ in } [n_1, n_2] \text{ do } S \mid \Gamma$$

$$2. \rho \models \Gamma$$

then

$$1. \rho \vdash_p \text{for } x \text{ in } [n_1, n_2] \text{ do } S \Downarrow \rho', _$$

$$2. \rho' \models \Gamma$$

Lemma 10. *If*

$$1. \Gamma \vdash e : \tau, p$$

$$2. \mu \models \Gamma$$

then,

$$a) \mu \vdash_p e \Downarrow \hat{v}$$

$$b) \hat{v} \models (\tau, p)$$

Lemma 11. • *If*

$$1. \Gamma \vdash_p s \mid \Gamma'$$

$$2. \mu \models \Gamma$$

3. *s is not a loop statement.*

then

$$a) \mu \vdash_p s \Downarrow \mu', _$$

$$b) \mu' \models \Gamma'$$

• If

1. $\Gamma \vdash S \mid \Gamma'$
2. $\mu \models \Gamma$

then

- a) $\mu \vdash S \downarrow \mu', _$
- b) $\mu' \models \Gamma'$

• If

1. $\Gamma \vdash_p \text{ for } x \text{ in } [n_1, n_2] \text{ do } S \mid \Gamma$
2. $\mu \models \Gamma$

then

- a) $\mu \vdash_p \text{ for } x \text{ in } [n_1, n_2] \text{ do } S \downarrow \mu', _$
- b) $\mu' \models \Gamma'$

Lemma 12. If

1. $\rho \models \Gamma$
2. $\mu \models \Gamma$
3. $\rho \sim \mu$
4. $\Gamma \vdash e : (\tau, p)$
5. $\rho \vdash_p e \downarrow v$
6. $\mu \vdash_p e \downarrow \hat{v}$

then

- a) $v \sim \hat{v}$

Lemma 13. If $\mathcal{O} \sim \hat{\mathcal{O}}$ then, $\text{len}(\mathcal{O}) = \text{len}(\hat{\mathcal{O}})$

Lemma 14. If

1. $\mathcal{O}_1 \sim \hat{\mathcal{O}}_1$
2. $\mathcal{O}_2 \sim \hat{\mathcal{O}}_2$

Then,

- a) $\mathcal{O}_1 \mathcal{O}_2 \sim \hat{\mathcal{O}}_1 \hat{\mathcal{O}}_2$

Lemma 15. If $\mathcal{G} = \hat{\mathcal{F}}$ then, $\text{len}(\mathcal{G}) = \text{len}(\hat{\mathcal{F}})$

Lemma 16. If

1. $\mathcal{G}_1 = \hat{\mathcal{F}}_1$
2. $\mathcal{G}_2 = \hat{\mathcal{F}}_2$

Then,

- a) $\mathcal{G}_1 \mathcal{G}_2 = \hat{\mathcal{F}}_1 \hat{\mathcal{F}}_2$

Lemma 17. • If

1. $\rho \models \Gamma$
2. $\mu \models \Gamma$
3. $\rho \sim \mu$
4. $\Gamma \vdash_p s \mid \Gamma'$
5. $\rho \vdash_p s \Downarrow \rho', \mathcal{T}, \mathcal{O}, \mathcal{G}$
6. $\mu \vdash_p s \Downarrow \mu', \hat{\mathcal{O}}, \hat{\mathcal{F}}$
7. s is not a loop statement.

then

- a) $\rho' \sim \mu'$
- b) $\mathcal{O} \sim \hat{\mathcal{O}}$
- c) $\mathcal{G} = \hat{\mathcal{F}}$

• If

1. $\rho \models \Gamma$
2. $\mu \models \Gamma$
3. $\rho \sim \mu$
4. $\Gamma \vdash S \mid \Gamma'$
5. $\rho \vdash S \Downarrow \rho', \mathcal{T}, \mathcal{O}, \mathcal{G}$
6. $\mu \vdash S \Downarrow \mu', \hat{\mathcal{O}}, \hat{\mathcal{F}}$

then

- a) $\rho' \sim \mu'$
- b) $\mathcal{O} \sim \hat{\mathcal{O}}$
- c) $\mathcal{G} = \hat{\mathcal{F}}$

• If

1. $\rho \models \Gamma$
2. $\mu \models \Gamma$
3. $\rho \sim \mu$
4. $\Gamma \vdash_p \text{for } x \text{ in } [n_1, n_2] \text{ do } S \mid \Gamma$
5. $\rho \vdash_p \text{for } x \text{ in } [n_1, n_2] \text{ do } S \Downarrow \rho', \mathcal{T}, \mathcal{O}, \mathcal{G}$
6. $\mu \vdash_p \text{for } x \text{ in } [n_1, n_2] \text{ do } S \Downarrow \mu', \hat{\mathcal{O}}, \hat{\mathcal{F}}$

then

- a) $\rho' \sim \mu'$
- b) $\mathcal{O} \sim \hat{\mathcal{O}}$
- c) $\mathcal{G} = \hat{\mathcal{F}}$

9 Proofs

Lemma 1. *If $\vdash c : \gamma_p$ then $\vdash \text{makeval}(c, p) : \gamma_p, p$*

Proof of Lemma 1. $\text{makeval}(c, p) = v$ s.t. $\pi_i(v) = c$ if $i \in p$ and $\perp$ otherwise.

So $\vdash c : \gamma_p \implies \vdash \pi_i(v) : \gamma_p$ if $i \in p$ and $\vdash \pi_i(v) : \perp$ if $i \notin p$.

So, from rule V-STORE we have $\vdash \text{makeval}(c, p) : \gamma_p, p$

□

Lemma 2. *If $\vdash v : \gamma_\ell, p$ then $\exists c$ s.t. $v = \text{sh}_\ell p c$ and $\vdash c : \gamma$*

Proof of Lemma 2. $\vdash v : \gamma_\ell, p$.

From inversion of value typing $\exists c$ s.t. $\vdash c : \gamma$ and $\forall i \in p \pi_i(v) = \text{sh}_\ell c$ otherwise $\pi_i(v) = \perp$

By definition, $v = \text{sh}_\ell p c$

□

Lemma 3. *If*

1. $\rho \models \Gamma'$

2. $\Gamma' \supseteq \Gamma$

then

- a) $\rho \models \Gamma$

Proof of Lemma 3. Proof by induction on the derivation of (2), analysis on last rule used:

Case EMP-EXT:

Inverting the rule we get $\Gamma = \emptyset$. Consequence follows using rule EMP.

Case NON-EMP-EXT:

$$\rho \models \Gamma' \quad \text{Antecedent 1} \quad \dots(1)$$

$$\Gamma' \supseteq \Gamma \quad \text{Antecedent 2} \quad \dots(2)$$

Inverting (2) using the rule NON-EMP-EXT we get:

$$\Gamma' = x : (\tau, p), \Gamma'_1 \quad \dots(3)$$

$$\Gamma = x : (\tau, p), \Gamma_1 \quad \dots(4)$$

$$\Gamma'_1 \supseteq \Gamma_1 \quad \dots(5)$$

Rewriting (1):

$$\rho \models x : (\tau, p), \Gamma'_1 \quad \dots(6)$$

Inverting (6) (only rule [Non-Emp] is possible with Γ in the rule = $\emptyset$):

$$\rho \models \Gamma'_1 \quad \dots(7)$$

$$\vdash \rho(x) : (\tau, p) \quad \dots(8)$$

Using I.H. with (5) and (7):

$$\rho \models \Gamma_1 \quad \dots(9)$$

Consequence follows from (4), (8) and (9) using rule NON-EMP

□

Lemma 4. *If*

1. $\mu \models \Gamma'$

2. $\Gamma' \supseteq \Gamma$

then

a) $\mu \models \Gamma$

Proof of Lemma 3. Proof by induction on the derivation of (2), analysis on last rule used:

Case EMP-EXT:

Inverting the rule we get $\Gamma = \emptyset$. Consequence follows using rule EMP.

Case NON-EMP-EXT:

$\mu \models \Gamma'$ Antecedent 1 ... (1)

$\Gamma' \supseteq \Gamma$ Antecedent 2 ... (2)

Inverting (2) using the rule NON-EMP-EXT we get:

$\Gamma' = x : (\tau, p), \Gamma'_1$... (3)

$\Gamma = x : (\tau, p), \Gamma_1$... (4)

$\Gamma'_1 \supseteq \Gamma_1$... (5)

Rewriting (1):

$\mu \models x : (\tau, p), \Gamma'_1$... (6)

Inverting (6) (only rule [NON-EMP-REF] is possible with Γ in the rule = $\emptyset$) :

$\mu \models \Gamma'_1$... (7)

$\mu(x) \models (\tau, p)$... (8)

Using I.H. with (5) and (7):

$\mu \models \Gamma_1$... (9)

Consequence follows from (4), (8) and (9) using rule NON-EMP-REF

□

Lemma 5. $\Gamma \vdash S : \Gamma'$ then $\Gamma' \supseteq \Gamma$

Proof of Lemma 5. By inspection of the typing rules, we see that all the rules either leave Γ unchanged or append to Γ . Thus, the lemma holds. $\square$

Lemma 6. *If*

$$1. \rho \models \Gamma$$

$$2. x \notin \Gamma$$

then

$$a) \rho[x \mapsto v] \models \Gamma$$

Proof of Lemma 6. Proof by induction on the size of Γ

Base Case: $\Gamma = \emptyset$

In this case consequence follows directly from rule EMP.

Induction Case: $\Gamma \neq \emptyset$

$$\rho \models \Gamma \quad \dots(1)$$

$$x \notin \Gamma \quad \dots(2)$$

$$\text{Let } \rho' = \rho[x \mapsto v] \quad \dots(3)$$

Since $\Gamma \neq \emptyset$, rule NON-EMP is the only rule that applies. Inverting (1) it NON-EMP:

$$\Gamma = \Gamma_1, x' : (\tau, p), \Gamma_2 \quad \dots(4)$$

$$\rho \models \Gamma_1 \quad \dots(5)$$

$$\rho \models \Gamma_2 \quad \dots(6)$$

$$\vdash \rho(x') : (\tau, p) \quad \dots(7)$$

From (3):

$$\rho(x') = \rho'(x') \quad \dots(8)$$

From (7) and (8):

$$\vdash \rho'(x') : (\tau, p) \quad \dots(9)$$

From (2) and (4):

$$x \notin \Gamma_1 \quad \dots(10)$$

$$x \notin \Gamma_2 \quad \dots(11)$$

From (5) and (10), using I.H.

$$\rho' \models \Gamma_1 \quad \dots(12)$$

From (6) and (11), using I.H.

$$\rho' \models \Gamma_2 \quad \dots(13)$$

From (4), (9), (12) and (13) using rule NON-EMP

$$\rho' \models \Gamma \quad \text{Consequent}$$

$\square$

Lemma 7. *If*

1. $\mu \models \Gamma$

2. $x \notin \Gamma$

then

a) $\mu[x \mapsto \hat{v}] \models \Gamma$

Proof of Lemma 7. Proof by induction on the size of Γ

Base Case: $\Gamma = \emptyset$

In this case consequence follows directly from rule EMP.

Induction Case: $\Gamma \neq \emptyset$

$\mu \models \Gamma$...(1)

$x \notin \Gamma$...(2)

Let $\mu' = \mu[x \mapsto \hat{v}]$...(3)

Since $\Gamma \neq \emptyset$, rule NON-EMP-REF is the only rule that applies. Inverting (1) it NON-EMP-REF:

$\Gamma = \Gamma_1, x' : (\tau, p), \Gamma_2$...(4)

$\mu \models \Gamma_1$...(5)

$\mu \models \Gamma_2$...(6)

$\mu(x') \models (\tau, p)$...(7)

From (3):

$\mu(x') = \mu'(x')$...(8)

From (7) and (8):

$\mu'(x') \models (\tau, p)$...(9)

From (2) and (4):

$x \notin \Gamma_1$...(10)

$x \notin \Gamma_2$...(11)

From (5) and (10), using I.H.

$\mu' \models \Gamma_1$...(12)

From (6) and (11), using I.H.

$\mu' \models \Gamma_2$...(13)

From (4), (9), (12) and (13) using rule NON-EMP-REF

$\mu' \models \Gamma$

Consequent

□

Lemma 8. *If*

$$1. \Gamma \vdash e : \tau, p$$

$$2. \rho \models \Gamma$$

then,

$$a) \rho \vdash_p e \Downarrow v$$

$$b) \vdash v : (\tau, p)$$

Proof of Lemma 8. Proof by induction on size of typing proof tree.

Base cases:

T-UINT

$\Gamma \vdash n : \text{uint}_{p,p}$	Antecedent 1	...(1)
$\rho \models \Gamma$	Antecedent 2	...(2)
From rule A-CONSTANT, $\rho \vdash_p n \Downarrow \text{makeval}(n,p)$	Consequent a	
From V-NAT, $\vdash n : \text{uint}_p$		...(3)
Using (3) from Lemma 1, $\vdash \text{makeval}(n,p) : \text{uint}_{p,p}$	Consequent b	

T-BOOL

$\Gamma \vdash t : \text{bool}_{p,p}$	Antecedent 1	...(1)
$\rho \models \Gamma$	Antecedent 2	...(2)
Inverting type rule, $t \in \{\text{true}, \text{false}\}$		
From rule A-CONSTANT, $\rho \vdash_p t \Downarrow \text{makeval}(t,p)$	Consequent a	
From V-BOOL, $\vdash t : \text{bool}_p$		...(3)
Using (3) from Lemma 1, $\vdash \text{makeval}(n,p) : \text{bool}_{p,p}$	Consequent b	

T-VAR

$\Gamma \vdash x : \tau, p$	Antecedent 1	...(1)
$\rho \models \Gamma$	Antecedent 2	...(2)
Inverting (1) with rule T-VAR:		
$\Gamma(x) = \tau, p'$		...(3)
public $\tau \implies p \subseteq p'$		...(4)
secret $\tau \implies p = p'$		...(5)
Case 1: public τ		
$p \subseteq p'$		...(6)
Since $\Gamma \neq \emptyset$ and (2), $\exists v$ s.t. :		
From (2) using NON-EMP, $\rho(x) = v$		...(7)
$\vdash v : \tau, p'$		...(8)
From rule A-VAR:		
$\rho \vdash_p x \Downarrow \rho(x) _p$	Consequent a	...(9)
From (2) and (3) using rule NON-EMP:		
$\vdash \rho(x) : \tau, p'$		...(10)
Inverting (10) using rule V-STORE:		
$\vdash \pi_i(\rho(x)) : \tau$ if $i \in p'$ otherwise $\vdash \pi_i(\rho(x)) : \perp$		...(11)
From definition:		
$\pi_i(\rho(x) _p) = \pi_i(\rho(x))$ if $i \in p$ otherwise $\pi_i(\rho(x) _p) = \perp$		...(12)
Using (6), (11) and (12):		
$\forall i \in p, \vdash \pi_i(\rho(x) _p) : \tau$ and $\vdash \pi_i(\rho(x) _p) : \perp$ if $i \notin p$		...(13)
From (13) using rule V-STORE:		
$\vdash \rho(x) _p : \tau, p$	Consequent b	...(14)
Case 2: secret τ		
From (3) and (5), $\Gamma(x) = \tau, p$		...(15)
Since $\Gamma \neq \emptyset$ and (2), $\exists v$ s.t. :		
From (2) using NON-EMP, $\rho(x) = v$		...(16)
$\vdash v : \tau, p$		...(17)
From rule A-VAR:		
$\rho \vdash_p x \Downarrow \rho(x) _p$	Consequent a	...(18)
From (2) and (15) using rule NON-EMP:		
$\vdash \rho(x) : \tau, p$		...(19)
Inverting (19) using rule V-STORE:		
$\vdash \pi_i(\rho(x)) : \tau$ if $i \in p$ otherwise $\vdash \pi_i(\rho(x)) : \perp$		...(20)
From definition:		
$\pi_i(\rho(x) _p) = \pi_i(\rho(x))$ if $i \in p$ otherwise $\pi_i(\rho(x) _p) = \perp$		...(21)
Using (20) and (21):		
$\forall i \in p, \vdash \pi_i(\rho(x) _p) : \tau$ and $\vdash \pi_i(\rho(x) _p) : \perp$ otherwise		...(22)
From (22) using rule V-STORE:		
$\vdash \pi_i(\rho(x) _p) : \tau, p$	Consequent b	

Induction cases:

T-BINOP

$\Gamma \vdash e_1 \oplus e_2 : \mathbf{uint}_{\ell, p}$	Antecedent 1	...(1)
$\rho \models \Gamma$	Antecedent 2	...(2)
Inverting (1) with T-BINOP:		
$\Gamma \vdash e_1 : \mathbf{uint}_{\ell_1, p}$		...(3)
$\Gamma \vdash e_2 : \mathbf{uint}_{\ell_2, p}$		...(4)
$\mathcal{J}(\ell_1, \ell_2) = \ell$		...(5)
Using (2) and (3), from I.H.		
$\rho \vdash_p e_1 \Downarrow v_1$		...(6)
$\vdash v_1 : \mathbf{uint}_{\ell_1, p}$		...(7)
Using (2) and (4), from I.H.		
$\rho \vdash_p e_2 \Downarrow v_2$		...(8)
$\vdash v_2 : \mathbf{uint}_{\ell_2, p}$		...(9)
Using (6) and (8), from rule A-BINOP:		
$\rho \vdash_p e_1 \oplus e_2 \Downarrow v$ where $v = \oplus_{\ell_1 \ell_2}(v_1, v_2)$	Consequent a	...(10)
Using (7) from Lemma 2:		
$\exists c_1$ s.t. $v_1 = \mathbf{sh}_{\ell_1} p c_1$ where $\vdash c_1 : \mathbf{uint}$		...(11)
Using (9) from Lemma 2:		
$\exists c_2$ s.t. $v_2 = \mathbf{sh}_{\ell_2} p c_2$ where $\vdash c_2 : \mathbf{uint}$		...(12)
Using (5), (11) and (12), from operator homomorphism axiom:		
$\oplus_{\ell_1 \ell_2}(v_1, v_2) = \mathbf{sh}_{\ell} p (c_1 \oplus c_2)$		...(13)
From value typing judgement:		
$\vdash \oplus_{\ell_1 \ell_2}(v_1, v_2) : \mathbf{uint}_{\ell, p}$	Consequent b	

T-GT

$\Gamma \vdash e_1 > e_2 : \text{bool}_{\ell}, p$	Antecedent 1	...(1)
$\rho \models \Gamma$	Antecedent 2	...(2)
Inverting (1) with T-BINOP:		
$\Gamma \vdash e_1 : \text{uint}_{\ell_1}, p$		...(3)
$\Gamma \vdash e_2 : \text{uint}_{\ell_2}, p$		...(4)
$\mathcal{J}(\ell_1, \ell_2) = \ell$		...(5)
Using (2) and (3), from I.H.		
$\rho \vdash_p e_1 \Downarrow v_1$		...(6)
$\vdash v_1 : \text{uint}_{\ell_1}, p$		...(7)
Using (2) and (4), from I.H.		
$\rho \vdash_p e_2 \Downarrow v_2$		...(8)
$\vdash v_2 : \text{uint}_{\ell_2}, p$		...(9)
Using (6) and (8), from rule A-GT:		
$\rho \vdash_p e_1 > e_2 \Downarrow v$ where $v = >_{\ell_1 \ell_2}(v_1, v_2)$	Consequent a	...(10)
Using (7) from Lemma 2:		
$\exists c_1 \text{ s.t. } v_1 = \text{sh}_{\ell_1} p c_1$ where $\vdash c_1 : \text{uint}$		...(11)
Using (9) from Lemma 2:		
$\exists c_2 \text{ s.t. } v_2 = \text{sh}_{\ell_2} p c_2$ where $\vdash c_2 : \text{uint}$		...(12)
Using (5), (11) and (12), from operator homomorphism axiom:		
$>_{\ell_1 \ell_2}(v_1, v_2) = \text{sh}_{\ell} p (c_1 > c_2)$		...(13)
From value typing judgement:		
$\vdash >_{\ell_1 \ell_2}(v_1, v_2) : \text{bool}_{\ell}, p$	Consequent b	

T-MUX

$\Gamma \vdash (e_1 ? e_2 : e_3) : \gamma_\ell, p$	Antecedent 1	...(1)
$\rho \models \Gamma$	Antecedent 2	...(2)
Inverting (1) with T-MUX:		
$\Gamma \vdash e_1 : \mathbf{bool}_{\ell_1}, p$		...(3)
$\Gamma \vdash e_2 : \gamma_{\ell_2}, p$		...(4)
$\Gamma \vdash e_3 : \gamma_{\ell_3}, p$		...(5)
$\mathcal{J}(\ell_1, \ell_2, \ell_3) = \ell$		...(6)
Using (2) and (3), from I.H.		
$\rho \vdash_p e_1 \Downarrow v_1$		...(7)
$\vdash v_1 : \mathbf{bool}_{\ell_1}, p$		...(8)
Using (2) and (4), from I.H.		
$\rho \vdash_p e_2 \Downarrow v_2$		...(9)
$\vdash v_2 : \gamma_{\ell_2}, p$		...(10)
Using (2) and (5), from I.H.		
$\rho \vdash_p e_3 \Downarrow v_3$		...(11)
$\vdash v_3 : \gamma_{\ell_3}, p$		...(12)
Using (7), (9) and (11), from rule A-MUX:		
$\rho \vdash_p e_1 ? e_2 : e_3 \Downarrow v$ where $v = ?_{\ell_1 \ell_2 \ell_3}(v_1, v_2, v_3)$	Consequent a	...(13)
Using (8) from Lemma 2:		
$\exists c_1 \text{ s.t. } v_1 = \mathbf{sh}_{\ell_1} p c_1$ where $\vdash c_1 : \mathbf{bool}$		...(14)
Using (10) from Lemma 2:		
$\exists c_2 \text{ s.t. } v_2 = \mathbf{sh}_{\ell_2} p c_2$ where $\vdash c_2 : \gamma$		...(15)
Using (12) from Lemma 2:		
$\exists c_3 \text{ s.t. } v_3 = \mathbf{sh}_{\ell_3} p c_3$ where $\vdash c_3 : \gamma$		...(16)
Using (14), (15) and (16), from operator homomorphism axiom:		
$?_{\ell_1 \ell_2 \ell_3}(v_1, v_2, v_3) = \mathbf{sh}_\ell p ?(c_1, c_2, c_3)$		...(17)
From value typing judgement:		
$\vdash ?_{\ell_1 \ell_2 \ell_3}(v_1, v_2, v_3) : \gamma_\ell, p$	Consequent b	

T-ARR

$\Gamma \vdash [\bar{e}_i]_n : \gamma_\ell[n], p$	Antecedent 1	...(1)
$\rho \models \Gamma$	Antecedent 2	...(2)
Inverting (1) using T-ARR:		
$\forall i \in [n], \Gamma \vdash e_i : \gamma_\ell, p$		...(3)
Using (2) and (3), from I.H.:		
$\forall i \in [n], \rho \vdash_p e_i \Downarrow v_i$		...(4)
$\forall i \in [n], \vdash v_i : \gamma_\ell, p$		...(5)
Using (4), from rule A-ARR: $\rho \vdash_p [\bar{e}_i]_n \Downarrow v$, where:		
$\forall j \in p, \pi_j(v) = [\pi_j(v_1), \dots, \pi_j(v_n)]$		...(6)
$\forall j \notin p, \pi_j(v) = \perp$		...(7)
This proves consequent (a).		
Inverting (5) with rule V-STORE:		
$\forall j \in p \vdash \pi_j(v_i) : \gamma_\ell$		...(8)
Using (8), from rule V-ARR		
$\forall j \in p, \vdash [\pi_j(v_1), \dots, \pi_j(v_n)] : \gamma_\ell[n]$		...(9)
Also, $\forall j \notin p, \vdash \pi_j(v) : \perp$		...(10)
Using (9) and (10), from rule V-STORE:		
$\vdash v : \gamma_\ell[n], p$	Consequent b	

T-ARR_READ

$\Gamma \vdash x[e] : \gamma_\ell, p$	Antecedent 1	...(1)
$\rho \models \Gamma$	Antecedent 2	...(2)
Inverting (1) using rule T-ARR_READ:		
$\Gamma \vdash x : \gamma_\ell[n], p$		...(3)
$\Gamma \vdash e : \text{uint}_p, p$		...(4)
$\Gamma \models e < n$		...(5)
Using (2) and (3), from I.H.		
$\rho \vdash_p x \Downarrow v_1$		...(6)
$\vdash v_1 : \gamma_\ell[n], p$		...(7)
Using (2) and (4), from I.H.		
$\rho \vdash_p e \Downarrow v_2$		...(8)
$\vdash v_2 : \text{uint}_p, p$		...(9)
Using (9), from Lemma 2:		
$\exists i \text{ s.t. } v_2 = \text{sh}_p p i \text{ and } \vdash i : \text{uint}$		...(10)
Using (6), (8) and (10), from rule A-ARR_READ:		
$\rho \vdash_p x[e] \Downarrow v \text{ where } v = \text{select}(v_1, v_2)$	Consequent a	...(11)
From definition of select operation:		
$\forall j \notin p, \pi_j(v) = \perp$		...(12)
From (12):		
$\forall j \notin p, \vdash \pi_j(v) : \perp$		...(13)
Inverting (7) with rule V-STORE:		
$\forall j \in p, \vdash \pi_j(v_1) : \gamma_\ell[n]$		...(14)
From (5):		
$i < n$		...(15)
Inverting V-ARR using (14) and (15):		
$\forall j \in p, \vdash \pi_j(v_1)[i] : \gamma_\ell$		...(16)
From (13) and (16), using rule V-STORE:		
$\vdash v : \gamma_\ell, p$	Consequent b	

T-ORAM

$\Gamma \vdash \text{Oram}(e) : \text{oram}[n], p$	Antecedent 1	...(1)
$\rho \models \Gamma$	Antecedent 2	...(2)
Inverting (1) using rule T-ORAM:		
$\Gamma \vdash e : \text{uint}_s[n], p$		...(3)
Using (2) and (3), from I.H.		
$\rho \vdash_p e \Downarrow v'$		...(4)
$\vdash v' : \text{uint}_s[n], p$		...(5)
From (5) using V-STORE,		
$\forall j \in p, \vdash \pi_j(v') : \text{uint}_s[n]$		...(6)
$\forall j \notin p, \vdash \pi_j(v') : \perp$		...(7)
Let $v = \text{convert}(v')$		
...(8)		
From (6) using V-ARR, $\pi_j(v') = [bv_i]_n$		
...(9)		
$\forall i \in [n], \vdash bv_i : \gamma_s$		
...(10)		
From (6), (7) using definition of $\text{convert}(v')$,		
$\forall j \in p, \pi_j(v) = \langle bv_i \rangle_n$		...(11)
$\forall j \notin p, \pi_j(v) = \perp$		...(12)
From (10) using V-ORAM, $\vdash \langle bv_i \rangle_n : \text{oram}[n]$		
...(13)		
From (11), (13) $\forall j \in p, \vdash \pi_j(v) : \text{oram}[n]$		
...(14)		
From (12) using V-BOT, $\forall j \notin p, \vdash \pi_j(v) : \perp$		
...(15)		
From (14), (15) using V-STORE, $\vdash v : \text{oram}[n], p$		Consequent b
From (4), (8) using A-ORAM, $\rho \vdash_p \text{Oram}(e) \Downarrow v$		Consequent a

□

Lemma 9. • *If*

1. $\Gamma \vdash_p s \mid \Gamma'$
2. $\rho \models \Gamma$
3. s is not a loop statement.

then

- a) $\rho \vdash_p s \Downarrow \rho', _$
- b) $\rho' \models \Gamma'$

• *If*

1. $\Gamma \vdash S \mid \Gamma'$
2. $\rho \models \Gamma$

then

- a) $\rho \vdash S \Downarrow \rho', _$
- b) $\rho' \models \Gamma'$

• *If*

1. $\Gamma \vdash_p \text{for } x \text{ in } [n_1, n_2] \text{ do } S \mid \Gamma$
2. $\rho \models \Gamma$

then

1. $\rho \vdash_p$ for x in $[n_1, n_2]$ do $S \Downarrow \rho', _$
2. $\rho' \models \Gamma$

Proof of Lemma 9. We prove by mutual induction on the size of typing proof tree and $n_2 - n_1$.

Notation (only for this proof): $\rho \vdash_p s \Downarrow \rho' \equiv \rho \vdash_p s \Downarrow \rho', _, _, _$
 $\rho \vdash S \Downarrow \rho' \equiv \rho \vdash S \Downarrow \rho', _, _, _$

Base Cases:

T-DEF

$$\Gamma \vdash_p (\tau \ x = e) \mid \Gamma, x : (\tau, p). \quad \text{Antecedant 1} \quad \dots(1)$$

$$\rho \models \Gamma \quad \text{Antecedant 2} \quad \dots(2)$$

Inverting (1) with rule T-DEF:

$$\Gamma \vdash e : \tau, p \quad \dots(3)$$

$$x \notin \Gamma \quad \dots(4)$$

Using (2) and (3), from Lemma 8:

$$\rho \vdash_p e \Downarrow v \quad \dots(5)$$

$$\vdash v : (\tau, p) \quad \dots(6)$$

Applying A-DEF rule using (5):

$$\rho \vdash_p (\tau \ x = e) \Downarrow \rho[x \mapsto v] \quad \text{Consequent a} \quad \dots(7)$$

$$\text{Let } \rho' = \rho[x \mapsto v] \quad \dots(8)$$

$$\text{From (6), (7), } \vdash \rho'(x) : (\tau, p) \quad \dots(9)$$

Let $\Gamma' = \emptyset$

$$\text{Using EMP rule, } \rho' \models \Gamma' \quad \dots(10)$$

$$\text{From Lemma 6 using (2), (4), (8), } \rho' \models \Gamma \quad \dots(11)$$

Applying NON-EMP rule using (9), (10), (11):

$$\rho' \models \Gamma, x : (\tau, p), \Gamma'$$

$$\implies \rho' \models \Gamma, x : (\tau, p) \quad \text{Consequent b}$$

T-ASSIGN

$$\begin{array}{l} \Gamma \vdash_p (x = e) \mid \Gamma \\ \rho \models \Gamma \end{array} \quad \begin{array}{ll} \text{Antecedant 1} & \dots(1) \\ \text{Antecedant 2} & \dots(2) \end{array}$$

Inverting (1) with rule T-ASSIGN:

$$\Gamma \vdash x = (\gamma_\ell, p) \quad \dots(3)$$

$$\Gamma \vdash e : \gamma_\ell, p \quad \dots(4)$$

From (3):

$$\Gamma = \Gamma_1, x : (\gamma_\ell, p), \Gamma_2 \quad \dots(5)$$

From inversion of NON-EMP rule using (2) and (5), from :

$$\rho \models \Gamma_1 \quad \dots(6)$$

$$\rho \models \Gamma_2 \quad \dots(7)$$

From (5):

$$x \notin \Gamma_1 \quad \dots(8)$$

$$x \notin \Gamma_2 \quad \dots(9)$$

Using (2) and (4), from Lemma 8:

$$\rho \vdash_p e \Downarrow v \quad \dots(10)$$

$$\vdash v : \gamma_\ell, p \quad \dots(11)$$

Applying A-ASSIGN rule using (10):

$$\begin{array}{l} \rho \vdash_p (x = e) \Downarrow \rho[x \mapsto v] \\ \rho' = \rho[x \mapsto v] \end{array} \quad \begin{array}{ll} \text{Consequent a} & \\ & \dots(12) \end{array}$$

From lemma 6 using (6) and (8):

$$\rho' \models \Gamma_1 \quad \dots(13)$$

From lemma 6 using (7) and (9):

$$\rho' \models \Gamma_2 \quad \dots(14)$$

Applying NON-EMP rule using (5), (11), (12), (13), (14):

$$\rho' \models \Gamma \quad \text{Consequent b}$$

T-INPUT

$\Gamma \vdash_p \text{input}(x, \tau) \mid \Gamma, x : (\tau, p).$	Antecedant 1	...(1)
$\rho \models \Gamma$	Antecedant 2	...(2)
Inverting (1) with rule T-INPUT:		
$x \notin \Gamma$		...(3)
Let $v = \text{userin}(\tau, p)$		...(4)
From Axiom 1 using (4), $\vdash v : (\tau, p)$		...(5)
From rule A-INPUT using (3):		
$\rho \vdash_p \text{input}(x, \tau) \Downarrow \rho[x \mapsto v]$	Consequent a	...(6)
$\rho' = \rho[x \mapsto v]$		...(7)
From Lemma 6 using (2), (3), $\rho' \models \Gamma$		...(8)
Let $\Gamma' = \emptyset$		
Using EMP rule, $\rho' \models \Gamma'$		...(9)
Applying NON-EMP rule using (5), (8), (9):		
$\rho' \models \Gamma, x : (\tau, p), \Gamma'$		
$\implies \rho' \models \Gamma, x : (\tau, p)$	Consequent b	

T-ORAM_READ

$\Gamma \vdash_p y = \text{OramRead}(x, e) \mid \Gamma, y : \text{uint}_s, p$	Antecedent 1	...(1)
$\rho \models \Gamma$	Antecedant 2	...(2)
Inverting (1) with rule T-ORAM_READ:		
$\Gamma \vdash x : \text{oram}[n], p$		...(3)
$\Gamma \vdash e : \text{uint}_\ell, p$		...(4)
$y \notin \Gamma$		...(5)
From (3):		
$\Gamma = \Gamma_1, x : (\text{oram}[n], p), \Gamma_2$		...(6)
From inversion of NON-EMP rule using (2) and (6), from :		
$\rho \models \Gamma_1$		...(7)
$\rho \models \Gamma_2$		...(8)
From (6):		
$x \notin \Gamma_1$		...(9)
$x \notin \Gamma_2$		...(10)
From Lemma 8 using (2), (3),		
$\rho \vdash_p x \Downarrow v$		...(11)
$\vdash v : \text{oram}[n], p$		...(12)
From Lemma 8 using (2), (4),		
$\rho \vdash_p e \Downarrow v_1$		...(13)
$\vdash v_1 : \text{uint}_\ell, p$		...(14)
Let $v', v_2 = \mathcal{OR}(v, v_1)$		...(15)
From Axiom (3) using (12), (14), (15),		
$\vdash v' : \text{oram}[n], p$		...(16)
$\vdash v : \text{uint}_s, p$		...(17)
Let $\rho' = \rho[x \mapsto v']$		...(18)
From lemma 6 using (7) and (9):		
$\rho' \models \Gamma_1$		...(19)
From lemma 6 using (8) and (10):		
$\rho' \models \Gamma_2$		...(20)
Applying NON-EMP rule using (6), (16), (18), (19), (20):		
$\rho' \models \Gamma$		...(21)
Let $\rho'' = \rho'[y \mapsto v_2]$		...(22)
From lemma 6 using (5) and (21):		
$\rho' \models \Gamma$		...(23)
Applying NON-EMP rule using (17), (23):		
$\rho'' \models \Gamma, y : \text{uint}_s, p$	Consequent b	
Applying A-ORAM_READ rule using (11), (13), (15):		
$\rho \vdash_p y = \text{OramRead}(x, e) \Downarrow \rho''$	Consequent a	

T-ORAM_WRITE

$\Gamma \vdash_p \text{OramWrite}(x, e_1, e_2) \mid \Gamma$	Antecedant 1	...(1)
$\rho \models \Gamma$	Antecedant 2	...(2)
Inverting (1) with rule T-ORAM_WRITE:		
$\Gamma \vdash x : \text{oram}[n], p$		...(3)
$\Gamma \vdash e_1 : \text{uint}_{\ell_1}, p$		...(4)
$\Gamma \vdash e_2 : \text{uint}_{\ell_2}, p$		...(5)
From (3):		
$\Gamma = \Gamma_1, x : (\text{oram}[n], p), \Gamma_2$		...(6)
From inversion of NON-EMP rule using (2) and (6), from :		
$\rho \models \Gamma_1$		...(7)
$\rho \models \Gamma_2$		...(8)
From (6):		
$x \notin \Gamma_1$		...(9)
$x \notin \Gamma_2$		...(10)
From Lemma 8 using (2), (3),		
$\rho \vdash_p x \Downarrow v$		...(11)
$\vdash v : \text{oram}[n], p$		...(12)
From Lemma 8 using (2), (4),		
$\rho \vdash_p e_1 \Downarrow v_1$		...(13)
$\vdash v_1 : \text{uint}_{\ell_1}, p$		...(14)
From Lemma 8 using (2), (5),		
$\rho \vdash_p e_2 \Downarrow v_2$		...(15)
$\vdash v_2 : \text{uint}_{\ell_2}, p$		...(16)
Let $v' = \mathcal{OW}(v, v_1, v_2)$		...(17)
From Axiom (3) using (12), (14), (16), (17),		
$\vdash v' : \text{oram}[n], p$		...(18)
Applying A-ORAM_WRITE rule using (10):		
$\rho \vdash_p \text{OramWrite}(x, e_1, e_2) \Downarrow \rho[x \mapsto v']$	Consequent a	
$\rho' = \rho[x \mapsto v']$		...(19)
From lemma 6 using (7) and (9):		
$\rho' \models \Gamma_1$		...(20)
From lemma 6 using (8) and (10):		
$\rho' \models \Gamma_2$		...(21)
Applying NON-EMP rule using (6), (18), (19), (20), (21):		
$\rho' \models \Gamma$	Consequent b	

T-REVEAL

$$\begin{array}{ll} \Gamma \vdash (\gamma_p \ x_1 = \text{reveal}(x_2, p)) \mid \Gamma, x_1 : (\gamma_p, p) & \text{Antecedant 1} \quad \dots(1) \\ \rho \models \Gamma & \text{Antecedant 2} \quad \dots(2) \end{array}$$

Inverting (1) using T-REVEAL:

$$\begin{array}{ll} \Gamma(x_2) = (\gamma_s, p') & \dots(3) \\ x_1 \notin \Gamma & \dots(4) \end{array}$$

$$\text{Let } v = \mathcal{D}(\rho(x_2), p) \quad \dots(5)$$

$$\text{From correctness of MPC protocol using (3), } \vdash v : (\gamma_p, p) \quad \dots(6)$$

$$\begin{array}{ll} \text{Using Lemma (2) using (6),} & \\ v = \text{sh}_p \ p \ c & \dots(7) \end{array}$$

From rule A-REVEAL using (5), (7):

$$\rho \vdash (\gamma_p \ x_1 = \text{reveal}(x_2, p)) \Downarrow \rho[x_1 \mapsto v] \quad \text{Consequent a} \quad \dots(8)$$

$$\rho' = \rho[x \mapsto v] \quad \dots(9)$$

$$\text{From Lemma 6 using (2), (4), } \rho' \models \Gamma \quad \dots(10)$$

Let $\Gamma' = \emptyset$

$$\text{Using EMP rule, } \rho' \models \Gamma' \quad \dots(11)$$

Applying NON-EMP rule using (6), (10), (11):

$$\begin{array}{ll} \rho' \models \Gamma, x_1 : (\tau, p), \Gamma' & \\ \implies \rho' \models \Gamma, x_1 : (\tau, p) & \text{Consequent b} \end{array}$$

T-MAKESH

$$\begin{array}{ll} \Gamma \vdash \gamma_s \ x_1 = \text{makesh}(x_2, p) \mid \Gamma, x_1 : (\gamma_s, p) & \text{Antecedant 1} \quad \dots(1) \\ \rho \models \Gamma & \text{Antecedant 2} \quad \dots(2) \end{array}$$

Inverting (1) using T-MAKESH:

$$\begin{array}{ll} \Gamma(x_2) = (\gamma_p, p') & \dots(3) \\ x_1 \notin \Gamma & \dots(4) \\ \neg \text{singleton}(p) & \end{array}$$

$$\text{Let } v = \mathcal{E}(\rho(x_2), p) \quad \dots(5)$$

$$\text{From correctness of MPC protocol using (3), } \vdash v : (\gamma_s, p) \quad \dots(6)$$

$$\text{From Lemma 8 using (2), (3), } \vdash \rho(x_2) : (\gamma_p, p) \quad \dots(7)$$

$$\implies \rho(x_2) = \text{sh}_p \ p' \ c \quad \dots(8)$$

From rule A-MAKESH using (5), (8):

$$\rho \vdash \gamma_s \ x_1 = \text{makesh}(x_2, p) \Downarrow \rho[x_1 \mapsto v] \quad \text{Consequent a} \quad \dots(9)$$

$$\rho' = \rho[x \mapsto v] \quad \dots(10)$$

$$\text{From Lemma 6 using (2), (4), } \rho' \models \Gamma \quad \dots(11)$$

Let $\Gamma' = \emptyset$

$$\text{Using EMP rule, } \rho' \models \Gamma' \quad \dots(12)$$

Applying NON-EMP rule using (6), (11), (12):

$$\rho' \models \Gamma, x_1 : (\gamma_s, p), \Gamma'$$

$$\implies \rho' \models \Gamma, x : (\gamma_s, p) \quad \text{Consequent b}$$

T-RESHARE

$$\begin{array}{ll} \Gamma \vdash \gamma_s \ x_1 = \text{reshare}(x_2, p) \mid \Gamma, x_1 : (\gamma_s, p) & \text{Antecedant 1} \quad \dots(1) \\ \rho \models \Gamma & \text{Antecedant 2} \quad \dots(2) \end{array}$$

Inverting (1) using T-RESHARE:

$$\begin{array}{ll} \Gamma(x_2) = (\gamma_s, p') & \dots(3) \\ x_1 \notin \Gamma & \dots(4) \end{array}$$

$$\text{Let } v = \mathcal{R}(\rho(x_2), p) \quad \dots(5)$$

$$\text{From correctness of MPC protocol using (3), } \vdash v : (\gamma_s, p) \quad \dots(6)$$

$$\text{From Lemma 8 using (2), (3), } \vdash \rho(x_2) : (\gamma_s, p) \quad \dots(7)$$

$$\implies \rho(x_2) = \text{sh}_s p' c \quad \dots(8)$$

From rule A-RESHARE using (5):

$$\rho \vdash \gamma_s \ x_1 = \text{reshare}(x_2, p) \Downarrow \rho, x_1 \mapsto v \quad \text{Consequent a} \quad \dots(9)$$

$$\rho' = \rho[x \mapsto v] \quad \dots(10)$$

$$\text{From Lemma 6 using (2), (4), } \rho' \models \Gamma \quad \dots(11)$$

Let $\Gamma' = \emptyset$

$$\text{Using EMP rule, } \rho' \models \Gamma' \quad \dots(12)$$

Applying NON-EMP rule using (6), (11), (12):

$$\rho' \models \Gamma, x_1 : (\gamma_s, p), \Gamma'$$

$$\implies \rho' \models \Gamma, x : (\gamma_s, p) \quad \text{Consequent b}$$

T-BROADCAST

$\Gamma \vdash \gamma_p \ x_1 = \text{broadcast}(x_2, p) \mid \Gamma, x_1 : (\gamma_p, p)$	Antecedant 1	...(1)
$\rho \models \Gamma$	Antecedant 2	...(2)

Inverting (1) using T-BROADCAST:

$\Gamma(x_2) = (\gamma_p, p')$		...(3)
$x_1 \notin \Gamma$		...(4)

Let $v = \mathcal{P}(\rho(x_2), p)$		...(5)
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From correctness of MPC protocol using (3), $\vdash v : (\gamma_p, p)$		...(6)
--	--	--------

From rule A-BROADCAST using (5):

$\rho \vdash \gamma_p \ x_1 = \text{broadcast}(x_2, p) \Downarrow \rho[x_1 \mapsto v]$	Consequent a	...(7)
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$\rho' = \rho[x_1 \mapsto v]$		...(8)
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From Lemma 6 using (2), (4), $\rho' \models \Gamma$		...(9)
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Let $\Gamma' = \emptyset$

Using EMP rule, $\rho' \models \Gamma'$		...(10)
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Applying NON-EMP rule using (6), (9), (10):

$\rho' \models \Gamma, x_1 : (\gamma_p, p), \Gamma'$		
--	--	--

$\implies \rho' \models \Gamma, x : (\gamma_p, p)$	Consequent b	
--	--------------	--

T-ARR_WRITE

$\Gamma \vdash x[e_1] = e_2 \mid \Gamma$	Antecedant 1	...(1)
$\rho \models \Gamma$	Antecedant 2	...(2)

Inverting (1) using T-ARR_WRITE:

$\Gamma \vdash x : (\gamma_\ell[n], p)$		...(3)
$\implies \Gamma = \Gamma_1, x : (\gamma_\ell[n], p), \Gamma_2$ s.t. $x \notin \Gamma_1, x \notin \Gamma_2$		...(4)
$\Gamma \vdash e_1 : (\mathbf{uint}_p, p)$		...(5)
$\Gamma \vdash e_2 : (\gamma_\ell, p)$		...(6)

From Lemma 8 using (2), (3):

$\rho \vdash_p x \Downarrow v$		...(7)
$\vdash v : (\gamma_\ell[n], p)$		...(8)

From Lemma 8 using (2), (5):

$\rho \vdash_p e_1 \Downarrow v_1$		...(9)
$\vdash v_1 : (\mathbf{uint}_p, p)$		...(10)

From Lemma 8 using (2), (6):

$\rho \vdash_p e_2 \Downarrow v_2$		...(11)
$\vdash v_2 : (\gamma_\ell, p)$		...(12)

From Lemma 2 using (10):

$v_1 = \mathbf{sh}_p p c$		...(13)
$v' = \mathbf{update}(v, v_1, v_2)$		...(14)
$\forall i \in p, \pi_i(v')[c] = \pi_i(v_2) \implies \vdash \pi_i(v')[c] : \gamma_\ell$		...(15)
$\forall i \in p, \vdash \pi_i(v) : \gamma_\ell[n]$		...(16)
$\forall i \in p, \forall j \neq c, \pi_i(v')[j] = \pi_i(v)[j]$		...(17)
From (15), (16), (17), $\forall i \in p, \vdash \pi_i(v') : \gamma_\ell[n]$		...(18)
$\forall i \notin p, \pi_i(v') = \perp$		...(19)
From (18), (19), $\vdash v' : \gamma_\ell[n], p$		...(20)

From rule A-ARR_WRITE using (7), (9), (11), (14):

$\rho \vdash x[e_1] = e_2 \Downarrow \rho[x \mapsto v']$	Consequent a	...(21)
Let $\rho' = \rho[x \mapsto v']$		...(22)

From inversion of NON-EMP rule using (2), (4),

$\rho \models \Gamma_1, \rho \models \Gamma_2$		...(23)
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From Lemma 6, using (22), (23), $\rho' \models \Gamma_1, \rho' \models \Gamma_2$		...(24)
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Applying NON-EMP rule using (4), (8), (24):

$\rho' \models \Gamma$	Consequent b	
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Induction Cases:**T-AS**

$$\begin{array}{lll} \Gamma \vdash_p \text{as}(p, s) \mid \Gamma' & \text{Antecedant 1} & \dots(1) \\ \rho \models \Gamma & \text{Antecedant 2} & \dots(2) \end{array}$$

Inverting (1) with rule T-AS:

$$\Gamma \vdash_p s \mid \Gamma' \quad \dots(3)$$

Applying IH using (2) and (3):

$$\begin{array}{lll} \rho \vdash_p s \Downarrow \rho' & & \dots(4) \\ \rho' \models \Gamma' & \text{Consequent b} & \dots(5) \end{array}$$

Applying A-AS rule using (4):

$$\rho \vdash_p \text{as}(p, s) \Downarrow \rho' \quad \text{Consequent a}$$

T-SEQ

$$\begin{array}{lll} \Gamma \vdash_p s_1; s_2 \mid \Gamma' & \text{Antecedant 1} & \dots(1) \\ \rho \models \Gamma & \text{Antecedant 2} & \dots(2) \end{array}$$

Inverting (1) with rule T-SEQ:

$$\begin{array}{lll} \Gamma \vdash_p s_1 \mid \Gamma_1 & & \dots(3) \\ \Gamma_1 \vdash_p s_2 \mid \Gamma' & & \dots(4) \end{array}$$

Applying IH using (2) and (3):

$$\begin{array}{lll} \rho \vdash_p s_1 \Downarrow \rho_1 & & \dots(5) \\ \rho_1 \models \Gamma_1 & & \dots(6) \end{array}$$

Applying IH using (4) and (6):

$$\begin{array}{lll} \rho_1 \vdash_p s_2 \Downarrow \rho' & & \dots(7) \\ \rho' \models \Gamma' & \text{Consequent b} & \end{array}$$

Applying A-SEQ rule using (5), (7):

$$\rho \vdash_p s_1; s_2 \Downarrow \rho' \quad \text{Consequent a}$$

T-ANNOT_SEQ

$\Gamma \vdash S_1; S_2 \mid \Gamma'$ Antecedant 1 ... (1)
 $\rho \models \Gamma$ Antecedant 2 ... (2)

Inverting (1) with rule T-ANNOT_SEQ:

$\Gamma \vdash S_1 \mid \Gamma_1$... (3)

$\Gamma_1 \vdash S_2 \mid \Gamma'$... (4)

Applying IH using (2) and (3):

$\rho \vdash S_1 \Downarrow \rho_1$... (5)

$\rho_1 \models \Gamma_1$... (6)

Applying IH using (4) and (6):

$\rho_1 \vdash S_2 \Downarrow \rho'$... (7)

$\rho' \models \Gamma'$ Consequent b

Applying A-ANNOT_SEQ rule using (5), (7):

$\rho \vdash S_1; S_2 \Downarrow \rho'$ Consequent a

T-IF

$$\Gamma \vdash \text{if}(e, S_1, S_2) \mid \Gamma$$

$$\rho \models \Gamma$$

Antecedant 1 ... (1)

Antecedant 2 ... (2)

Inverting (1) with rule T-IF

$$\Gamma \vdash e : \text{bool}_p, p$$

... (3)

$$\Gamma \vdash S_1 \mid \Gamma_1$$

... (4)

$$\Gamma \vdash S_2 \mid \Gamma_2$$

... (5)

Using (2) and (3), from Lemma 8

$$\rho \vdash_p e \Downarrow v$$

... (6)

$$\vdash v : \text{bool}_p, p$$

... (7)

Applying IH using (2) and (4):

$$\rho \vdash S_1 \Downarrow \rho_1$$

... (8)

$$\rho_1 \models \Gamma_1$$

... (9)

Applying IH using (2) and (5):

$$\rho \vdash S_2 \Downarrow \rho_2$$

... (10)

$$\rho_2 \models \Gamma_2$$

... (11)

Using (4) from Lemma 5

$$\Gamma_1 \supseteq \Gamma$$

... (12)

Using (5) from Lemma 5

$$\Gamma_2 \supseteq \Gamma$$

... (13)

Depending on the value of $\text{istrue}(v)$ we have the following two cases :**Case1:** $\text{istrue}(v)$

Using (6) and (8), from A-IF rule,

$$\rho' = \rho_1$$

... (14)

$$\rho \vdash \text{if}(e, S_1, S_2) \Downarrow \rho'$$

Consequence (a)

Using (9), (12) and (14), from Lemma 3

$$\rho' \models \Gamma$$

Consequence (b)

Case2: $\neg \text{istrue}(v)$

Using (6) and (10), from A-IF rule,

$$\rho' = \rho_2$$

... (15)

$$\rho \vdash \text{if}(e, S_1, S_2) \Downarrow \rho'$$

Consequence (a)

Using (9), (13) and (15), from Lemma 3

$$\rho' \models \Gamma$$

Consequence (b)

T-FOR: We prove this case by induction on $n_2 - n_1$

Case: $n_2 - n_1 < 0$

In this case, consequence (a) follows from E-FOR_EXIT with $\rho' = \rho$. Consequence (b) follows from antecedent (2).

We now do induction for the case of $n_2 - n_1 \geq 0$.

Base Case: $n_2 - n_1 = 0$

$\Gamma \vdash_p \text{for } x \text{ in } [n_2, n_1] \text{ do } S \mid \Gamma$	Antecedent 1	...(1)
$\rho \models \Gamma$	Antecedent 2	...(2)
Inverting (1) with rule T-FOR:		
$\Gamma, x \mapsto (\text{uint}_p, p) \vdash S \mid \Gamma'$		...(3)
$x \notin \Gamma$		...(4)
$\text{party}(S) = p$		...(5)
Let $\rho^* = \rho[x \mapsto \text{makeval}(n_1, p)]$		...(6)
From V-NAT: $\vdash n_1 : \text{uint}_p$		...(7)
Using (7) from Lemma 1:		
$\vdash \text{makeval}(n_1, p) : \text{uint}_p, p$		...(8)
From (6) and (8):		
$\vdash \rho^*(x) : (\text{uint}_p, p)$		...(9)
Using (2), (4) and (6) from Lemma 6:		
$\rho^* \models \Gamma$		...(10)
Using (3), (9) and (10) from rule NON-EMP:		
$\rho^* \models \Gamma, x : (\text{uint}_p, p)$		...(11)
From (3) and (11) using I.H. for second lemma case		
$\rho^* \vdash S \Downarrow \rho'$		...(12)
$\rho' \models \Gamma'$		...(13)
Let $n'_1 = n_1 + 1$		...(14)
Using (3) from Lemma 5		
$\Gamma' \supseteq \Gamma, x \mapsto (\text{uint}_p, p)$		...(15)
$\Gamma' \supseteq \Gamma$		...(16)
From (13) and (16) using Lemma 3:		
$\rho' \models \Gamma$	Consequent (b)	...(17)
$n_2 - n'_1 < 0$		...(18)
From (18) using rule A-FOR_EXIT:		
$\rho' \vdash_p \text{for } x \text{ in } [n'_1, n_2] \text{ do } S \Downarrow \rho'$		...(19)
From (12) and (19) using rule A-FORI:		
$\rho \vdash_p \text{for } x \text{ in } [n_1, n_2] \text{ do } S \Downarrow \rho'$	Consequent (a)	...(20)
Consequent (b) follows from (17) and (20).		

Induction Case: $n_2 - n_1 \geq 0$

$\Gamma \vdash_p \text{ for } x \text{ in do } [n_1, n_2] \text{ do } S \mid \Gamma$	Antecedent 1	...(1)
$\rho \models \Gamma$	Antecedent 2	...(2)
Inverting (1) with rule T-FOR:		
$\Gamma, x : (\text{uint}_p, p) \vdash S \mid \Gamma'$		...(3)
$x \notin \Gamma$		...(4)
$\text{party}(S) = p$		...(5)
Let $\rho^* = \rho[x \mapsto \text{makeval}(n_1, p)]$		...(6)
From V-NAT: $\vdash n_1 : \text{uint}_p$		...(7)
Using (7) from Lemma 1:		
$\vdash \text{makeval}(n_1, p) : \text{uint}_p, p$		...(8)
From (6) and (8):		
$\vdash \rho^*(x) : (\text{uint}_p, p)$		...(9)
Using (2), (4) and (6) from Lemma 6:		
$\rho^* \models \Gamma$		...(10)
Using (3), (9) and (10) from rule NON-EMP:		
$\rho^* \models \Gamma, x : (\text{uint}_p, p)$		...(11)
From (3) and (11) using I.H. for second lemma case		
$\rho^* \vdash S \Downarrow \rho'$		...(12)
$\rho' \models \Gamma'$		...(13)
Let $n'_1 = n_1 + 1$		
Using (3) from Lemma 5		
$\Gamma' \supseteq \Gamma, x \mapsto (\text{uint}_p, p)$		...(15)
$\Gamma' \supseteq \Gamma$		...(16)
From (13) and (16) using Lemma 3:		
$\rho' \models \Gamma$		...(17)
From T-FOR rule using (3), (4), (5):		
$\Gamma \vdash_p \text{ for } x \text{ in do } [n'_1, n_2] \text{ do } S : \Gamma$		...(18)
From (13), $n_2 - n'_1 < n_2 - n_1$		...(19)
From (17), (18), (19) using I.H. for third lemma case		
$\rho' \vdash_p \text{ for } x \text{ in do } [n'_1, n_2] \text{ do } S \Downarrow \rho''$		...(20)
$\rho'' \models \Gamma$	Consequent (b)	...(21)
From (12) and (20) using rule A-FORI:		
$\rho \vdash_p \text{ for } x \text{ in do } [n'_1, n_2] \text{ do } S \Downarrow \rho''$	Consequent (a)	...(22)
Consequence (b) follows from (21) and (22).		

□

Lemma 10. *If*

1. $\Gamma \vdash e : \tau, p$

2. $\mu \models \Gamma$

then,

a) $\mu \vdash_p e \downarrow \hat{v}$

b) $\hat{v} \models (\tau, p)$

Proof of Lemma 10. Proof by induction on size of typing proof tree.

Base cases:

T-UINT

$\Gamma \vdash n : \text{uint}_{p,p}$	Antecedent 1	...(1)
$\mu \models \Gamma$	Antecedent 2	...(2)
From rule R-CONSTANT, $\mu \vdash_p n \downarrow n, p$.	Consequent a	
From V-NAT: $\vdash n : \text{uint}_p$		...(3)
Using (3) from V-REF1, $\vdash (n, p) : \text{uint}_{p,p}$.		...(4)
From (4) using REF-NON-ARR, $(n, p) \models (\text{uint}_{p,p})$	Consequent b	

T-BOOL

$\Gamma \vdash t : \text{bool}_{p,p}$	Antecedent 1	...(1)
$\mu \models \Gamma$	Antecedent 2	...(2)
Inverting type rule, $t \in \{\text{true}, \text{false}\}$		
From rule R-CONSTANT, $\rho \vdash_p t \downarrow t, p$	Consequent a	
From V-BOOL: $\vdash t : \text{bool}_p$		...(3)
Using (3) from V-REF1, $\vdash (t, p) : \text{bool}_{p,p}$.		...(4)
From (4) using REF-NON-ARR, $(t, p) \models (\text{bool}_{p,p})$	Consequent b	

T-VAR

$\Gamma \vdash x : \tau, p$	Antecedent 1	...(1)
$\mu \models \Gamma$	Antecedent 2	...(2)
Inverting (1) with rule T-VAR:		
$\Gamma(x) = \tau, p'$		...(3)
public $\tau \implies p \subseteq p'$		...(4)
secret $\tau \implies p = p'$		...(5)
Case 1: public τ		
$p \subseteq p'$		...(6)
Since $\Gamma \neq \emptyset$ and (2), from rule NON-EMP-REF: $\exists \hat{v} \text{ s.t. :}$		
$\mu(x) = \hat{v}$		...(7)
$\hat{v} \models (\tau, p')$		...(8)
From rule R-VAR:		
$\mu \vdash_p x \downarrow \mu(x) _p$	Consequent a	...(9)
Since τ is public , $\tau = \gamma_p$ or $\tau = \gamma_p[n]$		
From (8) using rule REF-ARR/REF-NON-ARR:		
$\vdash \mu(x) : \tau, p'$		...(10)
Inverting (10) using rule V-STORE:		
$\vdash \pi_i(\mu(x)) : \tau$ if $i \in p'$ otherwise $\vdash \pi_i(\mu(x)) : \perp$		...(11)
From definition:		
$\pi_i(\mu(x) _p) = \pi_i(\mu(x))$ if $i \in p$ otherwise $\pi_i(\mu(x) _p) = \perp$		...(12)
Using (6), (11) and (12):		
$\forall i \in p, \vdash \pi_i(\mu(x) _p) : \tau$ and $\vdash \pi_i(\mu(x) _p) : \perp$ otherwise		...(13)
From (13) using rule V-STORE: $\vdash \mu(x) _p : \tau, p$		...(14)
From (14), using rule REF-ARR/REF-NON-ARR, $\hat{v} \models (\tau, p)$	Consequent b	
Case 2: secret τ		
$\Gamma(x) = \tau, p$		...(15)
Since $\Gamma \neq \emptyset$ and (2), from rule NON-EMP-REF: $\exists \hat{v} \text{ s.t. :}$		
$\mu(x) = \hat{v}$		...(16)
$\hat{v} \models \tau, p$		...(17)
From rule R-VAR: $\mu \vdash_p x \downarrow \mu(x) _p$	Consequent a	...(18)
Let $\tau' = \gamma_p$ if $\tau = \gamma_\ell$ or $\tau' = \gamma_p[n]$ if $\tau = \gamma_\ell[n]$ or		
$\tau' = \text{uint}_p[n]$ if $\tau = \text{oram}[n]$		
From (17) using rule REF-ARR/REF-NON-ARR/REF-ORAM:		
$\vdash \mu(x) : \tau', p$		...(19)
Inverting (7) using rule V-STORE:		
$\vdash \pi_i(\mu(x)) : \tau'$ if $i \in p$ otherwise $\vdash \pi_i(\mu(x)) : \perp$		...(20)
From definition:		
$\pi_i(\mu(x) _p) = \pi_i(\mu(x))$ if $i \in p$ otherwise $\pi_i(\mu(x) _p) = \perp$		...(21)
Using (20) and (21):		
$\forall i \in p, \vdash \pi_i(\mu(x) _p) : \tau'$ and $\vdash \pi_i(\mu(x) _p) : \perp$ otherwise		...(22)
From (22) using rule V-STORE: $\vdash \mu(x) _p : \tau', p$		...(23)
From (23) using REF-ARR/REF-NON-ARR/REF-ORAM:		
$\hat{v} \models (\tau, p)$	Consequent b	

Induction cases:

T-BINOP

$\Gamma \vdash e_1 \oplus e_2 : \text{uint}_{\ell}, p$ Antecedent 1 ... (1)

$\mu \models \Gamma$ Antecedent 2 ... (2)

Inverting (1) with T-BINOP:

$\Gamma \vdash e_1 : \text{uint}_{\ell_1}, p$... (3)

$\Gamma \vdash e_2 : \text{uint}_{\ell_2}, p$... (4)

Using (2) and (3), from I.H.

$\mu \vdash_p e_1 \downarrow c_1, p$... (5)

$(c_1, p) \models \text{uint}_{\ell_1}, p$... (6)

Using (2) and (4), from I.H.

$\mu \vdash_p e_2 \downarrow c_2, p$... (7)

$(c_2, p) \models \text{uint}_{\ell_2}, p$... (8)

Using (5) and (7), from rule R-BINOP:

$\mu \vdash_p e_1 \oplus e_2 \downarrow (c_1 + c_2), p$... (9)

This proves consequent (a).

Using (6) from REF-NON-ARRAY:

$\vdash (c_1, p) : \text{uint}_p, p$... (10)

Using (10) from rule V-REF1:

$\vdash c_1 : \text{uint}_p$... (11)

Using (8) from REF-NON-ARRAY:

$\vdash (c_2, p) : \text{uint}_p, p$... (12)

Using (12) from rule V-REF1:

$\vdash c_2 : \text{uint}_p$... (13)

From (11) and (13):

$\vdash c_1 \oplus c_2 : \text{uint}_p$... (14)

Using (14) from V-REF1:

$\vdash (c_1 \oplus c_2), p : \text{uint}_p, p$... (15)

Consequent (b) follows from REF-NON-ARRAY using (1), (9) and (15).

T-GT

$\Gamma \vdash e_1 > e_2 : \text{bool}_{\ell}, p$ Antecedent 1 ... (1)

$\mu \models \Gamma$ Antecedent 2 ... (2)

Inverting (1) with T-GT:

$\Gamma \vdash e_1 : \text{uint}_{\ell_1}, p$... (3)

$\Gamma \vdash e_2 : \text{uint}_{\ell_2}, p$... (4)

Using (2) and (3), from I.H.

$\mu \vdash_p e_1 \downarrow c_1, p$... (5)

$(c_1, p) \models \text{uint}_{\ell_1}, p$... (6)

Using (2) and (4), from I.H.

$\mu \vdash_p e_2 \downarrow c_2, p$... (7)

$(c_2, p) \models \text{uint}_{\ell_2}, p$... (8)

Using (5) and (7), from rule R-GT:

$\mu \vdash_p e_1 > e_2 \downarrow (c_1 > c_2), p$... (9)

This proves consequent (a).

Using (6) from REF-NON-ARRAY:

$\vdash (c_1, p) : \text{uint}_p, p$... (10)

Using (10) from rule V-REF1:

$\vdash c_1 : \text{uint}_p$... (11)

Using (8) from REF-NON-ARRAY:

$\vdash (c_2, p) : \text{uint}_p, p$... (12)

Using (12) from rule V-REF1:

$\vdash c_2 : \text{uint}_p$... (13)

From (11) and (13):

$\vdash c_1 > c_2 : \text{bool}_p$... (14)

Using (14) from V-REF1:

$\vdash (c_1 > c_2), p : \text{bool}_p, p$... (15)

Consequent (b) follows from REF-NON-ARRAY using (1), (9) and (15).

T-MUX

$\Gamma \vdash e_1? e_2 : e_3 : \gamma_\ell, p$	Antecedent 1	...(1)
$\mu \models \Gamma$	Antecedent 2	...(2)
Inverting (1) with T-MUX:		
$\Gamma \vdash e_1 : \text{bool}_{\ell_1}, p$		...(3)
$\Gamma \vdash e_2 : \gamma_{\ell_2}, p$		...(4)
$\Gamma \vdash e_3 : \gamma_{\ell_3}, p$		...(5)
Using (2) and (3), from I.H.		
$\mu \vdash_p e_1 \downarrow c_1, p$		...(6)
$(c_1, p) \models \text{bool}_{\ell_1}, p$		...(7)
Using (2) and (4), from I.H.		
$\mu \vdash_p e_2 \downarrow c_2, p$		...(8)
$(c_2, p) \models \gamma_{\ell_2}, p$		...(9)
Using (2) and (5), from I.H.		
$\mu \vdash_p e_3 \downarrow c_3, p$		...(10)
$(c_2, p) \models \gamma_{\ell_3}, p$		...(11)
Using (6), (8) and (10), from rule R-MUX:		
$\mu \vdash_p e_1? e_2 : e_3 \downarrow ?_\ell(c_1, c_2, c_3), p$		...(12)
This proves consequent (a).		
Using (7) from REF-NON-ARR:		
$\vdash (c_1, p) : \text{bool}_p, p$		...(13)
Using (13) from rule V-REF1:		
$\vdash c_1 : \text{bool}_p$		...(14)
Using (9) from REF-NON-ARR:		
$\vdash (c_2, p) : \gamma_p, p$		...(15)
Using (15) from rule V-REF1:		
$\vdash c_2 : \gamma_p$		...(16)
Using (11) from REF-NON-ARR:		
$\vdash (c_3, p) : \gamma_p, p$		...(17)
Using (17) from rule V-REF1:		
$\vdash c_3 : \gamma_p$		...(18)
Using (14), (16) and (18):		
$\vdash ?(c_1, c_2, c_3) : \gamma_p$		...(19)
Using (19) from rule V-REF1:		
$\vdash ?(c_1, c_2, c_3), p : \gamma_p, p$		...(20)
Consequent (b) follows from REF-NON-ARR using (1), (12) and (20)		

T-ARR

$\Gamma \vdash [\overline{e_i}]_n : \gamma_\ell[n], p$ Antecedent 1 ... (1)

$\mu \models \Gamma$ Antecedent 2 ... (2)

Inverting (1) using T-ARR:

$\forall i \in [n], \Gamma \vdash e_i : \gamma_\ell, p$... (3)

Using (2) and (3), from I.H.:

$\forall i \in [n], \mu \vdash_p e_i \downarrow c_i, p$... (4)

$\forall i \in [n], (c_i, p) \models \gamma_\ell, p$... (5)

Using (4), from rule R-ARR:

$\mu \vdash_p [\overline{e_i}]_n \downarrow [c_1, \dots, c_n], p$... (6)

This proves consequent (a).

From (5) with rule REF-NON-ARR:

$\forall i \in [n] \vdash (c_i, p) : \gamma_p, p$... (7)

Using (7) from rule V-REF1:

$\forall i \in [n], \vdash c_i : \gamma_p$... (8)

Using (8), from rule V-ARR

$\vdash [c_1, \dots, c_n] : \gamma_p[n]$... (9)

Using (9) from rule V-REF2

$\vdash [c_1, \dots, c_n], p : \gamma_p[n], p$... (10)

Consequent (b) follows from (1), (6) and (10) using REF-ARR.

T-ARR_READ

$\Gamma \vdash x[e] : \gamma_\ell, p$	Antecedent 1	...(1)
$\mu \models \Gamma$	Antecedent 2	...(2)
Inverting (1) using rule T-ARR_READ:		
$\Gamma \vdash x : \gamma_\ell[n], p$		...(3)
$\Gamma \vdash e : \mathbf{uint}_p, p$		...(4)
$\Gamma \models e < n$		...(5)
Using (2) and (3), from I.H.		
$\mu \vdash_p x \downarrow [\bar{c}_i]_n, p$		...(6)
$([\bar{c}_i]_n, p) \models \gamma_\ell[n], p$		...(7)
Using (2) and (4), from I.H.		
$\mu \vdash_p e \downarrow c, p$		...(8)
$(c, p) \models \mathbf{uint}_p, p$		...(9)
From (7) and (9), using rule R-ARR_READ		
$\mu \vdash_p x[e] \downarrow u[c], p$ where $u = [\bar{c}_i]_n$		...(10)
This proves consequent (a).		
From (7) using REF-ARR:		
$\vdash [\bar{c}_i]_n, p : \gamma_p[n], p$		...(11)
From (11) using rule V-REF2:		
$\vdash [\bar{c}_i]_n : \gamma_p[n]$		...(12)
From 5:		
$c < n$		...(13)
Using (10), (12) and (13), from rule V-ARR:		
$\vdash u[c] : \gamma_p$		...(14)
Using (14) from rule V-REF1:		
$\vdash u[c], p : \gamma_p, p$		...(15)
Consequent (b) follows from (1), (10) and (15) using rule REF-NON-ARR.		

T-ORAM

$\Gamma \vdash \mathbf{Oram}(e) : \mathbf{oram}[n], p$	Antecedent 1	...(1)
$\mu \models \Gamma$	Antecedent 2	...(2)
Inverting (1) using T-ORAM:		
$\Gamma \vdash e : \mathbf{uint}_s[n], p$		...(3)
Using (2) and (3), from I.H.:		
$\mu \vdash_p e \downarrow \hat{v}$		...(4)
$\hat{v} \models \gamma_s[n], p$		...(5)
From REF-ARR using (4), $\vdash \hat{v} : \mathbf{uint}_p[n], p$		...(6)
From REF-ORAM using (6), $\hat{v} \models \mathbf{oram}[n], p$		...(7)
From R-ORAM using (4), $\mu \vdash_p \mathbf{Oram}(e) \downarrow \hat{v}$	Consequent a	
Consequent b follows from (7)		

□

Lemma 11. • *If*

1. $\Gamma \vdash_p s \mid \Gamma'$
2. $\mu \models \Gamma$
3. s is not a loop statement.

then

- a) $\mu \vdash_p s \downarrow \mu', _$
- b) $\mu' \models \Gamma'$

• *If*

1. $\Gamma \vdash S \mid \Gamma'$
2. $\mu \models \Gamma$

then

- a) $\mu \vdash S \downarrow \mu', _$
- b) $\mu' \models \Gamma'$

• *If*

1. $\Gamma \vdash_p \text{for } x \text{ in } [n_1, n_2] \text{ do } S \mid \Gamma$
2. $\mu \models \Gamma$

then

- a) $\mu \vdash_p \text{for } x \text{ in } [n_1, n_2] \text{ do } S \downarrow \mu', _$
- b) $\mu' \models \Gamma'$

Proof of Lemma 11. We prove by mutual induction on the size of typing proof tree and $n_2 - n_1$.

Notation (only for this proof): $\mu \vdash_p s \downarrow \mu' \equiv \mu \vdash_p s \downarrow \mu', _, _$

$\mu \vdash S \downarrow \mu' \equiv \mu \vdash S \downarrow \mu', _, _$

Base Cases:

T-DEF

$$\Gamma \vdash_p (\tau \ x = e) \mid \Gamma, x : (\tau, p). \quad \text{Antecedant 1} \quad \dots(1)$$

$$\mu \models \Gamma \quad \text{Antecedant 2} \quad \dots(2)$$

Inverting (1) with rule T-DEF:

$$\Gamma \vdash e : \tau, p \quad \dots(3)$$

$$x \notin \Gamma \quad \dots(4)$$

Using (2) and (3), from Lemma 10:

$$\mu \vdash_p e \downarrow \hat{v} \quad \dots(5)$$

$$\hat{v} \models \tau, p \quad \dots(6)$$

Applying R-DEF rule using (5):

$$\mu \vdash_p (\tau \ x = e) \downarrow \mu[x \mapsto \hat{v}] \quad \text{Consequent a}$$

$$\text{Let } \mu' = \mu[x \mapsto \hat{v}] \quad \dots(7)$$

$$\text{From (6), (7), } \mu'(x) \models (\tau, p) \quad \dots(8)$$

Let $\Gamma' = \emptyset$

$$\text{Using REF-EMP rule, } \mu' \models \Gamma' \quad \dots(9)$$

Applying NON-EMP-REF rule using (2), (8), (9):

$$\mu' \models \Gamma, x : (\tau, p), \Gamma'$$

$$\implies \mu' \models \Gamma, x : (\tau, p) \quad \text{Consequent b}$$

T-ASSIGN

$$\Gamma \vdash_p (x = e) \mid \Gamma \quad \text{Antecedant 1} \quad \dots(1)$$

$$\mu \models \Gamma \quad \text{Antecedant 2} \quad \dots(2)$$

Inverting (1) with rule T-ASSIGN:

$$\Gamma \vdash x : \gamma_\ell, p \quad \dots(3)$$

$$\Gamma \vdash e : \gamma_\ell, p \quad \dots(4)$$

From (3):

$$\Gamma = \Gamma_1, x : (\gamma_\ell, p), \Gamma_2 \quad \dots(5)$$

From inversion of NON-EMP-REF rule using (2) and (5), from :

$$\mu_1 \models \Gamma_1 \quad \dots(6)$$

$$\mu_2 \models \Gamma_2 \quad \dots(7)$$

From (5):

$$x \notin \Gamma_1 \quad \dots(8)$$

$$x \notin \Gamma_2 \quad \dots(9)$$

Using (2) and (4), from Lemma 10:

$$\mu \vdash_p e \downarrow \hat{v} \quad \dots(10)$$

$$\hat{v} \models \gamma_\ell, p \quad \dots(11)$$

Applying R-ASSIGN rule using (9):

$$\mu \vdash_p (x = e) \downarrow \mu[x \mapsto \hat{v}] \quad \text{Consequent a}$$

$$\mu' = \mu[x \mapsto \hat{v}] \quad \dots(12)$$

From lemma 7 using (6) and (8):

$$\mu' \models \Gamma_1 \quad \dots(13)$$

From lemma 7 using (7) and (9):

$$\mu' \models \Gamma_2 \quad \dots(14)$$

Applying NON-EMP-REF rule using (5), (11), (12), (13), (14):

$$\mu' \models \Gamma \quad \text{Consequent b}$$

T-INPUT

$\Gamma \vdash_p \text{input}(x, \tau) \mid \Gamma, x : (\tau, p).$	Antecedant 1	...(1)
$\mu \models \Gamma$	Antecedant 2	...(2)
From inversion of T-INPUT rule using (1):		
$x \notin \Gamma$		...(3)
labelof $\tau = p$		...(4)
Let $\hat{v} = \text{userin}(\tau, p)$		...(5)
From Axiom 1 using (4), $\vdash \hat{v} : (\tau, p)$		...(6)
From REF-NON-ARR rule using (4), (5):		
$\hat{v} \models (\tau, p)$		...(7)
From rule R-INPUT using (5):		
$\mu \vdash_p \text{input}(x, \tau) \downarrow \mu[x \mapsto \hat{v}]$	Consequent a	...(8)
$\mu' = \mu[x \mapsto \hat{v}]$		...(9)
From Lemma 7 using (2), (3), $\mu' \models \Gamma$		...(10)
Let $\Gamma' = \emptyset$		
Using REF-EMP rule, $\mu' \models \Gamma'$		...(11)
Applying NON-EMP-REF rule using (2), (10), (11):		
$\mu' \models \Gamma, x : (\tau, p), \Gamma'$		
$\implies \mu' \models \Gamma, x : (\tau, p)$	Consequent b	

T-ORAM_READ

$\Gamma \vdash_p y = \text{OramRead}(x, e) \mid \Gamma, y : \text{uint}_s, p$	Antecedent 1	...(1)
$\mu \models \Gamma$	Antecedent 2	...(2)
Inverting (1) using rule T-ORAM_READ:		
$\Gamma \vdash x : \text{oram}[n], p$		...(3)
$\Gamma \vdash e : \text{uint}_\ell, p$		...(4)
$y \notin \Gamma$		...(5)
Using (2) and (3), from I.H.		
$\mu \vdash_p x \downarrow [\bar{c}_i]_n, p$		...(6)
$([\bar{c}_i]_n, p) \models \text{oram}[n], p$		...(7)
Using (2) and (4), from I.H.		
$\mu \vdash_p e \downarrow c, p$		...(8)
$(c, p) \models \text{uint}_\ell, p$		...(9)
From (7) and (9), using rule R-ORAM_READ		
$\mu \vdash_p y = \text{OramRead}(x, e) \downarrow \mu[y \mapsto \hat{v}]$ where,		
$\hat{v} = ((0 \leq c < n) ? u[c], 0), p$ and $u = [\bar{c}_i]_n$		...(10)
This proves consequent (a).		
From (7) using REF-ORAM:		
$\vdash [\bar{c}_i]_n, p : \text{uint}_p[n], p$		...(11)
From (11) using rule V-REF2:		
$\vdash [\bar{c}_i]_n : \text{uint}_p[n]$		...(12)
Using (9), (11) and (12), from rule V-ARR:		
$\vdash u[c] : \text{uint}_p$		...(13)
From V-NAT, $\vdash 0 : \text{uint}_p, p$		
		...(14)
Using (10), (13), (14) from rule V-REF1:		
$\vdash \hat{v} : \text{uint}_p, p$		...(15)
$\implies \hat{v} \models \text{uint}_s, p$		...(16)
Let $\mu' = \rho[y \mapsto \hat{v}]$		...(17)
Applying NON-EMP-REF rule using (2), (16), (17):		
$\mu' \models \Gamma, y : \text{uint}_s, p$	Consequent b	

T-ORAM_WRITE

$\Gamma \vdash_p \text{OramWrite}(x, e_1, e_2) \mid \Gamma$	Antecedant 1	...(1)
$\mu \models \Gamma$	Antecedant 2	...(2)
Inverting (1) using T-ORAM_WRITE:		
$\Gamma \vdash x : (\text{oram}[n], p)$		...(3)
$\implies \Gamma = \Gamma_1, x : (\text{oram}[n], p), \Gamma_2 \quad \text{s.t. } x \notin \Gamma_1, x \notin \Gamma_2$		...(4)
$\Gamma \vdash e_1 : (\text{uint}_{\ell_1}, p)$		...(5)
$\Gamma \vdash e_2 : (\text{uint}_{\ell_2}, p)$		...(6)
From Lemma 10 using (2), (3):		
$\mu \vdash_p x \downarrow \hat{v}$		...(7)
$\hat{v} \models (\text{oram}[n], p)$		...(8)
From REF-ARR using (9), $\vdash \hat{v} : (\text{uint}_p[n], p)$		
$\implies \hat{v} = [\bar{c}_i]_n, p \quad \vdash \bar{c}_i : \text{uint}_p$		...(10)
From Lemma 10 using (2), (5):		
$\mu \vdash_p e_1 \downarrow \hat{v}_1$		...(11)
$\hat{v}_1 \models (\text{uint}_{\ell_1}, p)$		...(12)
From REF-NON-ARR using (12), $\vdash \hat{v}_1 : (\text{uint}_p, p)$		
$\implies \hat{v}_1 = c_1, p$		...(14)
From Lemma 10 using (2), (6):		
$\mu \vdash_p e_2 \downarrow \hat{v}_2$		...(15)
$\hat{v}_2 \models (\text{uint}_{\ell_2}, p)$		...(16)
From REF-NON-ARR using (16), $\vdash \hat{v}_2 : (\text{uint}_p, p)$		
$\implies \hat{v}_2 = c_2, p$		...(18)
Let $u = [\bar{c}_i]_n$		
$\vdash u : \text{uint}_p[n]$		...(19)
From V-ARR using (9), (10), (19), $\vdash u : \text{uint}_p[n]$		
$\vdash u : \text{uint}_p[n]$		...(20)
Let $\hat{v}' = u', p$ where		
$u'[c_1] = c_2$ if $0 \leq c_1 < n$		...(21)
$\forall i \in [n], i \neq c_1, u'[i] = u[i]$		...(22)
From (19), (21), (22): $\vdash u' : \text{uint}_p[n]$		
$\vdash u' : \text{uint}_p[n]$		...(23)
From REF-ORAM, $\hat{v}' \models \text{oram}[n], p$		
From rule R-ORAM_WRITE using (11), (15), (19), (21), (22):		
$\mu \vdash_p \text{OramWrite}(x, e_1, e_2) \downarrow \mu'$ where $\mu' = \mu[x \mapsto \hat{v}']$	Consequent a	...(24)
From inversion of NON-EMP-REF rule using (2), (4), (8),		
$\mu \models \Gamma_1, \mu \models \Gamma_2$		...(25)
From Lemma 7, using (4), (24), (25)		
$\mu' \models \Gamma_1, \mu' \models \Gamma_2$		...(26)
Applying NON-EMP-REF rule using (4), (23), (26):		
$\mu' \models \Gamma$	Consequent b	

T-REVEAL

$\Gamma \vdash (\gamma_p \ x_1 = \text{reveal}(x_2, p)) \mid \Gamma, x_1 : (\gamma_p, p)$ Antecedant 1 ... (1)
 $\mu \models \Gamma$ Antecedant 2 ... (2)

Inverting (1) using T-REVEAL:

$\Gamma(x_2) = (\gamma_s, p')$... (3)

$x_1 \notin \Gamma$... (4)

From Lemma 10 using (2), (3):

$\mu \vdash_p x_2 \downarrow \hat{v}_2$... (5)

$\hat{v}_2 \models (\gamma_s, p')$... (6)

From inversion of REF-NON-ARR, $\vdash \hat{v}_2 : (\gamma_p, p')$... (7)

$\implies \hat{v}_2 = c, p'$ where $\vdash c : \gamma_p$... (8)

Let $\hat{v} = c, p$... (9)

From V-REF1 (8), $\vdash \hat{v} : (\gamma_p, p)$... (10)

From REF-NON-ARR using (10), $\hat{v} \models (\gamma_p, p)$... (11)

From rule R-REVEAL using (5), (9):

$\mu \vdash (\gamma_p \ x_1 = \text{reveal}(x_2, p)) \downarrow \mu[x_1 \mapsto \hat{v}]$ Consequent a ... (12)

Let $\mu' = \mu[x \mapsto \hat{v}]$... (13)

Let $\Gamma' = \emptyset$

Using REF-EMP rule, $\mu' \models \Gamma'$... (14)

Applying NON-EMP-REF rule using (2), (11), (14):

$\mu' \models \Gamma, x_1 : (\gamma_p, p), \Gamma'$

$\implies \mu' \models \Gamma, x_1 : (\gamma_p, p)$ Consequent b

T-MAKESH

$\Gamma \vdash (\gamma_s \ x_1 = \text{makesh}(x_2, p)) \mid \Gamma, x_1 : (\gamma_s, p)$ Antecedant 1 ... (1)
 $\mu \models \Gamma$ Antecedant 2 ... (2)

Inverting (1) using T-MAKESH:

$\Gamma(x_2) = (\gamma_p, p')$... (3)

$x_1 \notin \Gamma$... (4)

From Lemma 10 using (2), (3):

$\mu \vdash_p x_2 \downarrow \hat{v}_2$... (5)

$\hat{v}_2 \models (\gamma_p, p')$... (6)

From REF-NON-ARR, $\vdash \hat{v}_2 : (\gamma_p, p')$... (7)

$\implies \hat{v}_2 = c, p'$ where $\vdash c : \gamma_p$... (8)

Let $\hat{v} = c, p$... (9)

From V-REF1 (8), $\vdash \hat{v} : (\gamma_p, p)$... (10)

From REF-NON-ARR using (10), $\hat{v} \models (\gamma_s, p)$... (11)

From rule R-MAKESH using (5), (9):

$\mu \vdash (\gamma_s \ x_1 = \text{makesh}(x_2, p)) \downarrow \mu[x_1 \mapsto \hat{v}]$ Consequent a ... (12)

Let $\mu' = \mu[x \mapsto \hat{v}]$... (13)

Let $\Gamma' = \emptyset$

Using REF-EMP rule, $\mu' \models \Gamma'$... (14)

Applying NON-EMP-REF rule using (2), (11), (14):

$\mu' \models \Gamma, x_1 : (\gamma_s, p), \Gamma'$

$\implies \mu' \models \Gamma, x_1 : (\gamma_s, p)$ Consequent b

T-RESHARE

$\Gamma \vdash (\gamma_s \ x_1 = \text{reshare}(x_2, p)) \mid \Gamma, x_1 : (\gamma_s, p)$ Antecedant 1 ... (1)
 $\mu \models \Gamma$ Antecedant 2 ... (2)

Inverting (1) using T-RESHARE:

$\Gamma(x_2) = (\gamma_s, p')$... (3)

$x_1 \notin \Gamma$... (4)

From Lemma 10 using (2), (3):

$\mu \vdash_p x_2 \downarrow \hat{v}_2$... (5)

$\hat{v}_2 \models (\gamma_s, p')$... (6)

From inversion of REF-NON-ARR, $\vdash \hat{v}_2 : (\gamma_p, p')$... (7)

$\implies \hat{v}_2 = c, p'$ where $\vdash c : \gamma_p$... (8)

Let $\hat{v} = c, p$... (9)

From V-REF1 (8), $\vdash \hat{v} : (\gamma_P, p)$... (10)

From REF-NON-ARR using (10), $\hat{v} \models (\gamma_s, p)$... (11)

From rule R-SHARE using (5), (9):

$\mu \vdash (\gamma_s \ x_1 = \text{reshare}(x_2, p)) \downarrow \mu[x_1 \mapsto \hat{v}]$ Consequent a ... (12)

Let $\mu' = \mu[x \mapsto \hat{v}]$... (13)

Let $\Gamma' = \emptyset$

Using REF-EMP rule, $\mu' \models \Gamma'$... (14)

Applying NON-EMP-REF rule using (2), (11), (14):

$\mu' \models \Gamma, x_1 : (\gamma_s, p), \Gamma'$

$\implies \mu' \models \Gamma, x_1 : (\gamma_s, p)$ Consequent b

T-BROADCAST

$\Gamma \vdash (\gamma_p \ x_1 = \text{broadcast}(x_2, p)) \mid \Gamma, x_1 : (\gamma_p, p)$ Antecedant 1 ... (1)
 $\mu \models \Gamma$ Antecedant 2 ... (2)

Inverting (1) using T-BROADCAST:

$\Gamma(x_2) = (\gamma_p, p')$... (3)

$x_1 \notin \Gamma$... (4)

From Lemma 10 using (2), (3):

$\mu \vdash_p x_2 \downarrow \hat{v}_2$... (5)

$\hat{v}_2 \models (\gamma_p, p')$... (6)

From inversion of REF-NON-ARR, $\vdash \hat{v}_2 : (\gamma_p, p')$... (7)

$\implies \hat{v}_2 = c, p'$ where $\vdash c : \gamma_p$... (8)

Let $\hat{v} = c, p$... (9)

From V-REF1 (8), $\vdash \hat{v} : (\gamma_p, p)$... (10)

From REF-NON-ARR using (10), $\hat{v} \models (\gamma_p, p)$... (11)

From rule R-SHARE using (5), (9):

$\mu \vdash (\gamma_p \ x_1 = \text{broadcast}(x_2, p)) \downarrow \mu[x_1 \mapsto \hat{v}]$ Consequent a ... (12)

Let $\mu' = \mu[x \mapsto \hat{v}]$... (13)

Let $\Gamma' = \emptyset$

Using REF-EMP rule, $\mu' \models \Gamma'$... (14)

Applying NON-EMP-REF rule using (2), (11), (14):

$\mu' \models \Gamma, x_1 : (\gamma_p, p), \Gamma'$

$\implies \mu' \models \Gamma, x_1 : (\gamma_p, p)$ Consequent b

T-ARR_WRITE

$\Gamma \vdash_p x[e_1] = e_2 \mid \Gamma$	Antecedant 1	...(1)
$\mu \models \Gamma$	Antecedant 2	...(2)
Inverting (1) using T-ARR_WRITE:		
$\Gamma \vdash x : (\gamma_\ell[n], p)$		...(3)
$\implies \Gamma = \Gamma_1, x : (\gamma_\ell[n], p), \Gamma_2$ s.t. $x \notin \Gamma_1, x \notin \Gamma_2$		...(4)
$\Gamma \vdash e_1 : (\text{uint}_p, p)$		...(5)
$\Gamma \vdash e_2 : (\gamma_\ell, p)$		...(6)
From Lemma 10 using (2), (3):		
$\mu \vdash_p x \downarrow \hat{v}$		...(7)
$\hat{v} \models (\gamma_\ell[n], p)$		...(8)
From REF-ARR using (8), $\vdash \hat{v} : (\gamma_p[n], p)$		...(9)
$\implies \hat{v} = [\bar{c}_i]_n, p$		...(10)
From Lemma 10 using (2), (5):		
$\mu \vdash_p e_1 \downarrow \hat{v}_1$		...(11)
$\hat{v}_1 \models (\text{uint}_p, p)$		...(12)
From REF-NON-ARR using (12), $\vdash \hat{v}_1 : (\text{uint}_p, p)$		...(13)
$\implies \hat{v}_1 = c_1, p$		...(14)
From Lemma 10 using (2), (6):		
$\mu \vdash_p e_2 \downarrow \hat{v}_2$		...(15)
$\hat{v}_2 \models (\gamma_\ell, p)$		...(16)
From REF-NON-ARR using (16), $\vdash \hat{v}_2 : (\gamma_p, p)$		...(17)
$\implies \hat{v}_2 = c_2, p$		...(18)
Let $u = [\bar{c}_i]_n$		...(19)
From V-ARR using (19), $\vdash u : \gamma_p[n]$		...(20)
Let $\hat{v}' = u', p$ where		
$u'[c_1] = c_2$		...(21)
$\forall i \in [n], i \neq c_1, u'[i] = u[i]$		...(22)
From (19), (21), (22): $\vdash u' : \gamma_P[n]$		
From REF-ARR, $\hat{v}' \models \gamma_\ell[n], p$		...(23)
From rule R-ARR_WRITE using (11), (15), (19), (21), (22):		
$\mu \vdash_p x[e_1] = e_2 \downarrow \mu'$ where $\mu' = \mu[x \mapsto \hat{v}']$	Consequent a	...(24)
From inversion of NON-EMP-REF rule using (2), (4),		
$\mu \models \Gamma_1, \mu \models \Gamma_2$		...(25)
From Lemma 7, using (24), (25)		
$\mu' \models \Gamma_1, \mu' \models \Gamma_2$		...(26)
Applying NON-EMP-REF rule using (4), (26):		
$\mu' \models \Gamma$	Consequent b	

Induction Cases:

T-AS

$$\Gamma \vdash_p \text{as}(p, s) \mid \Gamma' \quad \text{Antecedant 1} \quad \dots(1)$$

$$\mu \models \Gamma \quad \text{Antecedant 2} \quad \dots(2)$$

Inverting (1) with rule T-AS:

$$\Gamma \vdash_p s \mid \Gamma' \quad \dots(3)$$

Applying IH using (2) and (3):

$$\mu \vdash_p s \downarrow \rho' \quad \dots(4)$$

$$\mu' \models \Gamma' \quad \text{Consequent b} \quad \dots(5)$$

Applying R-AS rule using (4):

$$\mu \vdash_p \text{as}(p, s) \downarrow \mu' \quad \text{Consequent a}$$

T-SEQ

$$\Gamma \vdash_p s_1; s_2 \mid \Gamma' \quad \text{Antecedant 1} \quad \dots(1)$$

$$\mu \models \Gamma \quad \text{Antecedant 2} \quad \dots(2)$$

Inverting (1) with rule T-SEQ:

$$\Gamma \vdash_p s_1 \mid \Gamma_1 \quad \dots(3)$$

$$\Gamma_1 \vdash_p s_2 \mid \Gamma' \quad \dots(4)$$

Applying IH using (2) and (3):

$$\mu \vdash_p s_1 \downarrow \mu_1 \quad \dots(5)$$

$$\mu_1 \models \Gamma_1 \quad \dots(6)$$

Applying IH using (4) and (6):

$$\mu_1 \vdash_p s_2 \downarrow \mu' \quad \dots(7)$$

$$\mu' \models \Gamma' \quad \text{Consequent b}$$

Applying R-SEQ rule using (5), (7):

$$\mu \vdash_p s_1; s_2 \downarrow \mu' \quad \text{Consequent a}$$

T-ANNOT_SEQ

$\Gamma \vdash S_1; S_2 \mid \Gamma'$ Antecedant 1 ... (1)
 $\mu \models \Gamma$ Antecedant 2 ... (2)

Inverting (1) with rule T-ANNOT_SEQ:

$\Gamma \vdash S_1 \mid \Gamma_1$... (3)

$\Gamma_1 \vdash S_2 \mid \Gamma'$... (4)

Applying IH using (2) and (3):

$\mu \vdash S_1 \downarrow \mu_1$... (5)

$\mu_1 \models \Gamma_1$... (6)

Applying IH using (4) and (6):

$\mu_1 \vdash S_2 \downarrow \mu'$... (7)

$\mu' \models \Gamma'$ Consequent b

Applying R-ANNOT_SEQ rule using (5), (7):

$\mu \vdash S_1; S_2 \downarrow \mu'$ Consequent a

T-IF

$$\Gamma \vdash \text{if}(e, S_1, S_2) \mid \Gamma$$

$$\mu \models \Gamma$$

Antecedant 1 ... (1)

Antecedant 2 ... (2)

Inverting (1) with rule T-IF

$$\Gamma \vdash e : \text{bool}_p, p \quad \dots(3)$$

$$\Gamma \vdash S_1 \mid \Gamma_1 \quad \dots(4)$$

$$\Gamma \vdash S_2 \mid \Gamma_2 \quad \dots(5)$$

Using (2) and (3), from Lemma 10

$$\mu \vdash_p e \downarrow \hat{v} \quad \dots(6)$$

$$\hat{v} \models (\text{bool}_p, p) \quad \dots(7)$$

Applying IH using (2) and (4):

$$\mu \vdash S_1 \downarrow \mu_1 \quad \dots(8)$$

$$\mu_1 \models \Gamma_1 \quad \dots(9)$$

Applying IH using (2) and (5):

$$\mu \vdash S_2 \downarrow \mu_2 \quad \dots(10)$$

$$\mu_2 \models \Gamma_2 \quad \dots(11)$$

Using (4) from Lemma 5

$$\Gamma_1 \supseteq \Gamma \quad \dots(12)$$

Using (5) from Lemma 5

$$\Gamma_2 \supseteq \Gamma \quad \dots(13)$$
Depending on the value of $\text{istrue}(v)$ we have the following two cases :**Case1:** $\text{istrue}(\hat{v})$

From R-IF rule using (6), (8),

$$\mu' = \mu_1 \quad \dots(14)$$

$$\mu \vdash \text{if}(e, S_1, S_2) \downarrow \mu' \quad \text{Consequence a}$$

Using (9), (12) and (14), from Lemma 4

$$\mu' \models \Gamma \quad \text{Consequence (b)}$$
Case2: $\neg \text{istrue}(\hat{v})$

From R-IF rule using (6), (10),

$$\mu' = \mu_2 \quad \dots(15)$$

$$\mu \vdash \text{if}(e, S_1, S_2) \downarrow \mu' \quad \text{Consequence a}$$

Using (9), (13) and (15), from Lemma 4

$$\mu' \models \Gamma \quad \text{Consequence (b)}$$

T-FOR: We prove this case by induction on $n_2 - n_1$

Case: $n_2 - n_1 < 0$

In this case, consequence (a) follows from R-FOR_EXIT with $\mu' = \mu$. Consequence (b) follows from antecedent (2).

We now do induction for the case of $n_2 - n_1 \geq 0$.

Base Case: $n_2 - n_1 = 0$

$\Gamma \vdash_p \text{for } x \text{ in } [n_2, n_1] \text{ do } S \mid \Gamma$	Antecedent 1	...(1)
$\mu \models \Gamma$	Antecedent 2	...(2)
Inverting (1) with rule T-FOR:		
$\Gamma, x : (\text{uint}_p, p) \vdash S \mid \Gamma'$		...(3)
$x \notin \Gamma$		...(4)
$\text{party}(S) = p$		...(5)
Let $\mu^* = \mu[x \mapsto (n_1, p)]$		...(6)
From V-NAT: $\vdash n_1 : \text{uint}_p$		...(7)
From V-REF1 using (7): $\vdash (n_1, p) : \text{uint}_p, p$		...(8)
From REF-NON-ARR using (6) and (8):		
$\mu^*(x) \models (\text{uint}_p, p)$		...(9)
Using (2), (4) and (6) from Lemma 7:		
$\mu^* \models \Gamma$		...(10)
Using (3), (9) and (10) from rule NON-EMP-REF:		
$\mu^* \models \Gamma, x : (\text{uint}_p, p)$		...(11)
From (3) and (11) using I.H. for second lemma case		
$\mu^* \vdash S \downarrow \mu'$		...(12)
$\mu' \models \Gamma'$		...(13)
Let $n'_1 = n_1 + 1$		...(14)
Using (3) from Lemma 5		
$\Gamma' \supseteq \Gamma, x \mapsto (\text{uint}_p, p)$		...(15)
$\Gamma' \supseteq \Gamma$		...(16)
From (13) and (16) using Lemma 4:		
$\mu' \models \Gamma$	Consequent (b)	...(17)
$n_2 - n'_1 < 0$		...(18)
From (18) using rule R-FOR_EXIT:		
$\mu' \vdash_p \text{for } x \text{ in } [n'_1, n_2] \text{ do } S \downarrow \mu'$		...(19)
From (12) and (19) using rule R-FORI:		
$\mu \vdash_p \text{for } x \text{ in } [n_1, n_2] \text{ do } S \downarrow \mu'$	Consequent (a)	...(20)
Consequent (b) follows from (17) and (20).		

Induction Case: $n_2 - n_1 \geq 0$

$\Gamma \vdash_p \text{ for } x \text{ in do } [n_1, n_2] \text{ do } S \mid \Gamma$	Antecedent 1	...(1)
$\mu \models \Gamma$	Antecedent 2	...(2)
Inverting (1) with rule T-FOR:		
$\Gamma, x \mapsto (\text{uint}_p, p) \vdash S : \Gamma'$		...(3)
$x \notin \Gamma$		...(4)
$\text{party}(S) = p$		...(5)
Let $\mu^* = \mu[x \mapsto (n_1, p)]$		...(6)
From V-NAT: $\vdash n_1 : \text{uint}_p$		...(7)
From V-REF1 using (7): $\vdash (n_1, p) : \text{uint}_p, p$		...(8)
From REF-NON-ARR using (6) and (8):		
$\mu^*(x) \models (\text{uint}_p, p)$		...(9)
Using (2), (4) and (6) from Lemma 7:		
$\mu^* \models \Gamma$		...(10)
Using (3), (9) and (10) from rule NON-EMP-REF:		
$\mu^* \models \Gamma, x : (\text{uint}_p, p)$		...(11)
From (3) and (11) using I.H. for second lemma case		
$\mu^* \vdash S \downarrow \mu'$		...(12)
$\mu' \models \Gamma'$		...(13)
Let $n'_1 = n_1 + 1$		
Using (3) from Lemma 5		
$\Gamma' \supseteq \Gamma, x \mapsto (\text{uint}_p, p)$		...(15)
$\Gamma' \supseteq \Gamma$		...(16)
From (13) and (16) using Lemma 4:		
$\mu' \models \Gamma$		...(17)
From T-FOR rule using (3), (4), (5):		
$\Gamma \vdash_p \text{ for } x \text{ in do } [n'_1, n_2] \text{ do } S : \Gamma$		...(18)
From (13), $n_2 - n'_1 < n_2 - n_1$		...(19)
From (17), (18), (19) using I.H. for third lemma case		
$\mu' \vdash_p \text{ for } x \text{ in do } [n'_1, n_2] \text{ do } S \downarrow \mu''$		...(20)
$\mu'' \models \Gamma$	Consequent (b)	...(21)
From (12) and (20) using rule R-FORI:		
$\mu \vdash_p \text{ for } x \text{ in do } [n'_1, n_2] \text{ do } S \downarrow \mu''$	Consequent (a)	...(22)
Consequence (b) follows from (21) and (22).		

□

Lemma 12. *If*

1. $\rho \models \Gamma$
2. $\mu \models \Gamma$
3. $\rho \sim \mu$
4. $\Gamma \vdash e : (\tau, p)$

5. $\rho \vdash_p e \Downarrow v$

6. $\mu \vdash_p e \Downarrow \hat{v}$

then

a) $v \sim \hat{v}$

Proof of Lemma 12. Proof by induction on size of typing proof tree.

Base Cases:

T-UINT

$\rho \models \Gamma$	Antecedent 1	...(1)
$\mu \models \Gamma$	Antecedent 2	...(2)
$\rho \sim \mu$	Antecedent 3	...(3)
$\Gamma \vdash_p n : \text{uint}_{p,p}$	Antecedent 4	...(4)
$\rho \vdash_p n \Downarrow v$	Antecedent 5	...(5)
$\mu \vdash_p n \Downarrow \hat{v}$	Antecedent 6	...(6)
From (5) using rule A-CONSTANT:		
$v = \text{makeval}(n, p)$		...(7)
From (6) using rule R-CONSTANT:		
$\hat{v} = (n, p)$		...(8)
From (7) using definition of makeval:		
$\pi_i(v) = n$ if $i \in p$ otherwise $\perp$		...(9)
From (8) and (9) using VAL_EQ:		
$v = \hat{v}$		...(10)
From (1) and (4) using Lemma 8:		
$\vdash v : \text{uint}_{p,p}$		...(11)
From (2) and (4) using Lemma 10:		
$\vdash \hat{v} : \text{uint}_{p,p}$		...(12)
Consequence follows from SIM_NO_ARR using (10), (11) and (12).		

T-BOOL

$\rho \models \Gamma$	Antecedent 1	...(1)
$\mu \models \Gamma$	Antecedent 2	...(2)
$\rho \sim \mu$	Antecedent 3	...(3)
$\Gamma \vdash t : \mathbf{bool}_p, p$	Antecedent 4	...(4)
$\rho \vdash_p t \Downarrow v$	Antecedent 5	...(5)
$\mu \vdash_p t \Downarrow \hat{v}$	Antecedent 6	...(6)
From (5) using rule A-CONSTANT:		
$v = \mathbf{makeval}(t, p)$		...(7)
From (6) using rule R-CONSTANT:		
$\hat{v} = (t, p)$		...(8)
From (7) using definition of makeval:		
$\pi_i(v) = t$ if $i \in p$ otherwise $\perp$		...(9)
From (8) and (9) using VAL_EQ:		
$v = \hat{v}$		...(10)
From (1) and (4) using Lemma 8:		
$\vdash v : \mathbf{bool}_p, p$		...(11)
From (2) and (4) using Lemma 10:		
$\vdash \hat{v} : \mathbf{bool}_p, p$		...(12)
Consequence follows from SIM_NO_ARR using (10), (11) and (12).		

T-VAR:**Case I:** x is not an array.

$\rho \models \Gamma$	Antecedent 1	...(1)
$\mu \models \Gamma$	Antecedent 2	...(2)
$\rho \sim \mu$	Antecedent 3	...(3)
$\Gamma \vdash x : \tau, p$	Antecedent 4	...(4)
$\rho \vdash_p x \Downarrow v$	Antecedent 5	...(5)
$\mu \vdash_p x \Downarrow \hat{v}$	Antecedent 6	...(6)
Case a: public τ		
Inverting (4) using rule T-VAR		
$\Gamma(x) = \tau, p'$		...(7)
$p \subseteq p'$		...(8)
$\tau = \gamma_p$		...(9)
From (5) using A-VAR:		
$v = \rho(x) _p$		...(10)
From (6) using R-VAR:		
$\hat{v} = \mu(x) _p$		...(11)
From inversion of STORE_SIM using (3),		
$\rho(x) \sim \mu(x)$		...(12)
From (1), (7) and (9) using rule NON-EMP:		
$\vdash \rho(x) : \gamma_p, p'$		...(13)
From (2), (7) and (9) using rule NON-EMP-REF:		
$\mu(x) \models \gamma_p, p'$		...(14)
From (14) using REF-NON-ARR:		
$\vdash \mu(x) : \gamma_p, p'$		...(15)
From (12), (13) and (15) using SIM_NO_ARR:		
$\rho(x) = \mu(x)$		...(16)
From V-REF1, let $\mu(x) = (c, p')$		
		...(17)
From (16) and (17) using VAL_EQ:		
$\forall i \in p', \pi_i(\rho(x)) = c$		...(18)
$\forall i \notin p', \pi_i(\rho(x)) = \perp$		...(19)
From (11) and (17), by definition:		
$\hat{v} = c, p$		...(20)
From (10), by definition:		
$\pi_i(v) = \pi_i(\rho(x))$ if $i \in p$ otherwise $\pi_i(v) = \perp$		...(21)
From (8), (18), (19) and (21):		
$\forall i \in p, \pi_i(v) = c$		...(22)
$\forall i \notin p, \pi_i(v) = \perp$		...(23)
From (20), (22) and (23) using VAL_EQ: $v = \hat{v}$		
		...(24)
From (1), (4) and (5) using Lemma 8: $\vdash v : \gamma_p, p$		
		...(25)
From (2), (4) and (6) using Lemma 10: $\vdash \hat{v} : \gamma_p, p$		
		...(26)
Consequent follows from (24), (25) and (26) using SIM_NO_ARR		

Case b: secret τ

Inverting (4) using rule T-VAR

$$\Gamma(x) = \tau, p \quad \dots(27)$$

$$\tau = \gamma_s \quad \dots(28)$$

From (5) using A-VAR:

$$v = \rho(x)|_p \quad \dots(29)$$

From (6) using R-VAR:

$$\hat{v} = \mu(x)|_p \quad \dots(30)$$

From inversion of STORE_SIM using (3):

$$\rho(x) \sim \mu(x) \quad \dots(31)$$

From (1), (28) and (29) using rule NON-EMP:

$$\vdash \rho(x) : \gamma_s, p \quad \dots(32)$$

From (2), (28) and (29) using rule NON-EMP-REF:

$$\mu(x) \models \gamma_s, p \quad \dots(33)$$

From (33) using REF-NON-ARR:

$$\vdash \mu(x) : \gamma_p, p \quad \dots(34)$$

From (31), (32) and (34) using SIM_NO_ARR:

$$\mu(x) = \mathcal{D}(\rho(x), p, s) \quad \dots(35)$$

From V-REF1 using (34), let $\mu(x) = (c, p)$... (36)

From (30) and (376, by definition:

$$\hat{v} = c, p \quad \dots(37)$$

From (29), by definition:

$$\pi_i(v) = \pi_i(\rho(x)) \text{ if } i \in p \text{ otherwise } \pi_i(v) = \perp \quad \dots(38)$$

From (32) and (38) using V-STORE:

$$v = \rho(x) \quad \dots(39)$$

From (35), (36), (37), (38):

$$\hat{v} = \mathcal{D}(v, p, s) \quad \dots(40)$$

From (1), (4) and (5) using Lemma 8: $\vdash v : \gamma_s, p$... (41)

From (2), (4) and (6) using Lemma 10: $\vdash \hat{v} : \gamma_p, p$... (42)

Consequent follows from (40), (41) and (42) using SIM_NO_ARR

Case II: x is an array.

$\rho \models \Gamma$	Antecedent 1	...(1)
$\mu \models \Gamma$	Antecedent 2	...(2)
$\rho \sim \mu$	Antecedent 3	...(3)
$\Gamma \vdash x : \tau, p$	Antecedent 4	...(4)
$\rho \vdash_p x \Downarrow v$	Antecedent 5	...(5)
$\mu \vdash_p x \Downarrow \hat{v}$	Antecedent 6	...(6)
Case a: public τ		
Inverting (4) using rule T-VAR		
$\Gamma(x) = \tau, p'$		...(7)
$p \subseteq p'$		...(8)
$\tau = \gamma_p[n]$		...(9)
From (5) using A-VAR:		
$v = \rho(x) _p$		...(10)
From (6) using R-VAR:		
$\hat{v} = \mu(x) _p$		...(11)
From inversion of STORE_SIM using (3):		
$\rho(x) \sim \mu(x)$		...(12)
From (1), (7) and (9) using rule NON-EMP:		
$\vdash \rho(x) : \gamma_p[n], p'$		...(13)
From (2), (7) and (9) using rule NON-EMP-REF:		
$\mu(x) \models \gamma_p[n], p'$		...(14)
From (14) using REF-ARR:		
$\vdash \mu(x) : \gamma_p[n], p'$		...(15)
From V-REF2, let $\mu(x) = ([c_1, \dots, c_n], p')$		
$\text{Let } \rho(x) = (\nu_1, \dots, \nu_m)$		...(17)
From (12), (13), (15), (16) and (17) using SIM_ARR:		
$\forall i \in [n], \text{select}(\rho(x), i) = (c_i, p')$		...(18)
From (18) using VAL_EQ:		
$\forall i \in [n] \forall j \in p', \nu_j[i] = c_i$		...(19)
$\forall j \notin p', \nu_j = \perp$		...(20)
From (11) and (16), by definition:		
$\hat{v} = [c_1, \dots, c_n], p$		...(21)
From (10), by definition:		
$\pi_i(v) = \pi_i(\rho(x))$ if $i \in p$ otherwise $\pi_i(v) = \perp$		...(22)
From (8), (19), (20), (22) using VAL_EQ:		
$\forall i \in [n], \text{select}(v, i) = (c_i, p)$		...(23)
From (1), (4) and (5) using Lemma 8: $\vdash v : \gamma_p[n], p$		
$\vdash v : \gamma_p[n], p$		...(24)
From (2), (4) and (6) using Lemma 10: $\vdash \hat{v} : \gamma_p[n], p$		
$\vdash \hat{v} : \gamma_p[n], p$		...(25)
Consequent follows from (23), (24) and (25) using SIM_ARR		

Inverting (4) using rule T-VAR

$$\Gamma(x) = \tau, p \quad \dots(26)$$

$$\tau = \gamma_s[n] \quad \dots(27)$$

From (5) using A-VAR:

$$v = \rho(x)|_p \quad \dots(28)$$

From (6) using R-VAR:

$$\hat{v} = \mu(x)|_p \quad \dots(29)$$

From inversion of STORE_SIM using (3):

$$\rho(x) \sim \mu(x) \quad \dots(30)$$

From (1), (26) and (27) using rule NON-EMP:

$$\vdash \rho(x) : \gamma_s[n], p \quad \dots(31)$$

From (2), (26) and (27) using rule NON-EMP-REF:

$$\mu(x) \models \gamma_s[n], p \quad \dots(32)$$

From (32) using REF-ARR:

$$\vdash \mu(x) : \gamma_p[n], p \quad \dots(33)$$

From (28) and (31) by definition:

$$v = \rho(x) \quad \dots(34)$$

From (29) and (33) by definition:

$$\hat{v} = \mu(x) \quad \dots(35)$$

Consequent follows from (30), (34) and (35).

Case III: x is an oram.

$\rho \models \Gamma$	Antecedent 1	...(1)
$\mu \models \Gamma$	Antecedent 2	...(2)
$\rho \sim \mu$	Antecedent 3	...(3)
$\Gamma \vdash x : \tau, p$	Antecedent 4	...(4)
$\rho \vdash_p x \Downarrow v$	Antecedent 5	...(5)
$\mu \vdash_p x \Downarrow \hat{v}$	Antecedent 6	...(6)
Inverting (4) using rule T-VAR		
$\Gamma(x) = \tau, p$		...(7)
$\tau = \text{oram}[n]$		...(8)
From (5) using A-VAR:		
$v = \rho(x) _p$		...(9)
From (6) using R-VAR:		
$\hat{v} = \mu(x) _p$		...(10)
From inversion of STORE_SIM using (3):		
$\rho(x) \sim \mu(x)$		...(11)
From (1), (7) and (8) using rule NON-EMP:		
$\vdash \rho(x) : \text{oram}[n], p$		...(12)
From (2), (7) and (8) using rule NON-EMP-REF:		
$\mu(x) \models \text{oram}[n], p$		...(13)
From (14) using REF-ARR:		
$\vdash \mu(x) : \text{uint}_p[n], p$		...(14)
From (9) and (12) by definition:		
$v = \rho(x)$		...(15)
From (10) and (14) by definition:		
$\hat{v} = \mu(x)$		...(16)
Consequent follows from (11), (15) and (16).		

Induction Cases:

T-BINOP:

$\rho \models \Gamma$	Antecedent 1	...(1)
$\mu \models \Gamma$	Antecedent 2	...(2)
$\rho \sim \mu$	Antecedent 3	...(3)
$\Gamma \vdash e_1 \oplus e_2 : \mathbf{uint}_{\ell}, p$	Antecedent 4	...(4)
$\rho \vdash_p e_1 \oplus e_2 \Downarrow v$	Antecedent 5	...(5)
$\mu \vdash_p e_1 \oplus e_2 \Downarrow \hat{v}$	Antecedent 6	...(6)
Inverting (4) with T-BINOP:		
$\Gamma \vdash e_1 : \mathbf{uint}_{\ell_1}, p$		...(7)
$\Gamma \vdash e_2 : \mathbf{uint}_{\ell_2}, p$		...(8)
$\mathcal{J}(\ell_1, \ell_2) = \ell$		...(9)
Inverting (5) with A-BINOP:		
$\rho \vdash_p e_1 \Downarrow v_1$		...(10)
$\rho \vdash_p e_2 \Downarrow v_2$		...(11)
Inverting (6) with R-BINOP:		
$\mu \vdash_p e_1 \Downarrow \hat{v}_1$		...(12)
$\mu \vdash_p e_2 \Downarrow \hat{v}_2$		...(13)
Using (1), (2), (3), (7), (10), (12) from I.H.		
$v_1 \sim \hat{v}_1$		...(14)
Using (1), (2), (3), (8), (11), (13) from I.H.		
$v_2 \sim \hat{v}_2$		...(15)
From (1), (7), (10) using Lemma 8:		
$\vdash v_1 : \mathbf{uint}_{\ell_1}, p$		...(16)
From (1), (8), (11) using Lemma 8:		
$\vdash v_2 : \mathbf{uint}_{\ell_2}, p$		...(17)
From (16) using Lemma 2: $v_1 = \mathbf{sh}_{\ell_1} p c_1$		
		...(18)
From (17) using Lemma 2: $v_2 = \mathbf{sh}_{\ell_2} p c_2$		
		...(19)
From (14) and (18) using SIM_NO_ARR: $\hat{v}_1 = (c_1, p)$		
		...(20)
From (15) and (19) using SIM_NO_ARR: $\hat{v}_2 = (c_2, p)$		
		...(21)
From (5), (10) and (11) using rule A-BINOP:		
$v = \oplus_{\ell_1 \ell_2} (v_1, v_2)$		...(22)
From (9), (18), (19), (22) using operator homomorphism axiom:		
$v = \mathbf{sh}_{\ell} p (c_1 \oplus c_2)$		...(23)
From (6), (12), (13), (20), (21) using rule R-BINOP:		
$\hat{v} = (c_1 \oplus c_2), p$		...(24)
From (23): $\vdash v : \mathbf{uint}_{\ell}, p$		
		...(25)
From (24): $\vdash \hat{v} : \mathbf{uint}_p, p$		
		...(26)
Consequent follows from (23), (24), (25), (26) using SIM_NO_ARR		

T-GT:

$\rho \models \Gamma$	Antecedent 1	...(1)
$\mu \models \Gamma$	Antecedent 2	...(2)
$\rho \sim \mu$	Antecedent 3	...(3)
$\Gamma \vdash e_1 > e_2 : \text{bool}_{\ell}, p$	Antecedent 4	...(4)
$\rho \vdash_p e_1 > e_2 \Downarrow v$	Antecedent 5	...(5)
$\mu \vdash_p e_1 > e_2 \Downarrow \hat{v}$	Antecedent 6	...(6)
Inverting (4) with T-GT:		
$\Gamma \vdash e_1 : \text{uint}_{\ell_1}, p$		...(7)
$\Gamma \vdash e_2 : \text{uint}_{\ell_2}, p$		...(8)
$\mathcal{J}(\ell_1, \ell_2) = \ell$		...(9)
Inverting (5) with A-GT:		
$\rho \vdash_p e_1 \Downarrow v_1$		...(10)
$\rho \vdash_p e_2 \Downarrow v_2$		...(11)
Inverting (6) with R-GT:		
$\mu \vdash_p e_1 \Downarrow \hat{v}_1$		...(12)
$\mu \vdash_p e_2 \Downarrow \hat{v}_2$		...(13)
Using (1), (2), (3), (7), (10), (12) from I.H.		
$v_1 \sim \hat{v}_1$		...(14)
Using (1), (2), (3), (8), (11), (13) from I.H.		
$v_2 \sim \hat{v}_2$		...(15)
From (1), (7), (10) using Lemma 8:		
$\vdash v_1 : \text{uint}_{\ell_1}, p$		...(16)
From (1), (8), (11) using Lemma 8:		
$\vdash v_2 : \text{uint}_{\ell_2}, p$		...(17)
From (16) using Lemma 2: $v_1 = \text{sh}_{\ell_1} p c_1$		...(18)
From (17) using Lemma 2: $v_2 = \text{sh}_{\ell_2} p c_2$		...(19)
From (14) and (18) using SIM_NO_ARR: $\hat{v}_1 = (c_1, p)$		...(20)
From (15) and (19) using SIM_NO_ARR: $\hat{v}_2 = (c_2, p)$		...(21)
From (5), (10) and (11) using rule A-GT:		
$v \Rightarrow_{\ell_1 \ell_2} (v_1, v_2)$		...(22)
From (9), (18), (19), (22) using operator homomorphism axiom:		
$v = \text{sh}_{\ell} p (c_1 > c_2)$		...(23)
From (6), (12), (13), (20), (21) using rule R-GT:		
$\hat{v} = (c_1 > c_2), p$		...(24)
From (23): $\vdash v : \text{bool}_{\ell}, p$		...(25)
From (24): $\vdash \hat{v} : \text{bool}_p, p$		...(26)
Consequent follows from (23), (24), (25), (26) using SIM_NO_ARR		

T-MUX:

$\rho \models \Gamma$	Antecedent 1	...(1)
$\mu \models \Gamma$	Antecedent 2	...(2)
$\rho \sim \mu$	Antecedent 3	...(3)
$\Gamma \vdash e_1? e_2 : e_3 : \gamma_\ell, p$	Antecedent 4	...(4)
$\rho \vdash_p e_1? e_2 : e_3 \Downarrow v$	Antecedent 5	...(5)
$\mu \vdash_p e_1? e_2 : e_3 \Downarrow \hat{v}$	Antecedent 6	...(6)
Inverting (4) with T-MUX:		
$\Gamma \vdash e_1 : \mathbf{bool}_{\ell_1}, p$		...(7)
$\Gamma \vdash e_2 : \gamma_{\ell_2}, p$		...(8)
$\Gamma \vdash e_3 : \gamma_{\ell_3}, p$		...(9)
Inverting (5) with A-MUX:		
$\rho \vdash_p e_1 \Downarrow v_1$		...(10)
$\rho \vdash_p e_2 \Downarrow v_2$		...(11)
$\rho \vdash_p e_3 \Downarrow v_3$		...(12)
Inverting (6) with R-MUX:		
$\mu \vdash_p e_1 \Downarrow \hat{v}_1$		...(13)
$\mu \vdash_p e_2 \Downarrow \hat{v}_2$		...(14)
$\mu \vdash_p e_3 \Downarrow \hat{v}_3$		...(15)
Using (1), (2), (3), (7), (10), (13) from I.H.		
$v_1 \sim \hat{v}_1$		...(16)
Using (1), (2), (3), (8), (11), (14) from I.H.		
$v_2 \sim \hat{v}_2$		...(17)
Using (1), (2), (3), (9), (12), (15) from I.H.		
$v_3 \sim \hat{v}_3$		...(18)
From (1), (7), (10) using Lemma 8: $\vdash v_1 : \mathbf{bool}_{\ell_1}, p$		...(19)
From (1), (8), (11) using Lemma 8: $\vdash v_2 : \gamma_{\ell_2}, p$		...(20)
From (1), (9), (12) using Lemma 8: $\vdash v_3 : \gamma_{\ell_3}, p$		...(21)
From (19) using Lemma 2: $v_1 = \mathbf{sh}_{\ell_1} p c_1$		...(22)
From (20) using Lemma 2: $v_2 = \mathbf{sh}_{\ell_2} p c_2$		...(23)
From (21) using Lemma 2: $v_3 = \mathbf{sh}_{\ell_3} p c_3$		...(24)
From (16) and (22) using SIM_NO_ARR: $\hat{v}_1 = (c_1, p)$		...(25)
From (17) and (23) using SIM_NO_ARR: $\hat{v}_2 = (c_2, p)$		...(26)
From (18) and (24) using SIM_NO_ARR: $\hat{v}_3 = (c_3, p)$		...(27)
From (5), (10), (11), (12) using rule A-MUX:		
$v = ?_{\ell_1 \ell_2 \ell_3} (v_1, v_2, v_3)$		...(28)
From (22), (23), (24), (28) using operator homomorphism axiom:		
$v = \mathbf{sh}_\ell p ?(c_1, c_2, c_3)$		...(29)
From (6), (13), (14), (15), (25), (26), (27) using rule R-MUX:		
$\hat{v} = ?(c_1, c_2, c_3), p$		...(30)
From (29): $\vdash v : \gamma_\ell, p$		...(31)
From (30): $\vdash \hat{v} : \gamma_p, p$		...(32)
Consequent follows from (29), (30), (31), (32) using SIM_NO_ARR		

T-ARR

$\rho \models \Gamma$	Antecedent 1 ... (1)
$\mu \models \Gamma$	Antecedent 2 ... (2)
$\rho \sim \mu$	Antecedent 3 ... (3)
$\Gamma \vdash [\bar{e}_i]_n : \gamma_\ell[n], p$	Antecedent 4 ... (4)
$\rho \vdash_p [\bar{e}_i]_n \Downarrow v$	Antecedent 5 ... (5)
$\mu \vdash_p [\bar{e}_i]_n \Downarrow \hat{v}$	Antecedent 6 ... (6)
Inverting (4) with rule T-ARR:	
$\forall i \in [n], \Gamma \vdash e_i : \gamma_\ell, p$	... (7)
Inverting (5) with rule A-ARR:	
$\forall i \in [n], \rho \vdash_p e_i \Downarrow v_i$	... (8)
$\forall j \in p, \pi_j(v) = [\pi_j(v_1), \dots, \pi_j(v_n)]$	... (9)
$\forall j \in p, \pi_j(v) = \perp$	... (10)
Inverting (6) with rule R-ARR:	
$\forall i \in [n], \mu \vdash_p e_i \Downarrow c_i, p$	... (11)
$\hat{v} = [c_1, \dots, c_n], p$	... (12)
From (1), (2), (3), (7), (8), (11) using I.H.	
$\forall i \in [n], v_i \sim (c_i, p)$	... (13)
Using (1), (4), (5) from Lemma 8:	
$\vdash v : \gamma_\ell[n], p$	... (14)
Using (2), (4), (6) from Lemma 10:	
$\vdash \hat{v} : \gamma_p[n], p$	... (15)
From definition of select:	
$\forall i \in [n], \text{select}(v, \text{sh}_p p i) = v'_i$ where $\forall j \in p, \pi_j(v'_i) = \pi_j(v_i)$ and $\perp$ otherwise.	
$\implies v'_i = v_i$	... (16)
From (13) and (16):	
$\forall i \in [n], \text{select}(v, \text{sh}_p p i) \sim (c_i, p)$	... (17)
Consequent follows from (14), (15), (17) using SIM_ARR.	

T-ARR_READ

$\rho \models \Gamma$	Antecedent 1	...(1)
$\mu \models \Gamma$	Antecedent 2	...(2)
$\rho \sim \mu$	Antecedent 3	...(3)
$\Gamma \vdash x[e] : \gamma_\ell, p$	Antecedent 4	...(4)
$\rho \vdash_p x[e] \Downarrow v$	Antecedent 5	...(5)
$\mu \vdash_p x[e] \Downarrow \hat{v}$	Antecedent 6	...(6)
Inverting (4) using T-ARR_READ:		
$\Gamma \vdash x : \gamma_\ell[n], p$		...(7)
$\Gamma \vdash e : \text{uint}_p, p$		...(8)
$\Gamma \models e < n$		...(9)
Inverting (5) using A-ARR_READ:		
$\rho \vdash_p x \Downarrow v_1$		...(10)
$\rho \vdash_p e \Downarrow v_2$		...(11)
$v = \text{select}(v_1, v_2)$		...(12)
Inverting (6) using R-ARR_READ:		
$\mu \vdash_p x \Downarrow [\bar{c}_i]_n, p$		...(13)
$\mu \vdash_p e \Downarrow j, p$		...(14)
$\hat{v} = c_j, p$		...(15)
From (1), (2), (3), (7), (10), (13) using I.H.		
$v_1 \sim [\bar{c}_i]_n, p$		...(16)
Inverting (16) using SIM_ARR:		
$\forall i \in [n], \text{select}(v_1, \text{sh}_p p i) \sim (c_i, p)$		...(17)
From (1), (8), (11) using Lemma 8		
$\vdash v_2 : \text{uint}_p, p$		...(18)
From (18) using Lemma 2		
$v_2 = \text{sh}_p p j'$ for some j'		...(19)
From (1), (2), (3), (8), (11), (14) using I.H.		
$v_2 \sim (j, p)$		...(20)
From (19) and (20) using SIM_NO_ARR:		
$j' = j$		...(21)
From (9): $j < n$		...(22)
From (12), (19), (21)		
$v = \text{select}(v_1, \text{sh}_p p j)$		...(23)
Consequent follows from (15), (17), (22), (23).		

T-ORAM

$\rho \models \Gamma$	Antecedent 1	...(1)
$\mu \models \Gamma$	Antecedent 2	...(2)
$\rho \sim \mu$	Antecedent 3	...(3)
$\Gamma \vdash \text{Oram}(e) : \text{oram}[n], p$	Antecedent 4	...(4)
$\rho \vdash_p \text{Oram}(e) \Downarrow v$	Antecedent 5	...(5)
$\mu \vdash_p \text{Oram}(e) \Downarrow \hat{v}$	Antecedent 6	...(6)
Inverting (4) with rule T-ORAM:		
$\Gamma \vdash e : \text{uint}_s[n], p$		...(7)
Inverting (5) with rule A-ORAM:		
$\rho \vdash_p e \Downarrow v'$		...(8)
$v = \text{convert}(v')$		...(9)
Inverting (6) with rule R-ORAM:		
$\mu \vdash_p e \Downarrow \hat{v}, p$		...(10)
From (1), (2), (3), (7), (8), (10) using I.H.		
$v' \sim \hat{v}$		...(11)
Using (1), (4), (5) from Lemma 8:		
$\vdash v : \text{oram}[n], p$		...(12)
Using (1), (7), (8) from Lemma 8:		
$\vdash v' : \text{uint}_s[n], p$		...(13)
Using (2), (4), (6) from Lemma 10:		
$\hat{v} \models \text{oram}[n]$		...(14)
$\vdash \hat{v} : \text{uint}_p[n], p$		...(15)
From IH using (1), (2), (3), (7), (9), (10),		
$v' \sim \hat{v}$		...(16)
From REF-ARR using (13), (15), (16),		
$\hat{v} = [c_1, \dots, c_n], p$		...(17)
$\forall i \in [n], \text{select}(v', \text{sh}_p p i) \sim (c_i, p)$		...(18)
From REF-ORAM using (12), (15), (17), (18),		
$v \sim \hat{v}$	Consequent	

□

Lemma 13. *If $\mathcal{O} \sim \hat{\mathcal{O}}$ then, $\text{len}(\mathcal{O}) = \text{len}(\hat{\mathcal{O}})$*

Proof of Lemma 13. By induction on $\text{len}(\mathcal{O})$

Base Case: $\text{len}(\mathcal{O}) = 0$

From definition of $\text{len}(\mathcal{O})$, $\mathcal{O} = \emptyset$...(1)

From EMP_OBS using (1), $\hat{\mathcal{O}} = \emptyset$...(2)

From (2), $\text{len}(\hat{\mathcal{O}}) = 0$...(3)

$\implies \text{len}(\mathcal{O}) = \text{len}(\hat{\mathcal{O}})$ Consequent ... (4)

Induction Hypothesis: The lemma holds when $\text{len}(\mathcal{O}) = k$

Induction Case: $\text{len}(\mathcal{O}) = k + 1$

From definition of $\text{len}(\mathcal{O})$, $\mathcal{O} = v \mathcal{O}'$...(1)

$\text{len}(\mathcal{O}) = 1 + \text{len}(\mathcal{O}')$

$\implies k + 1 = 1 + \text{len}(\mathcal{O}')$

$\implies \text{len}(\mathcal{O}') = k$...(2)

From NON_EMP_OBS using (1), $\hat{\mathcal{O}} = \hat{v} \hat{\mathcal{O}}'$...(3)

and $v \sim \hat{v}$...(4)

and $\mathcal{O}' \sim \hat{\mathcal{O}}'$...(5)

From IH using (2), (5), $\text{len}(\hat{\mathcal{O}}') = k$...(6)

Using (3), (6), $\text{len}(\hat{\mathcal{O}}) = k + 1$...(7)

Using (7), $\text{len}(\mathcal{O}) = \text{len}(\hat{\mathcal{O}})$ Consequent

□

Lemma 14. *If*

1. $\mathcal{O}_1 \sim \hat{\mathcal{O}}_1$

2. $\mathcal{O}_2 \sim \hat{\mathcal{O}}_2$

Then,

a) $\mathcal{O}_1 \mathcal{O}_2 \sim \hat{\mathcal{O}}_1 \hat{\mathcal{O}}_2$

Proof. Proof of Lemma 14 by induction on length of $\mathcal{O}_1$: $\text{len}(\mathcal{O}_1)$

Base case: $\text{len}(\mathcal{O}_1) = 0$

$\implies \mathcal{O}_1 = \emptyset$...(1)

From inversion of EMP_OBS using (1) and Antecedant (1),

$\hat{\mathcal{O}}_1 = \emptyset$...(2)

Using (1), $\mathcal{O}_1 \mathcal{O}_2 = \mathcal{O}_2$...(3)

Using (2), $\hat{\mathcal{O}}_1 \hat{\mathcal{O}}_2 = \hat{\mathcal{O}}_2$...(4)

Using (3), (4), Antecedant (2), $\mathcal{O}_1 \mathcal{O}_2 \sim \hat{\mathcal{O}}_1 \hat{\mathcal{O}}_2$ Consequent a

Induction Hypothesis: Let the lemma be true when $\text{len}(\mathcal{O}_1) = k$

Induction case: $\text{len}(\mathcal{O}_1) = k + 1$

$$\implies \mathcal{O}_1 = v \mathcal{O}' \quad \dots(1)$$

From inversion of NON_EMP_OBS using (1) and Antecedant (1):

$$\hat{\mathcal{O}}_1 = \hat{v} \hat{\mathcal{O}}' \quad \dots(2)$$

$$\text{and } v \sim \hat{v} \quad \dots(3)$$

$$\text{and } \mathcal{O}' \sim \hat{\mathcal{O}}' \quad \dots(4)$$

$$\text{len}(\mathcal{O}_1) = 1 + \text{len}(\mathcal{O}')$$

$$\implies k + 1 = 1 + \text{len}(\mathcal{O}') \quad \dots(5)$$

$$\implies \text{len}(\mathcal{O}') = k \quad \dots(5)$$

$$\text{From Lemma 13 using (4), (5), } \text{len}(\hat{\mathcal{O}}') = k \quad \dots(6)$$

From IH using (4), (5), (6), Antecedant (2),

$$\mathcal{O}' \mathcal{O}_2 \sim \hat{\mathcal{O}}' \hat{\mathcal{O}}_2 \quad \dots(7)$$

From NON_EMP_OBS using (3), (7),

$$v \mathcal{O}' \mathcal{O}_2 \sim \hat{v} \hat{\mathcal{O}}' \hat{\mathcal{O}}_2 \quad \dots(8)$$

Rewriting (8) using (1), (2),

$$\mathcal{O}_1 \mathcal{O}_2 \sim \hat{\mathcal{O}}_1 \hat{\mathcal{O}}_2 \quad \text{Consequent}$$

□

Lemma 15. *If $\mathcal{G} = \hat{\mathcal{F}}$ then, $\text{len}(\mathcal{G}) = \text{len}(\hat{\mathcal{F}})$*

Proof of Lemma 15. By induction on $\text{len}(\mathcal{G})$

Base Case: $\text{len}(\mathcal{G}) = 0$

$$\text{From definition of } \text{len}(\mathcal{G}), \mathcal{G} = \emptyset \quad \dots(1)$$

$$\text{From EMP_EFF using (1), } \hat{\mathcal{F}} = \emptyset \quad \dots(2)$$

$$\text{From (2), } \text{len}(\hat{\mathcal{F}}) = 0 \quad \dots(3)$$

$$\implies \text{len}(\mathcal{G}) = \text{len}(\hat{\mathcal{F}}) \quad \text{Consequent} \quad \dots(4)$$

Induction Hypothesis: The lemma holds when $\text{len}(\mathcal{G}) = k$

Induction Case: $\text{len}(\mathcal{G}) = k + 1$

$$\text{From definition of } \text{len}(\mathcal{G}), \mathcal{G} = (d, p) \mathcal{G}' \quad \dots(1)$$

$$\text{len}(\mathcal{G}) = 1 + \text{len}(\mathcal{G}')$$

$$\implies k + 1 = 1 + \text{len}(\mathcal{G}')$$

$$\implies \text{len}(\mathcal{G}') = k \quad \dots(2)$$

$$\text{From NON_EMP_EFF using (1), } \hat{\mathcal{F}} = \hat{v} \hat{\mathcal{F}}' \quad \dots(3)$$

$$\text{and } (d, p) = \hat{v} \quad \dots(4)$$

$$\text{and } \mathcal{G}' = \hat{\mathcal{F}}' \quad \dots(5)$$

$$\text{From IH using (2), (5), } \text{len}(\hat{\mathcal{F}}') = k \quad \dots(6)$$

$$\text{Using (3), (6), } \text{len}(\hat{\mathcal{F}}) = k + 1 \quad \dots(7)$$

$$\text{Using (7), } \text{len}(\mathcal{G}) = \text{len}(\hat{\mathcal{F}}) \quad \text{Consequent}$$

□

Lemma 16. *If*

1. $\mathcal{G}_1 = \hat{\mathcal{F}}_1$

2. $\mathcal{G}_2 = \hat{\mathcal{F}}_2$

Then,

- a) $\mathcal{G}_1 \mathcal{G}_2 = \hat{\mathcal{F}}_1 \hat{\mathcal{F}}_2$

Proof. Proof of Lemma 16 by induction on length of $\mathcal{G}_1$: $\text{len}(\mathcal{G}_1)$

Base case: $\text{len}(\mathcal{G}_1) = 0$

$$\implies \mathcal{G}_1 = \emptyset \quad \dots(1)$$

From inversion of EMP_EFF using (1) and Antecedant (1),

$$\hat{\mathcal{F}}_1 = \emptyset \quad \dots(2)$$

$$\text{Using (1), } \mathcal{G}_1 \mathcal{G}_2 = \mathcal{G}_2 \quad \dots(3)$$

$$\text{Using (2), } \hat{\mathcal{F}}_1 \hat{\mathcal{F}}_2 = \hat{\mathcal{F}}_2 \quad \dots(4)$$

$$\text{Using (3), (4), Antecedant (2), } \mathcal{G}_1 \mathcal{G}_2 \sim \hat{\mathcal{F}}_1 \hat{\mathcal{F}}_2 \quad \text{Consequent a}$$

Induction Hypothesis: Let the lemma be true when $\text{len}(\mathcal{G}_1) = k$

Induction case: $\text{len}(\mathcal{G}_1) = k + 1$

$$\implies \mathcal{G}_1 = (d, p) \mathcal{G}' \quad \dots(1)$$

From inversion of NON_EMP_EFF using (1) and Antecedant (1):

$$\hat{\mathcal{F}}_1 = \hat{v} \hat{\mathcal{F}}' \quad \dots(2)$$

$$\text{and } (d, p) = \hat{v} \quad \dots(3)$$

$$\text{and } \mathcal{G}' = \hat{\mathcal{F}}' \quad \dots(4)$$

$$\text{len}(\mathcal{G}_1) = 1 + \text{len}(\mathcal{G}')$$

$$\implies k + 1 = 1 + \text{len}(\mathcal{G}') \quad \dots(5)$$

$$\implies \text{len}(\mathcal{G}') = k \quad \dots(6)$$

$$\text{From Lemma 15 using (4), (5), } \text{len}(\hat{\mathcal{F}}') = k \quad \dots(6)$$

From IH using (4), (5), (6), Antecedant (2),

$$\mathcal{G}' \mathcal{G}_2 = \hat{\mathcal{F}}' \hat{\mathcal{F}}_2 \quad \dots(7)$$

From NON_EMP_EFF using (3), (7),

$$(d, p) \mathcal{G}' \mathcal{G}_2 = \hat{v} \hat{\mathcal{F}}' \hat{\mathcal{F}}_2 \quad \dots(8)$$

Rewriting (8) using (1), (2),

$$\mathcal{G}_1 \mathcal{G}_2 = \hat{\mathcal{F}}_1 \hat{\mathcal{F}}_2 \quad \text{Consequent}$$

□

Lemma 17. • *If*

1. $\rho \models \Gamma$
2. $\mu \models \Gamma$
3. $\rho \sim \mu$
4. $\Gamma \vdash_p s \mid \Gamma'$
5. $\rho \vdash_p s \Downarrow \rho', \mathcal{T}, \mathcal{O}, \mathcal{G}$
6. $\mu \vdash_p s \Downarrow \mu', \hat{\mathcal{O}}, \hat{\mathcal{F}}$
7. s is not a loop statement.

then

- a) $\rho' \sim \mu'$
- b) $\mathcal{O} \sim \hat{\mathcal{O}}$
- c) $\mathcal{G} = \hat{\mathcal{F}}$

• *If*

1. $\rho \models \Gamma$
2. $\mu \models \Gamma$
3. $\rho \sim \mu$
4. $\Gamma \vdash S \mid \Gamma'$
5. $\rho \vdash S \Downarrow \rho', \mathcal{T}, \mathcal{O}, \mathcal{G}$
6. $\mu \vdash S \Downarrow \mu', \hat{\mathcal{O}}, \hat{\mathcal{F}}$

then

- a) $\rho' \sim \mu'$
- b) $\mathcal{O} \sim \hat{\mathcal{O}}$
- c) $\mathcal{G} = \hat{\mathcal{F}}$

• *If*

1. $\rho \models \Gamma$
2. $\mu \models \Gamma$
3. $\rho \sim \mu$
4. $\Gamma \vdash_p \text{for } x \text{ in } [n_1, n_2] \text{ do } S \mid \Gamma$
5. $\rho \vdash_p \text{for } x \text{ in } [n_1, n_2] \text{ do } S \Downarrow \rho', \mathcal{T}, \mathcal{O}, \mathcal{G}$
6. $\mu \vdash_p \text{for } x \text{ in } [n_1, n_2] \text{ do } S \Downarrow \mu', \hat{\mathcal{O}}, \hat{\mathcal{F}}$

then

- a) $\rho' \sim \mu'$
- b) $\mathcal{O} \sim \hat{\mathcal{O}}$
- c) $\mathcal{G} = \hat{\mathcal{F}}$

Proof of Lemma 17. We prove by mutual induction on the size of typing proof tree and $n_2 - n_1$.

Base cases:

T-ORAM_READ

$\rho \models \Gamma$	Antecedant 1	...(1)
$\mu \models \Gamma$	Antecedant 2	...(2)
$\rho \sim \mu$	Antecedant 3	...(3)
$\Gamma \vdash_p y = \text{OramRead}(x, e) \mid \Gamma'$	Antecedant 4	...(4)
$\rho \vdash_p y = \text{OramRead}(x, e) \Downarrow \rho', \mathcal{T}, \mathcal{O}, \mathcal{G}$	Antecedant 5	...(5)
$\mu \vdash_p y = \text{OramRead}(x, e) \Downarrow \mu', \hat{\mathcal{O}}, \hat{\mathcal{F}}$	Antecedant 6	...(6)
From inversion of STORE_SIM using (3):		
$\text{dom}(\rho) = \text{dom}(\mu)$		...(7)
$\forall x' \in \text{dom}(\rho), \rho(x') \sim \mu(x')$		...(8)
From inversion of T-ORAM-READ using (4),		
$\Gamma \vdash_p x : \text{oram}[n], p$		...(9)
$\Gamma \vdash_p e : \text{uint}_\ell, p$		...(10)
$y \notin \Gamma$		...(11)
From A-ORAM_READ using (5),		
$\rho \vdash_p x \Downarrow v_1$		...(12)
$\rho \vdash_p e \Downarrow v_2$		...(13)
Let $v'_1, v_3 = \mathcal{OR}(v_1, v_2)$		...(14)
$\rho \vdash_p y = \text{OramRead}(x, e) \Downarrow \rho[y \mapsto v_3][x \mapsto v'_1], _, \emptyset, \emptyset$		...(15)
From (15),		
$\mathcal{O} = \emptyset \quad \mathcal{G} = \emptyset$		...(16)
$\rho' = \rho[y \mapsto v_3][x \mapsto v'_1]$		...(17)
From Lemma 8 using (1), (9), (12), $\vdash v_1 : \text{oram}[n], p$		...(18)
From Lemma 8 using (1), (10), (13), $\vdash v_2 : \text{uint}_{\ell_1}, p$		...(19)
From R-ORAM_READ using (6),		
$\mu \vdash_p x \Downarrow [\bar{c}_i]_n, p$		...(20)
$\mu \vdash_p e \Downarrow c, p$		...(21)
Let $\hat{v}_1 = [\bar{c}_i]_n, p \quad \hat{v}_2 = c$		...(22)
$\hat{v}' = (0 \leq \hat{v}_2 < n) ? \hat{v}_1[\hat{v}_2] : 0$		...(23)
$\mu \vdash_p y = \text{OramRead}(x, e) \Downarrow \mu[y \mapsto \hat{v}'], \emptyset, \emptyset$		...(24)
From (24),		
$\hat{\mathcal{O}} = \emptyset \quad \hat{\mathcal{F}} = \emptyset$		...(25)
$\mu' = \mu[y \mapsto \hat{v}']$		...(26)
From Lemma 12 using (1), (2), (3), (9), (12), (20), (22), $v_1 \sim \hat{v}_1$		...(27)
From Lemma 12 using (1), (2), (3), (10), (13), (21), (22), $v_2 \sim \hat{v}_2$		...(28)
From Axiom (4) using (14), (18), (19), (23), (27), (28):		
$v'_1 \sim \hat{v}_1 \quad v_3 \sim \hat{v}'$		...(29)
$\implies \rho'(x) \sim \mu'(x) \quad \rho'(y) \sim \mu'(y)$		...(30)

From (17), $\text{dom}(\rho') = \text{dom}(\rho) \cup \{y\}$... (31)

From (26), $\text{dom}(\mu') = \text{dom}(\mu) \cup \{y\}$... (32)

From (7), (8), (31), (32),
 $\text{dom}(\rho') = \text{dom}(\mu')$... (33)

From (8), (17), (26)

$\forall x' (\neq x, y) \in \text{dom}(\rho'), \rho'(x') = \mu'(x')$... (34)

From (30), (33), (34), $\forall x' \in \text{dom}(\rho'), \rho'(x') = \mu'(x')$... (35)

From STORE_SIM using (33), (35), $\rho' \sim \mu'$ Consequent a

From EMP_OBS using (16), (25), $\mathcal{O} \sim \hat{\mathcal{O}}$ Consequent b

From (16), (25), $\mathcal{G} = \hat{\mathcal{F}}$ Consequent c

T-DEF

$\rho \models \Gamma$	Antecedant 1	...(1)
$\mu \models \Gamma$	Antecedant 2	...(2)
$\rho \sim \mu$	Antecedant 3	...(3)
$\Gamma \vdash_p \tau x = e \mid \Gamma'$	Antecedant 4	...(4)
$\rho \vdash_p \tau x = e \Downarrow \rho', \mathcal{T}, \mathcal{O}, \mathcal{G}$	Antecedant 5	...(5)
$\mu \vdash_p \tau x = e \Downarrow \mu', \hat{\mathcal{O}}, \hat{\mathcal{F}}$	Antecedant 6	...(6)
From inversion of STORE_SIM using (3):		
$\text{dom}(\rho) = \text{dom}(\mu)$		...(7)
$\forall x' \in \text{dom}(\rho), \rho(x') \sim \mu(x')$		...(8)
From A-DEF using (5),		
$\rho \vdash_p \tau x = e \Downarrow \rho[x \mapsto v], \mathcal{T}, \emptyset, \emptyset$		...(9)
From (9),		
$\mathcal{O} = \emptyset \quad \mathcal{G} = \emptyset$		...(10)
$\rho' = \rho[x \mapsto v]$		...(11)
From inversion of A-DEF using (9),		
$\rho \vdash_p e \Downarrow v$		...(12)
From R-DEF using (5),		
$\mu \vdash_p \tau x = e \Downarrow \mu[x \mapsto \hat{v}], \emptyset, \emptyset$		...(13)
From (13),		
$\hat{\mathcal{O}} = \emptyset \quad \hat{\mathcal{F}} = \emptyset$		...(14)
$\mu' = \mu[x \mapsto \hat{v}]$		...(15)
From inversion of R-DEF using (12),		
$\mu \vdash_p e \Downarrow \hat{v}$		...(16)
From Lemma 12 using (1), (2), (3), (4), (12), (16):		
$v \sim \hat{v}$		...(17)
$\implies \rho'(x) \sim \mu'(x)$		...(18)
From (11), $\text{dom}(\rho') = \text{dom}(\rho) \cup x$		...(19)
From (15), $\text{dom}(\mu') = \text{dom}(\mu) \cup x$		...(20)
From (7), (19), (20),		
$\text{dom}(\rho') = \text{dom}(\mu')$		...(21)
From (8), (19), (20),		
$\forall x' (\neq x) \in \text{dom}(\rho'), \rho'(x') = \mu'(x')$		...(22)
From (18), (22), $\forall x' \in \text{dom}(\rho'), \rho'(x') = \mu'(x')$		...(23)
From STORE_SIM using (21), (23), $\rho' \sim \mu'$	Consequent a	
From EMP_OBS using (10), (14), $\mathcal{O} \sim \hat{\mathcal{O}}$	Consequent b	
Using (10), (14), $\mathcal{G} = \hat{\mathcal{F}}$	Consequent c	

T-ASSIGN

$\rho \models \Gamma$	Antecedant 1	...(1)
$\mu \models \Gamma$	Antecedant 2	...(2)
$\rho \sim \mu$	Antecedant 3	...(3)
$\Gamma \vdash_p x = e \mid \Gamma'$	Antecedant 4	...(4)
$\rho \vdash_p x = e \Downarrow \rho', \mathcal{T}, \mathcal{O}, \mathcal{G}$	Antecedant 5	...(5)
$\mu \vdash_p x = e \Downarrow \mu', \hat{\mathcal{O}}, \hat{\mathcal{F}}$	Antecedant 6	...(6)

From inversion of STORE_SIM using (3):

$$\text{dom}(\rho) = \text{dom}(\mu) \quad \dots(7)$$

$$\forall x' \in \text{dom}(\rho), \rho(x') \sim \mu(x') \quad \dots(8)$$

From A-ASSIGN using (5),

$$\rho \vdash_p \tau x = e \Downarrow \rho[x \mapsto v], \mathcal{T}, \emptyset, \emptyset \quad \dots(9)$$

From (9),

$$\mathcal{O} = \emptyset \quad \mathcal{G} = \emptyset \quad \dots(10)$$

$$\rho' = \rho[x \mapsto v] \quad \dots(11)$$

From inversion of A-ASSIGN using (9),

$$\rho \vdash_p e \Downarrow v \quad \dots(12)$$

From R-ASSIGN using (5),

$$\mu \vdash_p \tau x = e \Downarrow \mu[x \mapsto \hat{v}], \emptyset, \emptyset \quad \dots(13)$$

From (13),

$$\hat{\mathcal{O}} = \emptyset \quad \hat{\mathcal{F}} = \emptyset \quad \dots(14)$$

$$\mu' = \mu[x \mapsto \hat{v}] \quad \dots(15)$$

From inversion of R-ASSIGN using (12),

$$\mu \vdash_p e \Downarrow \hat{v} \quad \dots(16)$$

From Lemma 12 using (1), (2), (3), (4), (12), (16):

$$v \sim \hat{v} \quad \dots(17)$$

$$\implies \rho'(x) \sim \mu'(x) \quad \dots(18)$$

$$\text{From (11), } \text{dom}(\rho') = \text{dom}(\rho) \cup x \quad \dots(19)$$

$$\text{From (15), } \text{dom}(\mu') = \text{dom}(\mu) \cup x \quad \dots(20)$$

From (7), (19), (20),

$$\text{dom}(\rho') = \text{dom}(\mu') \quad \dots(21)$$

From (8), (19), (20),

$$\forall x' (\neq x) \in \text{dom}(\rho'), \rho'(x') = \mu'(x') \quad \dots(22)$$

$$\text{From (18), (22), } \forall x' \in \text{dom}(\rho'), \rho'(x') = \mu'(x') \quad \dots(23)$$

From STORE_SIM using (21), (23), $\rho' \sim \mu'$ Consequent a

From EMP_OBS using (10), (14), $\mathcal{O} \sim \hat{\mathcal{O}}$ Consequent b

From (10), (14), $\mathcal{G} = \hat{\mathcal{F}}$ Consequent c

T-ARR_WRITE

$\rho \models \Gamma$	Antecedant 1	...(1)
$\mu \models \Gamma$	Antecedant 2	...(2)
$\rho \sim \mu$	Antecedant 3	...(3)
$\Gamma \vdash_p x[e_1] = e_2 \mid \Gamma'$	Antecedant 4	...(4)
$\rho \vdash_p x[e_1] = e_2 \Downarrow \rho', \mathcal{T}, \mathcal{O}, \mathcal{G}$	Antecedant 5	...(5)
$\mu \vdash_p x[e_1] = e_2 \Downarrow \mu', \hat{\mathcal{O}}, \hat{\mathcal{F}}$	Antecedant 6	...(6)
From inversion of T-ARR_WRITE using (4),		
$\Gamma(x) = \gamma_\ell[n], p$		...(7)
$\Gamma \vdash e_1 : \text{uint}_p, p$		...(8)
$\Gamma \vdash e_2 : \gamma_\ell, p$		...(9)
From inversion of A-ARR_WRITE using (5),		
$\rho(x) = v$		...(10)
$\rho \vdash_p e_1 \Downarrow v_1$		...(11)
$\rho \vdash_p e_2 \Downarrow v_2$		...(12)
From inversion of R-ARR_WRITE using (6),		
$\mu(x) = [\bar{c}_i]_n, p$		...(13)
$\mu \vdash_p e_1 \downarrow c_1, p$		...(14)
$\mu \vdash_p e_2 \downarrow c_2, p$		...(15)
From Lemma 12 using (1), (2), (3), (7), (10), (13),		
$v \sim [\bar{c}_i]_n, p$		...(16)
From Lemma 12 using (1), (2), (3), (8), (11), (14),		
$v_1 \sim c_1, p$		...(17)
From Lemma 12 using (1), (2), (3), (9), (12), (15),		
$v_2 \sim c_2, p$		...(18)
Based on 1, there are following two cases:		
Case 1: $1 = p$		
From inversion of SIM_ARR using (16),		
$\forall i \in [n], \bar{c}_i, p = \text{select}(v, \text{sh}_p p i)$		...(19)
Let $v = (\nu_1, \dots, \nu_m)$		...(20)
and $v' = \text{update}(v, v_1, v_2) = (\nu'_1, \dots, \nu'_m)$		...(21)
$\implies \forall j \notin [p], \nu'_j = \perp$		...(22)
and $\forall j \in [p], \forall i (\neq c_1) \in [n], \nu'_j[i] = \nu_j[i]$		...(23)
and $\forall j \in [p], \nu'_j[c_1] = c_2$		...(24)
From inversion of R-ARR_WRITE using (19), (22), (23),		
$\forall i (\neq c_1) \in [n], u'[i] = \text{select}(v', \text{sh}_p p i)$		...(25)
From inversion of R-ARR_WRITE using (19), (22), (24),		
$u'[c_1] = \text{select}(v', \text{sh}_p p c_1)$		...(26)
From (25), (26),		
$\forall i \in [n], \text{select}(v', \text{sh}_p p i) = u'[i]$		...(27)
From Lemma 8 using (1), (7), (10), $\vdash v : \gamma_p[n], p$		
From Lemma 8 using (1), (9), (12), $\vdash v_2 : \gamma_p, p$		
From (21), (22), (23), (24), $\vdash v' : \gamma_p[n], p$		
From (27), $\vdash u', p : \gamma_p[n], p$		

Let $\hat{v}' = u', p$... (32)

From (31), $\vdash \hat{v}' : \gamma_p, p$... (33)

From SIM_ARR rule, using (27), (30), (33)

$v' \sim \hat{v}'$... (34)

Case 2: $\ell = s$

$\forall i \in [n], \bar{c}_i, p = \mathcal{D}(\text{select}(v, \text{sh}_p p i), p, s)$... (35)

Let $v = (\nu_1, \dots, \nu_m)$... (36)

and $v' = \text{update}(v, v_1, v_2) = (\nu'_1, \dots, \nu'_m)$... (37)

$\implies \forall j \notin [p], \nu'_j = \perp$... (38)

and $\forall j \in [p], \forall i (\neq c_1) \in [n], \nu'_j[i] = \nu_j[i]$... (39)

and $\forall j \in [p], \nu'_j[c_1] = c_2$... (40)

From inversion of R-ARR_WRITE using (35), (38), (39),

$\forall i (\neq c_1) \in [n], u'[i] = \mathcal{D}(\text{select}(v', \text{sh}_p p i), p, s)$... (41)

From inversion of R-ARR_WRITE using (35), (38), (40),

$u'[c_1] = \mathcal{D}(\text{select}(v', \text{sh}_p p c_1), p, s)$... (42)

From (41), (42),

$\forall i \in [n], u'[i] = \mathcal{D}(\text{select}(v', \text{sh}_p p i), p, s)$... (43)

From Lemma 8 using (1), (7), (10), $\vdash v : \gamma_p[n], p$... (44)

From Lemma 8 using (1), (9), (12), $\vdash v_2 : \gamma_p, p$... (45)

From (37), (38), (39), (40), $\vdash v' : \gamma_p[n], p$... (46)

From (43), $\vdash u', p : \gamma_p[n], p$... (47)

Let $\hat{v}' = u', p$... (48)

From (47), $\vdash \hat{v}' : \gamma_p, p$... (49)

From SIM_ARR rule, using (43), (46), (49)

$v' \sim \hat{v}'$... (50)

From inversion of STORE_SIM using (3):

$\text{dom}(\rho) = \text{dom}(\mu)$... (51)

$\forall x' \in \text{dom}(\rho), \rho(x') \sim \mu(x')$... (52)

From A-ARR_WRITE using (5),

$\rho \vdash_p x[e_1] = e_2 \Downarrow \rho[x \mapsto v'], _, \emptyset, \emptyset$... (53)

From (53),

$\mathcal{O} = \emptyset \quad \mathcal{G} = \emptyset$... (54)

$\rho' = \rho[x \mapsto v']$... (55)

From R-ARR_WRITE using (6),

$\mu \vdash_p x[e_1] = e_2 \Downarrow \mu[x \mapsto \hat{v}'], \emptyset, \emptyset$... (56)

From (56),

$\hat{\mathcal{O}} = \emptyset \quad \hat{\mathcal{F}} = \emptyset$... (57)

$\mu' = \mu[x \mapsto \hat{v}']$... (58)

From (55), $\text{dom}(\rho') = \text{dom}(\rho) \cup x$... (59)

From (58), $\text{dom}(\mu') = \text{dom}(\mu) \cup x$... (60)

From (51), (59), (60),

$\text{dom}(\rho') = \text{dom}(\mu')$... (61)

From (52), (59), (61),
 $\forall x' (\neq x) \in \text{dom}(\rho'), \rho'(x') = \mu'(x')$... (62)

From (34), (50), (55), (58), (59), $\forall x' \in \text{dom}(\rho'), \rho'(x') = \mu'(x')$... (63)

From STORE_SIM using (61), (63), $\rho' \sim \mu'$ Consequent a

From EMP_OBS using (54), (57), $\mathcal{O} \sim \hat{\mathcal{O}}$ Consequent b

From (54), (57), $\mathcal{G} = \hat{\mathcal{F}}$ Consequent c

T-ORAM_WRITE

$\rho \models \Gamma$ Antecedant 1 ... (1)

$\mu \models \Gamma$ Antecedant 2 ... (2)

$\rho \sim \mu$ Antecedant 3 ... (3)

$\Gamma \vdash_p \text{OramWrite}(x, e_1, e_2) \mid \Gamma$ Antecedant 4 ... (4)

$\rho \vdash_p \text{OramWrite}(x, e_1, e_2) \Downarrow \rho', \mathcal{T}, \mathcal{O}, \mathcal{G}$ Antecedant 5 ... (5)

$\mu \vdash_p \text{OramWrite}(x, e_1, e_2) \Downarrow \mu', \hat{\mathcal{O}}, \hat{\mathcal{F}}$ Antecedant 6 ... (6)

From inversion of STORE_SIM using (3):

$\text{dom}(\rho) = \text{dom}(\mu)$... (7)

$\forall x' \in \text{dom}(\rho), \rho(x') \sim \mu(x')$... (8)

From inversion of T-ORAM-WRITE using (4),

$\Gamma \vdash_p x : \text{oram}[n], p$... (9)

$\Gamma \vdash_p e_1 : \text{uint}_{\ell_1}, p$... (10)

$\Gamma \vdash_p e_2 : \text{uint}_{\ell_2}, p$... (11)

From A-ORAM_WRITE using (5),

$\rho \vdash_p x \Downarrow v_1$... (12)

$\rho \vdash_p e_1 \Downarrow v_2$... (13)

$\rho \vdash_p e_2 \Downarrow v_3$... (14)

$v = \mathcal{OW}(v_1, v_2, v_3)$... (15)

$\rho \vdash_p \text{OramWrite}(x, e_1, e_2) \Downarrow \rho[x \mapsto v], _, \emptyset, \emptyset$... (16)

From (16),

$\mathcal{O} = \emptyset \quad \mathcal{G} = \emptyset$... (17)

$\rho' = \rho[x \mapsto v]$... (18)

From Lemma 8 using (1), (9), (12), $\vdash v_1 : \text{oram}_\gamma[n], p$... (19)

From Lemma 8 using (1), (10), (13), $\vdash v_2 : \text{uint}_{\ell_1}, p$... (20)

From Lemma 8 using (1), (11), (14), $\vdash v_3 : \text{uint}_{\ell_2}, p$... (21)

From R-ORAM_WRITE using (5),

$$\mu \vdash_p x \downarrow [\bar{c}_i]_{n,p} \quad \dots(22)$$

$$\mu \vdash_p e_1 \downarrow c_2, p \quad \dots(23)$$

$$\mu \vdash_p e_2 \downarrow c_3, p \quad \dots(24)$$

Let u' be s.t.

$$\forall i \in [n] \text{ s.t. } i \neq c_1, u'[i] = \bar{c}_i \quad \dots(25)$$

$$u'[c_1] = c_2 \text{ if } 0 \leq c_1 < n \quad \dots(26)$$

$$\mu \vdash_p \text{OramWrite}(x, e_1, e_2) \downarrow \mu[x \mapsto (u', p)], \emptyset, \emptyset \quad \dots(27)$$

From (27),

$$\hat{\mathcal{O}} = \emptyset \quad \hat{\mathcal{F}} = \emptyset \quad \dots(28)$$

$$\mu' = \mu[x \mapsto (u', p)] \quad \dots(29)$$

$$\text{From Lemma 12 using (1), (2), (3), (9), (12), (22), } v_1 \sim [\bar{c}_i]_{n,p} \quad \dots(30)$$

$$\text{From Lemma 12 using (1), (2), (3), (10), (13), (23), } v_2 \sim c_2, p \quad \dots(31)$$

$$\text{From Lemma 12 using (1), (2), (3), (11), (14), (24), } v_3 \sim c_3, p \quad \dots(32)$$

From Axiom (5) using (15), (19), (20), (21), (25), (26), (27), (30), (31), (32):

$$v \sim (u', p) \quad \dots(33)$$

$$\implies \rho'(x) \sim \mu'(x) \quad \dots(34)$$

$$\text{From (18), } \text{dom}(\rho') = \text{dom}(\rho) \cup x \quad \dots(35)$$

$$\text{From (29), } \text{dom}(\mu') = \text{dom}(\mu) \cup x \quad \dots(36)$$

From (7), (35), (36),

$$\text{dom}(\rho') = \text{dom}(\mu') \quad \dots(37)$$

From (8), (35), (36),

$$\forall x' (\neq x) \in \text{dom}(\rho'), \rho'(x') = \mu'(x') \quad \dots(38)$$

$$\text{From (34), (37), (38), } \forall x' \in \text{dom}(\rho'), \rho'(x') = \mu'(x') \quad \dots(39)$$

From STORE_SIM using (37), (39), $\rho' \sim \mu'$

Consequent a

From EMP_OBS using (17), (28), $\mathcal{O} \sim \hat{\mathcal{O}}$

Consequent b

From (17), (28), $\mathcal{G} = \hat{\mathcal{F}}$

Consequent c

T-INPUT

$\rho \models \Gamma$	Antecedant 1	...(1)
$\mu \models \Gamma$	Antecedant 2	...(2)
$\rho \sim \mu$	Antecedant 3	...(3)
$\Gamma \vdash_p \text{input}(x, \tau) \mid \Gamma'$	Antecedant 4	...(4)
$\rho \vdash_p \text{input}(x, \tau) \Downarrow \rho', \mathcal{T}, \mathcal{O}, \mathcal{G}$	Antecedant 5	...(5)
$\mu \vdash_p \text{input}(x, \tau) \Downarrow \mu', \hat{\mathcal{O}}, \hat{\mathcal{F}}$	Antecedant 6	...(6)

From inversion of STORE_SIM using (3):

$$\text{dom}(\rho) = \text{dom}(\mu) \quad \dots(7)$$

$$\forall x' \in \text{dom}(\rho), \rho(x') \sim \mu(x') \quad \dots(8)$$

From A-INPUT using (5),

$$\rho \vdash_p \tau \ x = e \Downarrow \rho[x \mapsto v], _, \emptyset, (d, p) \quad \dots(9)$$

From (9),

$$\mathcal{O} = \emptyset \quad \mathcal{G} = (d, p) \quad \dots(10)$$

$$\rho' = \rho[x \mapsto v] \quad \dots(11)$$

From inversion of A-INPUT using (9),

$$v = \text{userin}(\tau, p) \quad v = \text{sh}_p \ p \ d \quad \dots(12)$$

From R-INPUT using (6),

$$\mu \vdash_p \tau \ x = e \Downarrow \mu[x \mapsto \hat{v}], \emptyset, \hat{v} \quad \dots(13)$$

From (13),

$$\hat{\mathcal{O}} = \emptyset \quad \hat{\mathcal{F}} = \hat{v} \quad \dots(14)$$

$$\mu' = \mu[x \mapsto \hat{v}] \quad \dots(15)$$

From inversion of R-INPUT using (12),

$$\hat{v} = \text{userin}(\tau, p) \quad \dots(16)$$

Using (12), (16):

$$v \sim \hat{v} \quad \dots(17)$$

$$\text{From (11), } \text{dom}(\rho') = \text{dom}(\rho) \cup x \quad \dots(18)$$

$$\text{From (15), } \text{dom}(\mu') = \text{dom}(\mu) \cup x \quad \dots(19)$$

From (7), (19), (20),

$$\text{dom}(\rho') = \text{dom}(\mu') \quad \dots(20)$$

From (8), (19), (20),

$$\forall x' (\neq x) \in \text{dom}(\rho'), \rho'(x') = \mu'(x') \quad \dots(21)$$

$$\text{From (18), (22), } \forall x' \in \text{dom}(\rho'), \rho'(x') = \mu'(x') \quad \dots(22)$$

From STORE_SIM using (21), (23), $\rho' \sim \mu'$

Consequent a

From EMP_OBS using (10), (14), $\mathcal{O} \sim \hat{\mathcal{O}}$

Consequent b

From (10), (12), (14), (16), $\mathcal{G} = \hat{\mathcal{F}}$

Consequent c

T-REVEAL

$\rho \models \Gamma$	Antecedant 1	...(1)
$\mu \models \Gamma$	Antecedant 2	...(2)
$\rho \sim \mu$	Antecedant 3	...(3)
$\Gamma \vdash \gamma_p x_1 = \text{reveal}(x_2, p) \mid \Gamma'$	Antecedant 4	...(4)
$\rho \vdash \gamma_p x_1 = \text{reveal}(x_2, p) \Downarrow \rho', \mathcal{T}, \mathcal{O}, \mathcal{G}$	Antecedant 5	...(5)
$\mu \vdash \gamma_p x_1 = \text{reveal}(x_2, p) \Downarrow \mu', \hat{\mathcal{O}}, \hat{\mathcal{F}}$	Antecedant 6	...(6)
From inversion of STORE_SIM using (3):		
$\text{dom}(\rho) = \text{dom}(\mu)$		...(7)
$\forall x' \in \text{dom}(\rho), \rho(x') \sim \mu(x')$		...(8)
From T-REVEAL using (4),		
$\Gamma(x_2) = (\gamma_s, p')$		...(9)
$x_1 \notin \Gamma$		...(10)
From NON-EMP using (1), (9), $\vdash \rho(x_2) : (\gamma_s, p')$		...(11)
From NON-EMP-REF using (1), (9), $\mu(x_2) \models (\gamma_s, p')$		...(12)
From REF-NON-ARR using (12), $\vdash \mu(x_2) : (\gamma_p, p')$		...(13)
From STORE_SIM using (3), $\rho(x_2) \sim \mu(x_2)$		...(14)
From SIM_NO_ARR using (14), $\mu(x_2) = \mathcal{D}(\rho(x_2), p')$		...(15)
From correctness properties of MPC protocols using (15),		
$\rho(x_2) = \text{sh}_s p' c$		...(16)
$\mu(x_2) = \text{sh}_p p' c$		...(17)
Let $v = \mathcal{D}(\rho(x_2), p)$		...(18)
From correctness properties of MPC protocols using (11), (14), $v = \text{sh}_s p c$		...(19)
Let $\hat{v} = c, p$		...(20)
From correctness properties of MPC protocols using (19), (20), $\hat{v} = \mathcal{D}(v, p)$		...(21)
From SIM_NO_ARR using (21), $v \sim \hat{v}$		...(22)
From A-REVEAL using (5),		
$\rho \vdash \gamma_p x_1 = \text{reveal}(x_2, p) \Downarrow \rho[x_1 \mapsto v], _, (c, p), \emptyset$		...(23)
From (23),		
$\mathcal{O} = (c, p) \quad \mathcal{G} = \emptyset$		...(24)
$\rho' = \rho[x_1 \mapsto v]$		...(25)
From R-REVEAL using (6),		
$\mu \vdash \gamma_p x_1 = \text{reveal}(x_2, p) \Downarrow \mu[x_1 \mapsto \hat{v}], \hat{v}, \emptyset$		...(26)
From (26),		
$\hat{\mathcal{O}} = \hat{v} \quad \hat{\mathcal{F}} = \emptyset$		...(27)
$\mu' = \mu[x_1 \mapsto \hat{v}]$		...(28)
Using (22), $\rho'(x_1) \sim \mu'(x_1)$		...(29)
From (24), (28), $\text{dom}(\rho') = \text{dom}(\rho) \cup x$, $\text{dom}(\mu') = \text{dom}(\mu) \cup x$		...(30)
From (7), (30), $\text{dom}(\rho') = \text{dom}(\mu')$		...(31)
From (8), (29), (31),		
$\forall x' \in \text{dom}(\rho'), \rho'(x') = \mu'(x')$		...(32)
From STORE_SIM using (21), (23), $\rho' \sim \mu'$	Consequent a	
From EMP_OBS, $\emptyset \sim \emptyset$		...(33)
From NON_EMP_OBS using (22), (24), (27), (33), $(v \emptyset) \sim (\hat{v} \emptyset)$	Consequent b	
From (24), (27), $\mathcal{G} = \hat{\mathcal{F}}$	Consequent c	

T-MAKESH

$\rho \models \Gamma$	Antecedant 1	...(1)
$\mu \models \Gamma$	Antecedant 2	...(2)
$\rho \sim \mu$	Antecedant 3	...(3)
$\Gamma \vdash \gamma_s x_1 = \text{makesh}(x_2, p) \mid \Gamma'$	Antecedant 4	...(4)
$\rho \vdash \gamma_s x_1 = \text{makesh}(x_2, p) \Downarrow \rho', \mathcal{T}, \mathcal{O}, \mathcal{G}$	Antecedant 5	...(5)
$\mu \vdash \gamma_s x_1 = \text{makesh}(x_2, p) \Downarrow \mu', \hat{\mathcal{O}}, \mathcal{G}$	Antecedant 6	...(6)

From inversion of STORE_SIM using (3):

$$\text{dom}(\rho) = \text{dom}(\mu) \quad \dots(7)$$

$$\forall x' \in \text{dom}(\rho), \rho(x') \sim \mu(x') \quad \dots(8)$$

From T-MAKESH using (4),

$$\Gamma(x_2) = (\gamma_p, p') \quad \dots(9)$$

$$x_1 \notin \Gamma \quad \dots(10)$$

$$\text{From NON-EMP using (1), (9), } \vdash \rho(x_2) : (\gamma_p, p') \quad \dots(11)$$

$$\text{From NON-EMP-REF using (1), (9), } \mu(x_2) \models (\gamma_p, p') \quad \dots(12)$$

$$\text{From REF-NON-ARR using (12), } \vdash \mu(x_2) : (\gamma_p, p') \quad \dots(13)$$

$$\text{From STORE_SIM using (3), } \rho(x_2) \sim \mu(x_2) \quad \dots(14)$$

$$\text{From SIM_NO_ARR using (14), } \rho(x_2) = \mu(x_2) \quad \dots(15)$$

$$\text{Let } \rho(x_2) = \mu(x_2) = \text{sh}_p p' c \quad \dots(16)$$

$$\text{Let } \hat{v} = c, p \quad v = \mathcal{E}(\rho(x_2), p) \quad \dots(17)$$

From correctness properties of MPC protocols using (17),

$$\hat{v} = \mathcal{D}(v, p) \quad \dots(18)$$

$$\text{From SIM_NO_ARR using (21), } v \sim \hat{v} \quad \dots(19)$$

From A-MAKESH using (5),

$$\rho \vdash \gamma_s x_1 = \text{makesh}(x_2, p) \Downarrow \rho[x_1 \mapsto v], _, \emptyset, (c, p) \quad \dots(20)$$

From (9),

$$\mathcal{O} = \emptyset \quad \mathcal{G} = (c, p) \quad \dots(21)$$

$$\rho' = \rho[x_1 \mapsto v] \quad \dots(22)$$

From R-MAKESH using (6),

$$\mu \vdash \gamma_s x_1 = \text{makesh}(x_2, p) \Downarrow \mu[x_1 \mapsto \hat{v}], \emptyset, \mathcal{G} \quad \dots(23)$$

From (9),

$$\hat{\mathcal{O}} = \emptyset \quad \hat{\mathcal{F}} = \hat{v} \quad \dots(24)$$

$$\mu' = \mu[x_1 \mapsto \hat{v}] \quad \dots(25)$$

$$\text{Using (22), } \rho'(x_1) \sim \mu'(x_1) \quad \dots(26)$$

$$\text{From (24), (28), } \text{dom}(\rho') = \text{dom}(\rho) \cup x, \quad \text{dom}(\mu') = \text{dom}(\mu) \cup x \quad \dots(27)$$

$$\text{From (7), (30), } \text{dom}(\rho') = \text{dom}(\mu') \quad \dots(28)$$

From (8), (29), (31),

$$\forall x' \in \text{dom}(\rho'), \rho'(x') = \mu'(x') \quad \dots(29)$$

$$\text{From STORE_SIM using (21), (23), } \rho' \sim \mu' \quad \text{Consequent a}$$

$$\text{From EMP_OBS using (21), (24), } \mathcal{O} \sim \hat{\mathcal{O}} \quad \text{Consequent b}$$

$$\text{From (17), (21), (24), } \mathcal{G} = \hat{\mathcal{F}} \quad \text{Consequent c}$$

T-RESHARE

$\rho \models \Gamma$	Antecedant 1	...(1)
$\mu \models \Gamma$	Antecedant 2	...(2)
$\rho \sim \mu$	Antecedant 3	...(3)
$\Gamma \vdash \gamma_s x_1 = \text{reshare}(x_2, p) \mid \Gamma'$	Antecedant 4	...(4)
$\rho \vdash \gamma_s x_1 = \text{reshare}(x_2, p) \Downarrow \rho', \mathcal{T}, \mathcal{O}, \mathcal{G}$	Antecedant 5	...(5)
$\mu \vdash \gamma_s x_1 = \text{reshare}(x_2, p) \Downarrow \mu', \hat{\mathcal{O}}, \hat{\mathcal{F}}$	Antecedant 6	...(6)

From inversion of STORE_SIM using (3):

$$\text{dom}(\rho) = \text{dom}(\mu) \quad \dots(7)$$

$$\forall x' \in \text{dom}(\rho), \rho(x') \sim \mu(x') \quad \dots(8)$$

From T-RESHARE using (4),

$$\Gamma(x_2) = (\gamma_s, p') \quad \dots(9)$$

$$x_1 \notin \Gamma \quad \dots(10)$$

$$\text{From NON-EMP using (1), (9), } \vdash \rho(x_2) : (\gamma_s, p') \quad \dots(11)$$

$$\text{From NON-EMP-REF using (1), (9), } \mu(x_2) \models (\gamma_s, p') \quad \dots(12)$$

$$\text{From REF-NON-ARR using (12), } \vdash \mu(x_2) : (\gamma_p, p') \quad \dots(13)$$

$$\text{From STORE_SIM using (3), } \rho(x_2) \sim \mu(x_2) \quad \dots(14)$$

$$\text{From SIM_NO_ARR using (14), } \mu(x_2) = \mathcal{D}(\rho(x_2), p') \quad \dots(15)$$

From correctness properties of MPC protocols using (15),

$$\rho(x_2) = \text{sh}_s p' c \quad \dots(16)$$

$$\mu(x_2) = \text{sh}_p p' c \quad \dots(17)$$

$$\text{Let } v = \mathcal{R}(\rho(x_2), p) \quad \dots(18)$$

$$\text{From correctness properties of MPC protocols using (11), (14), } v = \text{sh}_s p c \quad \dots(19)$$

$$\text{Let } \hat{v} = c, p \quad \dots(20)$$

$$\text{From correctness properties of MPC protocols using (19), (20), } \hat{v} = \mathcal{D}(v, p) \quad \dots(21)$$

$$\text{From SIM_NO_ARR using (21), } v \sim \hat{v} \quad \dots(22)$$

From A-RESHARE using (5),

$$\rho \vdash \gamma_s x_1 = \text{reshare}(x_2, p) \Downarrow \rho[x_1 \mapsto v], \mathcal{T}, \emptyset, (c, p) \quad \dots(23)$$

From (23),

$$\mathcal{O} = \emptyset \quad \mathcal{G} = (c, p) \quad \dots(24)$$

$$\rho' = \rho[x_1 \mapsto v] \quad \dots(25)$$

From R-RESHARE using (6),

$$\mu \vdash \gamma_s x_1 = \text{reshare}(x_2, p) \Downarrow \mu[x_1 \mapsto \hat{v}], \emptyset, \hat{v} \quad \dots(26)$$

From (26),

$$\hat{\mathcal{O}} = \emptyset \quad \hat{\mathcal{F}} = \hat{v} \quad \dots(27)$$

$$\mu' = \mu[x_1 \mapsto \hat{v}] \quad \dots(28)$$

$$\text{Using (22), } \rho'(x_1) \sim \mu'(x_1) \quad \dots(29)$$

$$\text{From (24), (28), } \text{dom}(\rho') = \text{dom}(\rho) \cup x, \quad \text{dom}(\mu') = \text{dom}(\mu) \cup x \quad \dots(30)$$

$$\text{From (7), (30), } \text{dom}(\rho') = \text{dom}(\mu') \quad \dots(31)$$

From (8), (29), (31),

$$\forall x' \in \text{dom}(\rho'), \rho'(x') = \mu'(x') \quad \dots(32)$$

$$\text{From STORE_SIM using (21), (23), } \rho' \sim \mu' \quad \text{Consequent a}$$

$$\text{From EMP_OBS using (24), (27), } \mathcal{O} \sim \hat{\mathcal{O}} \quad \text{Consequent b}$$

$$\text{From (20), (24), (27), } \mathcal{G} = \hat{\mathcal{F}} \quad \text{Consequent c}$$

T-BROADCAST

$\rho \models \Gamma$	Antecedant 1	...(1)
$\mu \models \Gamma$	Antecedant 2	...(2)
$\rho \sim \mu$	Antecedant 3	...(3)
$\Gamma \vdash \gamma_p x_1 = \text{broadcast}(x_2, p) \mid \Gamma'$	Antecedant 4	...(4)
$\rho \vdash \gamma_p x_1 = \text{broadcast}(x_2, p) \Downarrow \rho', \mathcal{T}, \mathcal{O}, \mathcal{G}$	Antecedant 5	...(5)
$\mu \vdash \gamma_p x_1 = \text{broadcast}(x_2, p) \Downarrow \mu', \hat{\mathcal{O}}, \hat{\mathcal{F}}$	Antecedant 6	...(6)
From inversion of STORE_SIM using (3):		
$\text{dom}(\rho) = \text{dom}(\mu)$		...(7)
$\forall x' \in \text{dom}(\rho), \rho(x') \sim \mu(x')$		...(8)
From T-BROADCAST using (4),		
$\Gamma(x_2) = (\gamma_p, p')$		...(9)
$x_1 \notin \Gamma$		...(10)
From NON-EMP using (1), (9), $\vdash \rho(x_2) : (\gamma_p, p')$		...(11)
From NON-EMP-REF using (1), (9), $\mu(x_2) \models (\gamma_p, p')$		...(12)
From REF-NON-ARR using (12), $\vdash \mu(x_2) : (\gamma_p, p')$		...(13)
From STORE_SIM using (3), $\rho(x_2) \sim \mu(x_2)$		...(14)
From SIM_NO_ARR using (14), $\mu(x_2) = \rho(x_2)$		...(15)
From correctness properties of MPC protocols using (15),		
$\rho(x_2) = \text{sh}_p p' c$		...(16)
$\mu(x_2) = \text{sh}_p p' c$		...(17)
Let $v = \mathcal{P}(\rho(x_2), p)$		...(18)
From correctness properties of MPC protocols using (11), (14), $v = \text{sh}_p p c$		...(19)
Let $\hat{v} = c, p$		...(20)
From correctness properties of MPC protocols using (19), (20), $\hat{v} = v$		...(21)
From SIM_NO_ARR using (21), $v \sim \hat{v}$		...(22)
From A-BROADCAST using (5),		
$\rho \vdash \gamma_p x_1 = \text{broadcast}(x_2, p) \Downarrow \rho[x_1 \mapsto v], \mathcal{T}, (c, p), \emptyset$		...(23)
From (23), $\mathcal{O} = (c, p) \quad \mathcal{G} = \emptyset$		...(24)
$\rho' = \rho[x_1 \mapsto v]$		...(25)
From R-BROADCAST using (6),		
$\mu \vdash \gamma_p x_1 = \text{broadcast}(x_2, p) \Downarrow \mu[x_1 \mapsto \hat{v}], \hat{v}, \emptyset$		...(26)
From (26), $\hat{\mathcal{O}} = \hat{v} \quad \hat{\mathcal{F}} = \emptyset$		...(27)
$\mu' = \mu[x_1 \mapsto \hat{v}]$		...(28)
Using (22), $\rho'(x_1) \sim \mu'(x_1)$		...(29)
From (24), (28), $\text{dom}(\rho') = \text{dom}(\rho) \cup x, \quad \text{dom}(\mu') = \text{dom}(\mu) \cup x$		...(30)
From (7), (30), $\text{dom}(\rho') = \text{dom}(\mu')$		...(31)
From (8), (29), (31),		
$\forall x' \in \text{dom}(\rho'), \rho'(x') = \mu'(x')$		...(32)
From STORE_SIM using (21), (23), $\rho' \sim \mu'$	Consequent a	
From EMP_OBS, $\cdot \sim \cdot$		...(33)
From NON_EMP_OBS using (22), (24), (27), (33), $(v \cdot) \sim (\hat{v} \cdot)$	Consequent b	
From (24), (27) $\mathcal{G} = \hat{\mathcal{F}}$	Consequent b	

Induction cases:

T-SEQ

$\rho \models \Gamma$	Antecedant 1	...(1)
$\mu \models \Gamma$	Antecedant 2	...(2)
$\rho \sim \mu$	Antecedant 3	...(3)
$\Gamma \vdash_p s_1; s_2 \mid \Gamma'$	Antecedant 4	...(4)
$\rho \vdash_p s_1; s_2 \Downarrow \rho', \mathcal{T}, \mathcal{O}, \mathcal{G}$	Antecedant 5	...(5)
$\mu \vdash_p s_1; s_2 \Downarrow \mu', \hat{\mathcal{O}}, \hat{\mathcal{F}}$	Antecedant 6	...(6)
From inversion of T-SEQ using (4),		
$\Gamma \vdash_p s_1 \mid \Gamma_1$		...(7)
$\Gamma_1 \vdash_p s_2 \mid \Gamma'$		...(8)
From inversion of A-SEQ using (5),		
$\rho \vdash_p s_1 \Downarrow \rho_1, \mathcal{T}_1, \mathcal{O}', \mathcal{G}'$		...(9)
$\rho_1 \vdash_p s_2 \Downarrow \rho', \mathcal{T}_2, \mathcal{O}'', \mathcal{G}''$		...(10)
From inversion of R-SEQ using (6),		
$\mu \vdash_p s_1 \Downarrow \mu_1, \hat{\mathcal{O}}', \hat{\mathcal{F}}'$		...(11)
$\mu_1 \vdash_p s_2 \Downarrow \mu', \hat{\mathcal{O}}'', \hat{\mathcal{F}}''$		...(12)
From IH using (1), (2), (3), (7), (9), (11):		
$\rho_1 \sim \mu_1$		...(13)
$\mathcal{O}' \sim \hat{\mathcal{O}}'$		...(14)
$\mathcal{G}' = \hat{\mathcal{F}}$		...(15)
From Lemma 9 using (1), (7), (9), $\rho_1 \models \Gamma_1$		...(16)
From Lemma 11 using (2), (7), (11), $\mu_1 \models \Gamma_1$		...(17)
From IH using (16), (17), (13), (8), (10), (12):		
$\rho' \sim \mu'$	Consequent a	...(18)
$\mathcal{O}'' \sim \hat{\mathcal{O}}''$		...(19)
$\mathcal{G}'' = \hat{\mathcal{F}}''$		...(20)
From Lemma 14 using (14), (19), $\mathcal{O}' \mathcal{O}'' \sim \hat{\mathcal{O}}' \hat{\mathcal{O}}''$	Consequent b	
From Lemma 16 using (15), (20), $\mathcal{G}' \mathcal{G}'' = \hat{\mathcal{F}}' \hat{\mathcal{F}}''$	Consequent c	

T-AS

$\rho \models \Gamma$	Antecedant 1	...(1)
$\mu \models \Gamma$	Antecedant 2	...(2)
$\rho \sim \mu$	Antecedant 3	...(3)
$\Gamma \vdash \text{as}(p, s) \mid \Gamma'$	Antecedant 4	...(4)
$\rho \vdash \text{as}(p, s) \Downarrow \rho', \mathcal{O}$	Antecedant 5	...(5)
$\mu \vdash \text{as}(p, s) \Downarrow \mu', \hat{\mathcal{O}}$	Antecedant 6	...(6)

From inversion of T-AS using (5),

$$\Gamma \vdash_p s \mid \Gamma' \quad \dots(7)$$

From inversion of A-AS using (5),

$$\rho \vdash_p s \Downarrow \rho', \mathcal{T}, \mathcal{O}, \mathcal{G} \quad \dots(8)$$

From inversion of R-AS using (6),

$$\mu \vdash_p s \Downarrow \mu', \hat{\mathcal{O}}, \hat{\mathcal{F}} \quad \dots(9)$$

From IH using (1), (2), (3), (7), (8), (9):

$$\rho' \sim \mu' \quad \text{Consequent a} \quad \dots(10)$$

$$\text{and } \mathcal{O}' \sim \hat{\mathcal{O}}' \quad \text{Consequent b}$$

$$\text{and } \mathcal{G}' = \hat{\mathcal{F}}' \quad \text{Consequent c}$$

T-ANNOT_SEQ

$\rho \models \Gamma$	Antecedant 1	...(1)
$\mu \models \Gamma$	Antecedant 2	...(2)
$\rho \sim \mu$	Antecedant 3	...(3)
$\Gamma \vdash S_1; S_2 \mid \Gamma'$	Antecedant 4	...(4)
$\rho \vdash S_1; S_2 \Downarrow \rho', \mathcal{O}$	Antecedant 5	...(5)
$\mu \vdash S_1; S_2 \Downarrow \mu', \hat{\mathcal{O}}$	Antecedant 6	...(6)
From inversion of T-ANNOT_SEQ using (4),		
$\Gamma \vdash S_1 \mid \Gamma_1$		...(7)
$\Gamma_1 \vdash S_2 \mid \Gamma'$		...(8)
From inversion of A-ANNOT_SEQ using (5),		
$\rho \vdash S_1 \Downarrow \rho_1, \mathcal{T}_1, \mathcal{O}', \mathcal{G}'$		...(9)
$\rho_1 \vdash S_2 \Downarrow \rho', \mathcal{T}_2, \mathcal{O}'', \mathcal{G}''$		...(10)
From inversion of R-ANNOT_SEQ using (6),		
$\mu \vdash S_1 \Downarrow \mu_1, \hat{\mathcal{O}}', \hat{\mathcal{F}}'$		...(11)
$\mu_1 \vdash S_2 \Downarrow \mu', \hat{\mathcal{O}}'', \hat{\mathcal{F}}''$		...(12)
From IH using (1), (2), (3), (7), (9), (11):		
$\rho_1 \sim \mu_1$		...(13)
$\mathcal{O}' \sim \hat{\mathcal{O}}'$		...(14)
$\mathcal{G}' = \hat{\mathcal{F}}'$		...(15)
From Lemma 9 using (1), (7), (9), $\rho_1 \models \Gamma_1$		...(16)
From Lemma 11 using (2), (7), (11), $\mu_1 \models \Gamma_1$		...(17)
From IH using (16), (17), (13), (8), (10), (12):		
$\rho' \sim \mu'$	Consequent a	...(18)
$\mathcal{O}'' \sim \hat{\mathcal{O}}''$		...(19)
$\mathcal{G}'' = \hat{\mathcal{F}}''$		...(20)
From Lemma 14 using (14), (19), $\mathcal{O}' \mathcal{O}'' \sim \hat{\mathcal{O}}' \hat{\mathcal{O}}''$	Consequent b	
From Lemma 16 using (15), (20), $\mathcal{G}' \mathcal{G}'' = \hat{\mathcal{F}}' \hat{\mathcal{F}}''$	Consequent c	

T-IF

$\rho \models \Gamma$	Antecedant 1	...(1)
$\mu \models \Gamma$	Antecedant 2	...(2)
$\rho \sim \mu$	Antecedant 3	...(3)
$\Gamma \vdash_p \text{if}(e, S_1, S_2) \mid \Gamma'$	Antecedant 4	...(4)
$\rho \vdash_p \text{if}(e, S_1, S_2) \Downarrow \rho', \mathcal{O}$	Antecedant 5	...(5)
$\mu \vdash_p \text{if}(e, S_1, S_2) \Downarrow \mu', \hat{\mathcal{O}}$	Antecedant 6	...(6)
Inverting (4) with rule T-IF		
$\Gamma \vdash_p e : \text{bool}_p, p$		...(7)
$\Gamma \vdash S_1 \mid \Gamma_1$		...(8)
$\Gamma \vdash S_2 \mid \Gamma_2$		...(9)
From inversion of A-IF using (5),		
$\rho \vdash_p e \Downarrow v$		...(10)
From inversion of R-IF using (5),		
$\mu \vdash_p e \Downarrow \hat{v}$		...(11)
From Lemma 12 using (1), (2), (3), (7), (10), (11),		
$v \sim \hat{v}$		...(12)
Depending on the value of $\text{istrue}(v)$ we have the following two cases :		
Case1: $\text{istrue}(v)$		
From (12), $\text{istrue}(\hat{v})$		...(13)
$S = S_1$		...(14)
From inversion of A-IF using (5),		
$\rho \vdash_p S \Downarrow \rho', \mathcal{T}, \mathcal{O}, \mathcal{G}$		...(15)
From inversion of R-IF using (5),		
$\mu \vdash_p S \Downarrow \mu', \hat{\mathcal{O}}, \hat{\mathcal{F}}$		...(16)
From IH using (1), (2), (3), (8), (15), (16),		
$\rho' \sim \mu'$		...(17)
$\mathcal{O} \sim \hat{\mathcal{O}} \quad \mathcal{G} = \hat{\mathcal{F}}$		...(18)
$\rho \vdash \text{if}(e, S_1, S_2) \Downarrow \rho', \mathcal{T}, \mathcal{O}, \mathcal{G}$		
$\mu \vdash \text{if}(e, S_1, S_2) \Downarrow \mu', \hat{\mathcal{O}}, \hat{\mathcal{F}}$		
Consequence follows from (17), (18)		
Case2: $\neg \text{istrue}(v)$		
From (12), $\neg \text{istrue}(\hat{v})$		...(19)
$S = S_2$		...(20)
From inversion of A-IF using (5),		
$\rho \vdash_p S \Downarrow \rho', \mathcal{T}, \mathcal{O}, \mathcal{G}$		...(21)
From inversion of R-IF using (5),		
$\mu \vdash_p S \Downarrow \mu', \hat{\mathcal{O}}, \hat{\mathcal{F}}$		...(22)
From IH using (1), (2), (3), (9), (21), (22),		
$\rho' \sim \mu'$		...(23)
$\mathcal{O} \sim \hat{\mathcal{O}} \quad \mathcal{G} = \hat{\mathcal{F}}$		...(24)
$\rho \vdash \text{if}(e, S_1, S_2) \Downarrow \rho', \mathcal{T}, \mathcal{O}, \mathcal{G}$		
$\mu \vdash \text{if}(e, S_1, S_2) \Downarrow \mu', \hat{\mathcal{O}}, \hat{\mathcal{F}}$		
Consequence follows from (23), (24)		

T-FOR: We prove this case by induction on $n_2 - n_1$

Case: $n_2 - n_1 < 0$

In this case, consequence (a) follows from E-FOR_EXIT and R-FOR_EXIT with $\rho' = \rho$ and $\mu' = \mu$.
Consequence (b) follows from E-FOR_EXIT, R-FOR_EXIT and EMP_OBS with $\mathcal{O} = \emptyset$ and $\hat{\mathcal{O}} = \emptyset$.
Consequence (c) follows from E-FOR_EXIT, R-FOR_EXIT and EMP_EFF with $\mathcal{G} = \emptyset$ and $\hat{\mathcal{F}} = \emptyset$.

We now do induction for the case of $n_2 - n_1 \geq 0$.

Base Case: $n_2 - n_1 = 0$

$\rho \sim \mu$	Antecedent 3	...(1)
From inversion of STORE_SIM using (1), $\text{dom}(\rho) = \text{dom}(\mu)$		...(2)
and $\forall x \in \text{dom}(\rho), \rho(x) \sim \mu(x)$		...(3)
Let $\mu^* = \mu[x \mapsto (n_1, p)]$		...(4)
From V-NAT: $\vdash n_1 : \text{uint}_p$		...(5)
From V-REF1 using (6): $(n_1, p) \models \text{uint}_p, p$		...(6)
Let $\rho^* = \rho[x \mapsto \text{makeval}(n_1, p)]$		...(7)
From V-NAT: $\vdash n_1 : \text{uint}_p$		...(8)
Using (8) from Lemma 1:		
$\vdash \text{makeval}(n_1, p) : \text{uint}_p, p$		...(9)
From SIM_NO_ARR using (6) and (9):		
$\rho^*(x) \sim \mu^*(x)$		...(10)
Using (2), (4), (7), $\text{dom}(\rho^*) = \text{dom}(\mu^*) = \text{dom}(\rho) \cup x$		...(11)
Using (3), (10), (11), $\forall x \in \text{dom}(\rho^*), \rho^*(x) \sim \mu^*(x)$		...(12)
Using (11), (12) $\rho^* \sim \mu^*$		...(13)
$\Gamma \vdash_p \text{for } x \text{ in } [n_2, n_1] \text{ do } S \mid \Gamma$	Antecedent 4	...(14)
$\rho \models \Gamma$	Antecedent 1	...(15)
$\mu \models \Gamma$	Antecedent 2	...(16)
Inverting (14) with rule T-FOR:		
$\Gamma, x : (\text{uint}_p, p) \vdash S \mid \Gamma'$		...(17)
$\text{party}(S) = p$		...(18)
Using (7), (9) and (15) from rule NON-EMP:		
$\rho^* \models \Gamma, x : (\text{uint}_p, p)$		...(19)
Using (4), (6) and (16) from rule NON-EMP-REF:		
$\mu^* \models \Gamma, x : (\text{uint}_p, p)$		...(20)
From Lemma 11 using (17) and (21):		
$\mu^* \vdash S \downarrow \mu', \hat{\mathcal{O}}, \hat{\mathcal{F}}$		...(21)
From Lemma 9 using (17) and (20):		
$\rho^* \vdash S \downarrow \rho', \mathcal{T}, \mathcal{O}, \mathcal{G}$		...(22)
From IH using (19), (20), (10), (17), (21), (22)		
$\rho' \sim \mu'$		...(23)
$\mathcal{O} \sim \hat{\mathcal{O}} \quad \mathcal{G} = \hat{\mathcal{F}}$		...(24)
Let $n'_1 = n_1 + 1$		...(25)
Using (25), $n_2 - n'_1 < 0$		...(26)
From (26) using rule R-FOR_EXIT:		
$\mu' \vdash_p \text{for } x \text{ in } [n'_1, n_2] \text{ do } S \downarrow \mu', \emptyset, \emptyset$		...(27)
From (21) and (27) using rule R-FORI:		
$\mu \vdash_p \text{for } x \text{ in } [n_1, n_2] \text{ do } S \downarrow \mu', \hat{\mathcal{O}}, \hat{\mathcal{F}}$		...(28)
From (26) using rule A-FOR_EXIT:		
$\rho' \vdash_p \text{for } x \text{ in } [n'_1, n_2] \text{ do } S \downarrow \rho', _, \emptyset, \emptyset$		...(29)
From (22) and (29) using rule A-FORI:		
$\rho \vdash_p \text{for } x \text{ in } [n_1, n_2] \text{ do } S \downarrow \rho', _, \mathcal{O}, \mathcal{G}$		...(30)
Consequent (a) and (b) follows from (23) and (24).		

Induction Case: $n_2 - n_1 \geq 0$

$\rho \sim \mu$	Antecedent 3	...(1)
From inversion of STORE_SIM using (1), $\text{dom}(\rho) = \text{dom}(\mu)$		...(2)
and $\forall x \in \text{dom}(\rho), \rho(x) \sim \mu(x)$		...(3)
Let $\mu^* = \mu[x \mapsto (n_1, p)]$		...(4)
From V-NAT: $\vdash n_1 : \text{uint}_p$		...(5)
From V-REF1 using (6): $(n_1, p) \models \text{uint}_p, p$		...(6)
Let $\rho^* = \rho[x \mapsto \text{makeval}(n_1, p)]$		...(7)
From V-NAT: $\vdash n_1 : \text{uint}_p$		...(8)
Using (8) from Lemma 1:		
$\vdash \text{makeval}(n_1, p) : \text{uint}_p, p$		...(9)
From SIM_NO_ARR using (6) and (9):		
$\rho^*(x) \sim \mu^*(x)$		...(10)
Using (2), (4), (7), $\text{dom}(\rho^*) = \text{dom}(\mu^*) = \text{dom}(\rho) \cup x$		...(11)
Using (3), (10), (11), $\forall x \in \text{dom}(\rho^*), \rho^*(x) \sim \mu^*(x)$		...(12)
Using (11), (12) $\rho^* \sim \mu^*$		...(13)
$\Gamma \vdash_p \text{ for } x \text{ in } [n_2, n_1] \text{ do } S \mid \Gamma$	Antecedent 4	...(14)
$\rho \models \Gamma$	Antecedent 1	...(15)
$\mu \models \Gamma$	Antecedent 2	...(16)
Inverting (14) with rule T-FOR:		
$\Gamma, x : (\text{uint}_p, p) \vdash S \mid \Gamma'$		...(17)
$x \notin \Gamma$		...(18)
$\text{party}(S) = p$		...(19)
Using (7), (9) and (15) from rule NON-EMP:		
$\rho^* \models \Gamma, x : (\text{uint}_p, p)$		...(20)
Using (4), (6) and (16) from rule NON-EMP-REF:		
$\mu^* \models \Gamma, x : (\text{uint}_p, p)$		...(21)
From Lemma 11 using (17) and (21):		
$\mu^* \vdash S \downarrow \mu', \hat{\mathcal{O}}, \hat{\mathcal{F}}$		...(22)
From Lemma 9 using (17) and (20):		
$\rho^* \vdash S \downarrow \rho', _, \mathcal{O}, \mathcal{G}$		...(23)
From IH using (19), (20), (10), (17), (21), (22)		
$\rho' \sim \mu'$		...(24)
$\mathcal{O} \sim \hat{\mathcal{O}} \quad \mathcal{G} = \hat{\mathcal{F}}$		...(25)
Let $n'_1 = n_1 + 1$		...(26)
Using (17) from Lemma 5		
$\Gamma' \supseteq \Gamma, x : (\text{uint}_p, p)$		...(27)
$\Gamma' \supseteq \Gamma$		...(28)
From (23) and (28) using Lemma 4:		
$\mu' \models \Gamma$		...(29)
From (25) and (28) using Lemma 3:		
$\rho' \models \Gamma$		...(30)

From T-FOR using (17), (18), (19),
 $\Gamma \vdash_p$ for x in $[n'_1, n_2]$ do $S \mid \Gamma$... (31)
 Using (25), $n_2 - n'_1 < n_2 - n_1$... (32)
 From Lemma 11 using (29), (31)
 $\mu' \vdash_p$ for x in $[n'_1, n_2]$ do $S \downarrow \mu'', \hat{\mathcal{O}}', \hat{\mathcal{F}}'$... (33)
 $\mu'' \models \Gamma$... (34)
 From Lemma 9 using (30), (31)
 $\rho' \vdash_p$ for x in $[n'_1, n_2]$ do $S \Downarrow \rho'', _ , \mathcal{O}', \mathcal{G}'$... (35)
 $\rho'' \models \Gamma$... (36)
 From IH using (30), (29), (24), (31), (35), (33), (32)
 $\rho'' \sim \mu''$ Consequent a ... (37)
 $\mathcal{O}' \sim \hat{\mathcal{O}}' \quad \mathcal{G}' = \hat{\mathcal{F}}'$... (38)
 From R-FORI using (22), (33)
 $\mu \vdash_p$ for x in $[n_1, n_2]$ do $S \downarrow \mu'', \hat{\mathcal{O}}\hat{\mathcal{O}}', \hat{\mathcal{F}}\hat{\mathcal{F}}'$... (39)
 From A-FORI using (23), (35)
 $\rho \vdash_p$ for x in $[n_1, n_2]$ do $S \Downarrow \rho'', _ , \mathcal{O}\mathcal{O}', \mathcal{G}\mathcal{G}'$... (40)
 Consequent follows from (37)
 From Lemma 14 using (25), (38) $\mathcal{O} \mathcal{O}' \sim \hat{\mathcal{O}} \hat{\mathcal{O}}'$ Consequent b
 From Lemma 16 using (25), (38) $\mathcal{G} \mathcal{G}' = \hat{\mathcal{F}} \hat{\mathcal{F}}'$ Consequent c

□